

CCAIMB 2025

Proceedings of the Conference on Computational
and Artificial Intelligence for Mechanics and
Biomechanics

Porto, 18-19 September 2025

Editors:
Jorge Belinha
Ana Isabel Pais
Daniel Rodrigues
Marco Parente
Sérgio Tavares

Porto, 2025
Publisher: Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto (ISEP) ©
ISBN: 978-989-36167-5-8
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17131900>

Preface

The first Conference on Computational and Artificial Intelligence for Mechanics and Biomechanics (CCAIMB2025) took place from September 18 to 19, 2025, in Porto, Portugal. CCAIMB2025 featured relevant scientific activities, including plenary lectures, and mini-symposia presentations.

CCAIMB is a multidisciplinary gathering designed to discuss and explore the state-of-the-art in computational methods and artificial intelligence techniques in mechanics and biomechanics engineering. Consequently, scientists and engineers from various fields attended this conference, benefiting from the diverse technical program, which includes globally prominent plenary speakers and mini-symposia sessions with contributed papers.

CCAIMB2025 had 30 participants, distributed across 4 mini-symposia:

1. Computational Mechanics, Structures, and Materials
2. AI, Machine Learning, and Computational Methods
3. Biomedical Engineering and Healthcare Applications
4. Space, Robotics, and Design Optimization

A total of 25 abstracts were submitted and 23 were accepted. Concerning the regional distribution of participants, the majority came from Portugal with 20 participants. The remaining participants came from USA, France, Brazil and Croatia.

Porto,
September, 2025

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Sérgio Tavares*

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Keynote Speakers

- **Alexander Popp**
Full Professor of Computer-Based Simulation. University of the Bundeswehr Munich, Germany.
Title: Machine learning and computational contact mechanics – Dream team or nightmare?
- **Miguel Bessa**
Associate Professor of Engineering. School of Engineering – Brown University.
Title: Learning history-dependent material laws from a single experiment.
- **Jaime Cardoso**
Full Professor. Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering Faculty of Engineering – University of Porto.
Title: Visual Language Models: Challenges and Opportunities.
- **João Pedro Ferreira**
Head Data Scientist. DIGESTAID – Digestive Artificial Intelligence Development.
Title: Building a Data Framework for Medical Device Software Approval.

Involved Institutions

Institutional Organization

- Department of Mechanical Engineering - School of Engineering - Polytechnic of Porto (DEM-ISEP-IPP)
- Department of Mechanical Engineering - Faculty of Engineering - University of Porto (DEMec-FEUP)
- Department of Mechanical Engineering - University of Aveiro (DEM-UA)

Institutional Support

- FCT: Foundation for Science and Technology
- INEGI - Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering
- LAETA - Associate Laboratory of Energy, Transports and Aerospace
- Computational Mechanics Research Laboratory (CMech-Lab) - INEGI / ISEP
- Centre for Mechanical Technology and Automation (TEMA) - University of Aveiro
- Portuguese Biomechanics Society (SPB)

Sponsors

- ABREU

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Chapter 1

Abstracts of Oral Communications

Abstract This chapter includes all the abstracts of the oral communications submitted to CCAIMB2025. The topics cover all the sessions of CCAIMB2025: "Computational Mechanics, Structures, and Materials", "AI, Machine Learning, and Computational Methods", "Biomedical Engineering and Healthcare Applications", and "Space, Robotics, and Design Optimization".

1.1 Work A001

Characterization of elastomeric thin films for the design and computational modelling of soft robotic actuators

Rui A F Pereira ^{1,2}, Stefan del Rossi ¹, Elza M M Fonseca ^{*2}, and Silvia Schintke ^{*1}

¹ Laboratory of Applied NanoSciences, HEIG-VD / HES-SO University of Applied Sciences and Arts, Western Switzerland, Switzerland

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, School of Engineering, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal

* Corresponding author's emails: elz@isep.ipp.pt, silvia.schintke@heig-vd.ch

Abstract:

Thin elastomeric materials, such as thin films or thin membranes of silicone or silicone composites, have promising potential for applications in the field of flexible actuators and sensors in the fields of wearable electronics for health, sports, or robotics applications. For example, in dielectric actuators (DEA), a thin elastomer film is sandwiched between electrodes and deformed by the Maxwell stress when a high voltage is applied between the electrodes [1-3]. However, elastomeric materials show hyperelastic behaviour, such that their response to external stress strongly depends on the relative stretch or compression of the materials. Therefore, given the efficient development of thin film sensors and actuators based on elastomers, a combination of experimental and modelling approaches is relevant for determining their hyperelastic properties. In this work, we have determined the hyperelastic properties of thin elastomeric materials using tensile measurement using an adapted linear motorized mechanical system equipped with a force sensor. Through the hyperelastic models Neo-Hookean, Mooney-Rivlin, and Ogden, we fit the obtained force-displacement curves comparing various non-linear models, to determine the mechanical properties. Finally, finite element modelling in Ansys is used to model 3D deformations of thin films. This validated modeling framework lays the foundation for future parametric studies, where the influence of design variables on DEA performance can be systematically explored.

Acknowledgements: This work has been financially supported by HES-SO, project FLEXPAC (grant-number IA-DEPOT23-125). R.AF Pereira kindly acknowledges a grant from the Swiss European Mobility Programme, SEMP. R.AF Pereira would also like to thank LAETA/INEGI for the support provided for the conference registration.

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1.2 Work A002

Computational Thermal and Mechanical Study of Wooden Connections in Single Shear

João C P Aguiar ¹, Elza M M Fonseca ^{*,1}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, School of Engineering, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal

* Corresponding author's emails: elz@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract:

This work will focus on a specific type of wooden connections and the available analysis methods, such as numerical methods, including the application of the finite element method, and analytical methods. The objective is to study the behaviour of wooden connections with the other materials that compose them, such as steel and gypsum board, and the external actions to which they will be subjected (fire and general mechanical loading). The wooden connections to be studied aim to guarantee the greatest shear resistance, so they will be made up of steel dowels, chosen according to their diameter. The state of the art for the analysis of this type of connection is still limited, therefore, this study will allow a more in-depth knowledge of single shear connections when subjected to fire. It is intended that the constituent components of the connections to be developed are dimensioned following simplified equations, based on Eurocodes [1-4]. The design planned for the wooden connection, under certain conditions, will be subject to safety verification through the application of finite element analysis. The models under study will be analysed under thermal and mechanical action to evaluate the resistance capacity of the connection to fire [5-6].

Acknowledgements: João C P Aguiar would like to thank LAETA/INEGI for the support provided for the conference registration.

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1.3 Work A003

Hybrid AI–Physics Coupling for Multibody Dynamics with Contact

Mohammad ISSA ^{*,1}, Xavier Merlhiot ¹, and Anders Thorin ¹

¹ Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, List, F-91120, Palaiseau, France

* Corresponding author's emails: mohammad.issa2@cea.fr

Abstract:

In physical simulation, machine learning models from artificial intelligence (AI) are increasingly used as global surrogates for traditional PDE-based approaches. These methods can significantly reduce computational costs but are often limited in their integration with classical solvers, especially for systems exhibiting non-smooth dynamics such as mechanical contact. This research explores a hybrid numerical coupling between a multibody dynamics solver and AI based components within a framework that includes intermittent contacts. We propose a methodology where an AI surrogate replaces part of the physical system while remaining tightly integrated with a classical model. The hybrid system is solved using an implicit time integration method adapted for non-smooth mechanics, with contact constraints formulated as Signorini-type inclusions. The neural model is queried directly during each iteration, allowing non-intrusive integration into the solver. A test case involving beam–mass collision validates the feasibility of this intimate AI–mechanics coupling. Replacing the neural network with a finite element reference confirms the physical correctness of the nonlinear behavior reproduced by the surrogate model. This work demonstrates that structure-preserving hybrid simulations combining AI surrogates and classical solvers can be achieved robustly, even in the presence of contact and other non-smooth phenomena.

1.4 Work A004

3D Facial Soft Tissue Changes After Orthodontic Treatment

Višnja Katić ^{*1,2}, Boris Gašparović ³, Jonatan Lerga ³ and Doris Šimac ^{1,3}

¹ Department of Orthodontics, Faculty of Dental Medicine, University of Rijeka, Croatia

² Department of Dental Medicine, Clinical Hospital Centre Rijeka, Croatia

³ Faculty of Engineering, University of Rijeka, Croatia

* Corresponding author's email: visnja.katic@fdmri.uniri.hr

Abstract:

3D facial scans of 18 patients (7 girls, 11 boys) prior to and after one year of the Twin block treatment were captured using the Arc scanner (Bellus 3D, version 1.6.2, Inc., Campbell, USA) along with the Bellus3D software. Measurements were taken in millimetres, specifically the distance between the tragus and the pogonion, to assess soft tissue changes related to the effective length of the mandible. The exact "single source, all destinations" algorithm was employed [1]. The Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm was used to refine alignment by minimizing the squared distances between corresponding points in two-point clouds—typically referred to as the target and reference model [2]. We manually selected regions and points near the eyes and at the center of the forehead, as these areas tend to remain relatively stable from childhood through adulthood [3]. A distance map was generated by computing point-to-point distances across the facial surface, which were then visualized using a color-coded heat map. For distance measurements we used Hausdorff distance which is a commonly used metric for comparing two 3D surfaces or point clouds [4]. There is a high statistically significant difference in the results of the paired t-test for the measurements of the soft tissue changes of the effective length of the mandible. On average, for first measurement (T0) mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) was 148.71 ± 26.43 mm; for second measurement (T1), M and SD was 153.16 ± 9.86 , at $p < 0.001$. The color-coded heat map indicated that the most significant soft tissue changes following treatment were observed in the protrusion of the chin and the elongation of the mandible. The significant increase in the effective length of the mandible measured on the soft tissue is evidence of the appliance's effect on the soft tissues, contributing to a more harmonious facial appearance.

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1.5 Work A005

Artificial intelligence-driven in silico simulation for prediction of anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction clinical outcomes

Orlando Branco Simões ^{1,3}, António Manuel Ramos ², and José António Simões ^{*,3}

¹ Unidade Local de Saúde Gaia-Espinho, Vila Nova de Gaia, Portugal

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Aveiro, Portugal

³ ESAD.IDEA – Investigação em Design e Arte, Matosinhos, Portugal

* Corresponding author's email: josesimoes@esad.pt

Abstract:

An innovative project is under development that intersects Anterior Cruciate Ligament Reconstruction (ACLR) with artificial intelligence (AI) machine learning and in silico simulation for proposing a predictive model for ACLR clinical outcomes [1]. By integrating patient's clinical and specific surgery data in machine learning models/algorithms and computational simulation, it is possible to deliver insights to improve patient selection, surgical decision-making, pre and post operative management to enhance the efficiency of ACLR procedures. The inclusion of AI-driven in silico simulation into the ACLR management is an innovative element of the design approach, as it offers additional possibilities in the overall analysis of all different domains of ACLR surgery and particularly decision-making that is not possible solely with machine learning driven clinical data per se, surgical planning, especially for complex surgeries that pose difficult decisions to the surgical team. In this way, computational finite element results, including those of published studies, will be integrated and driven by machine learning models and algorithms, aiming to correlate the outputs of AI via clinical data and via biomechanical in silico factors. The following main research question is to be investigated: How effectively can machine learning algorithms predict post-operative clinical outcomes of ACLR based on preoperative patient data?

Acknowledgments: COMPETE2023-FEDER-00867200, under Project N° 15022, for financial support.

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[1] O B Simões, A M Ramos, and J A Simões. Que impacto terá a inteligência artificial e a simulação in silico em decisões clínicas e cirúrgicas no tratamento de lesões do ligamento cruzado anterior? *Tecnometal*, 267:26–45, 2024.

1.6 Work A006**Graph Recurrent Neural Network-based Material Patches for Implicit Finite Element Solutions**Rui Barreira ¹, Bernardo P. Ferreira ², and Miguel A. Bessa ^{*,2}¹ Department of Mechanical and Process Engineering, ETH Zurich, Switzerland² Brown University, Providence, RI, USA

* Corresponding author's email: miguel_bessa@brown.edu

Abstract:

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) have long been established as robust constitutive modeling tools, able to fit a wide range of material behaviors; yet, they cannot act as independent surrogate models for finite element (FE) simulators. This work introduces FE material patches into the implicit solution of quasi-static mechanical boundary value problems, combining recurrent neural networks (RNNs) into the message-passing layers of graph neural networks (GNNs) to replace explicit constitutive models and computationally intensive matrix operations. FE material patches, i.e., blocks of elements, are represented as a graph, with the mesh connectivity encoded as edge features and the displacements and reaction forces at the boundary as nodal features. By employing RNNs as feature update functions, displacements are mapped directly to forces, allowing for a seamless integration within the implicit FE solver, as well as the explicit computation of consistent spatial tangents by automatic differentiation. The model is first evaluated on homogeneous material patches under isotropic elasticity/hyperelasticity with varying boundary displacements and patch resolutions, before being fitted to history-dependent behavior. Finally, custom layers are integrated within the architecture to ensure force equilibration and prevent rigid body motion.

1.7 Work A007

Protective Face Masks: An Approach to Customized Designs

Inês C.J. Barbosa ^{1,2}, Ana S.A. Gonçalves ¹, and Maria A.R. Loja ^{*,1,2}

¹ CIMOSM, Centro de Investigação em Modelação e Otimização de Sistemas Multifuncionais, Instituto Superior de Engenharia de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

² IDMEC, Instituto Superior de Engenharia de Lisboa, Instituto Politécnico de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

* Corresponding author's email: amelia.loja@isel.pt

Abstract:

This study explores the modeling and design of customizable protective nose masks that can be fabricated using additive manufacturing techniques. This type of mask is in general needed for athletes, workers, and for individuals who have suffered a nose injury or may potentially suffer an impact in that region. These devices may be considered a preventive measure, part of individual protection equipment, or, in case of a previous local injury, their use is considered to provide protection to enhance the recovery process. This study was initiated with the development of a 3D computational model using computed tomography images, and some specialized open-source software such as InVesalius, 3D Slicer and Meshlab. The geometrical modelling of the protective nose masks was then developed using SolidWorks. Impact analyses, considering a set of preliminary material solutions, were conducted to simulate the impact of an external object with these devices, considering not only the overall stiffness performance of the mask but also considering the stress threshold value of 10 kPa, identified by Cao et al. [1], above which brain injuries may occur. The studies conducted demonstrate that, besides the advantages of customizing these masks for a better fit, different purposes and, therefore, different geometrical and material designs should be considered.

References:

[1] Y. Cao, Y. Liu, L. Tang, Z. Jiang, Z. Liu, L. Zhou e B. Yang. Quantitative assessment of brain injury and concussion induced by an unintentional soccer ball impact. *Injury*, 55(8), 2024

1.8 Work A008

Customized Protective Helmets: Reverse Engineering and Design

Ana S.A. Gonçalves ¹, Inês C.J. Barbosa ^{1,2}, and Maria A.R. Loja ^{*,1,2}

¹ CIMOSM, Centro de Investigação em Modelação e Otimização de Sistemas Multifuncionais, Instituto Superior de Engenharia de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

² IDMEC, Instituto Superior de Engenharia de Lisboa, Instituto Politécnico de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

* Corresponding author's email: amelia.loja@isel.pt

Abstract:

This work presents an exploratory study on the modeling and design of customized protective helmets, which can be subsequently produced via additive manufacturing. Helmets may be found in many different areas, ranging from individual protection devices used in industrial environments to athletes' protection devices, and also for various healthcare aims. In the present study, it was considered the development of a customized helmet to be used in sports. The dataflow of this work started with a combined reverse engineering process using medical computed tomography images and photogrammetry to achieve the required completeness of the computational model. These two acquisition techniques were used along with specialized open source software such as InVesalius, 3D Slicer and Meshlab to obtain the 3D surface head. The geometrical modelling of the protective helmets was then developed using SolidWorks. Impact analyses, considering a set of preliminary material solutions, were conducted to simulate the impact of the helmets with an external object. To assess the overall performance of the helmets, besides stiffness requirements, the stress threshold value of 10 kPa, identified by Cao et al. [1], was adopted, considering this represents the value above which brain injuries may occur. The studies conducted demonstrate that besides the advantages of customized helmets, further studies are desirable for enhanced performance and protection characteristics.

References:

[1] Y. Cao, Y. Liu, L. Tang, Z. Jiang, Z. Liu, L. Zhou e B. Yang. Quantitative assessment of brain injury and concussion induced by an unintentional soccer ball impact. *Injury*, 55(8), 2024

1.9 Work A009

A Stacked Deep Learning Approach for Optimized Retinal Imaging Analysis in Diabetes Care

Pedro Rebolo ^{*,1}, Eduardo Carvalho ¹, Guilherme Barbosa ¹, Bruno Areias ¹, Ana Guerra ¹, Sónia Torres-Costa ³, Nilza Ramião ¹, Manuel Falcão ^{3,4} and Marco Parente ^{1,2}

¹ INEGI - Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Porto, Portugal

² DEMec, Faculty of Engineering - University of Porto, Porto, Portugal

³ Department of Ophthalmology, Centro Hospitalar Universitario Sao Joao, Alameda Prof Hernani Monteiro, Porto, 4200-319, Portugal

⁴ Department of Surgery and Physiology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Porto - FMUP, Alameda Prof Hernani Monteiro, Porto, 4200-319, Portugal

* Corresponding author's email: prebolo@inegi.up.pt

Abstract:

Retinal disorders such as diabetic macular edema (DME) and macular edema from retinal vein occlusion (RVO) present overlapping features in OCT scans, particularly increased retinal thickness. This diagnostic similarity poses a challenge in clinical settings, especially for non specialist practitioners. While OCT remains a gold standard for non-invasive retinal imaging, the application of deep learning—particularly for RVO detection—remains underexplored [1, 2]. This study introduces a stacked convolutional neural network (CNN) approach to enhance the classification of OCT images and distinguish between DME and RVO. Pre-trained models (VGG-16, VGG-19, and ResNet50) were fine-tuned using the publicly available Kermamy dataset [3] and further trained on a private OCT dataset. Four stacked configurations were evaluated: VGG-16 + VGG-19, VGG-16 + ResNet50, VGG-19 + ResNet50, and a combined model integrating all three networks. Performance was assessed using metrics including accuracy, precision, recall, F2 score, and AU-ROC. Results demonstrate that stacking improves model robustness and feature discrimination, offering a promising AI-based solution for more accurate and accessible retinal disease diagnosis.

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[3] Kermamy, D.S.; Goldbaum, M.; Cai, W.; Valentim, C.C.S.; Liang, H.; Baxter, S.L.; McKeown, A.; Yang, G.; Wu, X.; Yan, F.; et al. Identifying Medical Diagnoses and Treatable Diseases by Image-Based Deep Learning. *Cell* 2018, 172, 1122–1131.e9. 303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2018.02.010>

1.10 Work A010

Evaluation of the Mechanical Performance of Biodegradable Meshes for Pelvic Organ Prolapse Treatment

N. M. Ferreira ^{*1,2}, A. R. Silva ^{1,2}, M. Parente ^{1,2}, and Elisabete Silva ²

¹ Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto, 4200-465, Porto, Portugal

² LAETA, INEGI, 4200-465, Porto, Portugal

* Corresponding author's email: nmferreira@inegi.up.pt

Abstract:

Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP) is a prevalent condition among women globally, arising from weakened pelvic floor structures. Traditional surgical treatments frequently utilize synthetic meshes for reinforcement; however, these materials can cause complications such as erosion and chronic pain [1]. Consequently, biodegradable mesh implants have emerged as promising alternatives due to their improved mechanical biocompatibility. This study investigates the mechanical properties of biodegradable polycaprolactone (PCL) meshes through experimental analyses and computational modeling, aiming to enhance their efficacy for POP repair. The study aims to evaluate the mechanical behavior of biodegradable PCL meshes versus native vaginal tissue, focusing on how different mesh geometries affect performance and validating computational models for future POP repair applications. Biodegradable PCL meshes with quadratic and cross-shaped geometries were created using melt electrowriting with a filament thickness of 240 μm . Uniaxial tensile and ball burst tests were conducted on these meshes and compared to sow vaginal tissue. Numerical simulations in Abaqus/Explicit were developed to assess tissue-mesh interaction, validated against experimental data. Results from ball burst testing demonstrated that biodegradable PCL meshes increased the maximum force resistance by approximately 14–20% compared to native vaginal tissue alone. Specifically, the cross-shaped mesh significantly outperformed the quadratic mesh, providing enhanced mechanical reinforcement by up to 30%. Numerical simulations closely matched the experimental results, with discrepancies of around 6% for vaginal tissue, 7% for mesh implants alone, and approximately 14% for mesh-reinforced tissue. These computational models effectively predicted mechanical behavior, indicating their potential in reducing the reliance on extensive in vivo testing. The study concludes that biodegradable PCL meshes present a highly promising alternative to conventional synthetic meshes for POP treatment. Future research should prioritize in vivo studies to thoroughly evaluate long-term biocompatibility, degradation profiles, and clinical outcomes.

References:

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1.11 Work A011

Development of Melt-Electrowritten Mesh Implants with Antistatic Features for Hernia Repair

E. Antoniadis^{1,2,*}, M.P. Ferraz¹, M. Parente^{1,2}, M.E.T. Silva²

¹ Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal

² LAETA, INEGI, Porto, Portugal

* Corresponding author's email: up202408581@edu.fe.up.pt

Abstract:

Hernia is a medical condition that significantly affects patients' quality of life, where an organ protrudes through the wall of the cavity that is normally contained, due to a weakness or opening in the abdominal wall. Surgery is commonly used to treat hernias by placing specialized meshes to support the abdominal wall, but it frequently leads to complications such as pain, infections, and even the need for revision surgeries. According to the Food and Drug Administration, hernia recurrence rates can reach up to 11%, surgical site infections occur in up to 21% of cases, and chronic pain incidence ranges from 0.3% to 68%. These statistics underscore the urgent need for better mesh technologies to reduce complications. This study introduces an early-stage, antistatic melt-electrowritten mesh for hernia repair. Melt Electrowriting is a promising method that enables the precise placement of thin fibers, resembling the fibrous part of the natural extracellular matrix. The study investigated the effect of incorporating the antistatic agent Hostastat® FA 38 (HT) at concentrations of 0.03, 0.06, and 0.1wt% on the fiber diameter and mechanical properties of Polycaprolactone (PCL) meshes. Adding HT reduced fiber diameter by 14–17%, 39–45%, and 65–66%, depending on the square or sinusoidal pattern (1.5 mm pore size). The smaller fiber diameter was associated with higher tensile strength and Young's modulus, as confirmed by uniaxial tensile tests. PCL/HT meshes outperformed pure PCL ones with similar diameters and geometries. Cytotoxicity tests, using the resazurin assay, indicated no cytotoxic effects at any HT concentration. Both sterilization methods (Ethanol+UV and UV only) showed similar results, with no significant differences. Incorporating HT into PCL meshes produces thinner, more stable filaments with improved mechanical performance and no cytotoxicity, making them promising for hernia repair. Future research on polymer-additive interactions could further optimize their mechanical and biological properties.

Keywords: Hernia Repair; Biodegradable Mesh Implants; Melt Electrowriting; Antistatic Agent; Cytotoxicity.

1.12 Work A013

Comparison between FEM and a meshfree method for impact analysis of an adhesive joint

L.D.C. Ramalho ^{1,*}, Diogo C. Gonçalves ², R.D.S.G. Campilho ^{1,2}, Jorge Belinha ^{1,2}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, School of Engineering, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal

² INEGI, Institute of Mechanical Engineering, Rua Dr. Roberto Frias, 4200-465 Porto, Portugal

* Corresponding author's email: ldr@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract:

Considering the widespread use of adhesive joints, it is important to develop tools for their analysis. Currently, The Finite Element Method (FEM) is the most commonly used method to analyze adhesive joints. However, it is also important to explore different numerical methods, like meshfree methods, to learn if it is advantageous to use them in the analysis of adhesive joints. The static behavior of adhesive joints is a well-studied field, comparatively their behavior under impact is still not as widely understood. Considering some of the applications of adhesive joints, like wind turbine blades, cars, or airplanes, it is important to understand well their behavior under impact, so it is important that the tools used for numerical analysis are well developed. This work aims at performing a numerical analysis of an adhesive joint under impact using the FEM and a meshfree method, the Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM). The use of two different numerical methods is related to the goal of comparing them with each other and with experimental results. The comparison includes stress analysis in the adhesive layer and joint strength prediction using the Intensity of Singular Stress Fields (ISSF) criterion. The ISSF criterion consists in predicting joint failure based on the stress singularity that arises at the adhesive/adherent interface corner.

1.13 Work A014

Graph Visualization and Centrality Analysis of Discrete Variables Correlation from Whole-Body Center of Mass Movement During Standard MVJ

Carlos Rodrigues^{1,2,*}, Miguel Correia^{1,2}, João Abrantes³, Marco Rodrigues⁴, and Jurandir Nadal⁵

¹ Doctoral Program in Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Portugal

² Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science, Portugal

³ MovLab, CICANT, Lusófona University, Lisbon, Portugal

⁴ Department of Electronic and Systems, Federal University of Pernambuco, Recife, Brazil

⁵ Biomedical Engineering Program, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

* Corresponding author's email: c.rodrigues@fe.up.pt

Abstract:

Lower limb force development is determinant for human walking ability with impact on our autonomy, self-esteem and health preservation. On natural human movement, the neuromuscular system presents a central role at the control of the muscles acting the skeletal system, along with the proprioceptive system to ensure kinesthesia [1]. Although isolated isometric, concentric and eccentric forms of muscle action have gathered larger research attention, natural form of muscle function involves the use of muscle stretch-shortening cycle (SSC) with preactivated muscle stretch preceding muscle contraction for efficient muscle action at submaximal activities such as gait and powerful actions at maximal activities such as running and jumping [2]. Thus, despite muscle SSC can be observed at gait and running, its higher expression and assessability is performed on standard maximum vertical jump (MVJ) using whole-body (WB) weight for long countermovement (CM) on countermovement jump (CMJ) and short CM on drop jump (DJ) from 40 cm step for comparison with squat jump (SJ) and no CM, assessing long and short lower limb muscle SSC contribution in relation to no SSC condition for lower limb force development to propel WB center of mass (COM). Data processing pipeline focused on a set of 51 dynamic and kinematic variables from WB movement on a sample of 198 trials with the selection of the highest MVJ from 3 CMJ, DJ and SJ repetitions performed by a group of 6 untrained (U) and 16 trained (T) subjects. These variables, grouped into three communities of (i) time-force-impulse (t-F-I), (ii) force-velocity-power (F-v-P), and (iii) force displacement-work (F-z-W) were subjected to bivariate correlation for each sample of U, T and MVJ type. Statistical significative correlations were detected at 5% significance level and graph analysis was performed with degree of centrality and graph density assessment. Whereas the global subgraphs densities presented similar profiles for U and T associated to the variable structure at each MVJ type, individual subgraphs densities presented clear differences at CMJ, DJ, and SJ for U and T. Thus, while F, t-F, I and F-W presented similar comparisons of CMJ, DJ and SJ graph densities at U and T, the remaining variable combinations presented distinct graph densities at U and T for CMJ, DJ, SJ.

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1.14 Work A015

Dynamic characterization of thermoformed magneto-piezoelectret sensors using laser vibrometry and motionscope

Leonardo S. Caires ^{1,2,*}, Amélia M. Santos ², Elvio P. Silva ^{1,2}, Ronaldo M. Lima ^{2,3}, Polyane A. Santos ^{1,2}, Rui A. S. Moreira ², Sergio M. O. Tavares ², Ruy A. P. Altafim ⁴

¹ Department of Electrical Engineering, Federal Institute of Bahia, Brazil ² Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Aveiro, Portugal ³ Department of Physics, Federal Institute of Sergipe, Brazil ⁴ Computer System Department, Informatic Center, Federal University of Paraiba, Brazil

* Corresponding author's email: leonardocaires@ua.pt

Abstract:

This study presents a dynamic characterization of thermoformed magneto-piezoelectret (TMPs) sensors, innovative multifunctional materials that feature air channels and integrated magnetic layers. These sensors combine piezoelectric and magnetoelectric properties, making them promising for energy harvesting, structural health monitoring, and wearable devices [1, 2]. TMPs were fabricated from FEP films laminated with PTFE molds, creating tubular channels coated with magnetic tapes following the method of Altafim et al., [3, 4], and were subsequently characterized by complementary methodologies as reported in recent studies [5, 6]. The dynamic response was investigated using two complementary techniques: laser vibrometry, for quantitative strain measurements at 144 points, and MotionScope, for high-resolution vibration visualization. Tests employed electric excitation from 0–4 kHz and enabled three-dimensional mapping of the piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} . The results revealed localized resonant behavior and high heterogeneity in the d_{33} distribution, with response peaks concentrated at the centers of the channels and maximum values reaching $25.59 \mu\text{V}/\text{m}$ at 50 Hz [7]. The MotionScope technique confirmed the observed patterns, highlighting high-amplitude zones within the channels and color transitions related to displacement variation, demonstrating the inverse piezoelectric effect [8]. Differences in response between channels and valleys suggest anisotropic coupling of the materials and uneven charge distribution [9, 10]. Detailed analysis of the vibrational modes provides guidance for geometric and functional optimization of the sensors, aiming for higher sensitivity and performance. The results show that TMPs hold excellent potential for smart-sensor and self-powered energy systems, contributing to advances in functional polymer material engineering [6, 11, 12, 13].

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1.15 Work A017

Assessment of Large Language Models for Automated Knee Image Analysis

Catarina Rocha ^{1,*}, Diogo Sousa ¹, Dulce Oliveira ¹, Mauro Rosa ² and João Lobo ³

¹ Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical Engineering and Industrial Engineering, Portugal

² Institute of Biomedical Sciences Abel Salazar, University of Porto, Portugal

³ Local Health Unit São João, Portugal

* Corresponding author's email: cmrocha@inegi.up.pt

Abstract:

Knee imaging, including X-ray, CT, and MRI, is crucial for diagnosing musculoskeletal conditions like osteoarthritis, ligament injuries, and fractures. While radiologists and orthopaedic specialists traditionally interpret these images, the increasing volume of medical data poses challenges for efficiency and consistency. Recent advancements in Large Language Models (LLMs), such as ChatGPT and Gemini, show promise in medical text processing and clinical decision support [1-2]. This study evaluates their performance using questions from the Orthopaedic In-Training Examination (OITE). A selection of 15 intermediate-level multiple-choice questions from the OITE was chosen. Each question presented five options, with one correct answer, and included MRI images along with other complementary information to enhance the assessment. The ChatGPT 4o and Gemini 2.5 Pro Experimental 03-25 models were used, with no prompting techniques applied. The models were compared based on accuracy, normality tests, the Wilcoxon test, and Cohen's Kappa. ChatGPT achieved an accuracy of 46.67%, while Gemini reached 66.67% on the OITE questions. Normality tests (Shapiro-Wilk) confirmed that the data did not follow a normal distribution. The Wilcoxon test yielded a p-value of 0.257, indicating no statistically significant difference in performance between the models. Additionally, a Cohen's Kappa of 0.087 suggests only slight agreement between them. Although the models achieved different accuracy rates, the low level of agreement suggests they do not consistently perform the same on all questions. This discordance indicates that they may be interpreting the questions differently, potentially due to variations in their training or decision-making processes. In medical exams like the OITE, where consistency and accuracy in image evaluation are crucial, prompt engineering could help refine questions and improve performance.

Acknowledgments: The authors acknowledge the support of the AIriage4SU Project (DOI: 10.54499/2024.07400.IACDC), funded by the FCT (Foundation for Science and Technology), which made this research possible.

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1.16 Work A018

Optimizing the Perseverance rover's wheel support system using a bio-inspired remodelling algorithm

Rui Monteiro^{1,4}, Daniel Rodrigues^{1,2,4}, Ana I. Pais^{3,4}, and Jorge Belinha^{1,4,*}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, ISEP, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Aveiro, Portugal

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, FEUP, University of Porto, Portugal

⁴ Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering

* Corresponding author's email: job@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract:

Nowadays, in space exploration, the limiting factors are the cost of launching devices into space, as well as the payload and volume limit of launch devices. For this, in order to reduce the launching cost, it is necessary that the components sent to space, in addition to fulfilling their function, are reliable, with a reduced mass. The remodelling process used is a Bio Inspired Remodelling Algorithm (BIRA), which is based on the remodelling of bone tissue. In the remodelling procedure, a mechanical stimulus will trigger the remodelling process, increasing the density of areas under a higher stress and decreasing the density of areas under lower stress [1]. To this end, numerical methods have been used such as Finite Element Method (FEM) and two meshless methods: the Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM) and Natural Neighbour Radial Point Interpolation Method (NNRPIM). Although some of these methods need a background mesh, the ones categorized as truly meshless methods, like NNRPIM, do not need a mesh at all. In order to validate the methods used in this work, some benchmark problems were conducted showing very similar results to the ones previously presented in the benchmark problems. This culminated in the analysis and optimization of the perseverance rover part that connects the wheel to the suspension system. The results obtained showed that there is room for improvement in the design of the rover part which would result in a decrease in its weight. This optimization can translate into a lower cost of launching of the rover to Mars thus helping to combat one of the major obstacles to space exploration.

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1.17 Work A019

Structural optimization of the Perseverance rover's suspension system using a meshless method approach

João Silva ^{1,4}, Daniel Rodrigues ^{1,2,4}, Ana I. Pais ^{3,4}, and Jorge Belinha ^{1,4,*}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, ISEP, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Aveiro, Portugal

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, FEUP, University of Porto, Portugal

⁴ Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering

* Corresponding author's email: job@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract:

Space exploration is becoming increasingly important and captivating. With growing interest in missions to Mars, the development of lighter and more efficient systems is essential to meet the demanding requirements of extraterrestrial environments. A major challenge in space missions is the high cost of transporting materials, therefore reducing the mass of structural components is a key strategy to lower costs. This work aims to optimize the suspension component of the Perseverance rover to reduce its weight without compromising performance using a bio-inspired bone remodeling algorithm. For the analysis, a meshless numerical method, the Natural neighbor radial point interpolation method (NNRPIM), was used. Unlike traditional mesh-based methods, NNRPIM operates with scattered nodes to construct the shape functions, leading to a truly meshless approach and avoiding mesh distortion issues. Regarding the nodal connectivity, two degrees of neighbourhood influence cells were used in the performed optimization analyses. In the validation phase, a cantilever beam test produced optimized geometries very similar to well-established benchmark solutions, confirming the method's effectiveness. When applied to the rover suspension system, the method also generated a structure with a comparable layout that closely aligns to those of the rover. Such also demonstrates its potential for a real-world aerospace application. In conclusion, the combination of the bio-inspired bone remodeling algorithm and the NNRPIM proved to structurally optimize a structure. The results suggest that this approach can be successfully used to design lighter and efficient components for space applications, contributing to reduce production and launch costs.

1.18 Work A020**Predicting Mechanical Behaviour in Solid Mechanics Using Artificial Neural Networks**

Guilherme Ribeiro ¹, Ana I. Pais ^{1,2}, and Jorge Belinha ^{2,3,*}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, FEUP, University of Porto, Portugal

² Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, ISEP, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal

* Corresponding author's email: job@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract:

Accurate prediction of mechanical behaviour in solid mechanics is essential for a wide range of engineering applications. However, traditional methods such as the Finite Element Method (FEM) are often computationally intensive. This study investigates the use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) as surrogate models to approximate FEM solutions more efficiently. The research focuses on two benchmark problems in two dimensions: a plate with a central hole and a plate with four holes. FEM simulations were used to generate training data for the ANN models. The study examined the influence of data outliers, identified optimal hyperparameters for improved model performance, and evaluated the accuracy of the ANN predictions against FEM results. The results indicate that ANNs can accurately replicate FEM outputs for both benchmark cases, with strong agreement observed between the ANN predictions and the FEM solutions. However, the presence of outliers in the training data negatively impacts prediction accuracy, with better performance achieved when outliers are removed. Furthermore, the analysis of hyperparameter tuning revealed that training the network on integration points enables accurate prediction at nodal locations.

1.19 Work A021

Generation of porous microstructures through deep learning techniques

Ana I. Pais ^{1,2}, Jorge Lino Alves ^{1,2}, and Jorge Belinha ^{2,3,*}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, FEUP, University of Porto, Portugal

² Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, ISEP, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal

* Corresponding author's email: job@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract:

This work introduces a hybrid framework that combines data-driven methods with physics-based analysis to design unit cells for 2D porous structures with specified elastic properties. Unlike conventional approaches, which typically vary strut or sheet thickness within fixed geometries, the proposed method enables full prediction of all independent components of the elastic tensor. This allows for broader and more flexible tailoring of mechanical behavior beyond the constraints of predefined lattice architectures. At the core of the approach is a generator network, built on a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture and implemented in PyTorch, which produces novel unit cell designs based on target elastic properties. To accelerate training and avoid costly numerical homogenization, an evaluator network is trained on an extended dataset to accurately estimate elastic properties from generated structures. Training results show that incorporating mechanical properties directly into the generator's loss function significantly enhances prediction accuracy compared to a purely image-based loss. However, structures generated with the image-based loss exhibit greater symmetry and stronger resemblance to existing samples in the design database.

1.20 Work A022**In silico model of strain adaptative bone remodeling - a preliminary study of hip artroplasty**António Ramos^{1,*} and Zia Javanbakht²¹ TEMA, Mechanical Engineering Department, University of Aveiro, Portugal² School of Engineering and Built Environment, Griffith University, QLD, Australia

* Corresponding author's email: a.ramos@ua.pt

Abstract:

Intramedullary hip stems are a common type of surgical implants that are used to treat joint diseases. However, the long-term success of intramedullary hip stems depends on their ability to integrate with the surrounding bone tissue and withstand the mechanical loads imposed on the femur. In-silico models (i.e., computational models such as finite element models) [1] have become increasingly valuable tools for studying the biomechanical behaviour and predicting their long-term performance. This study aims to develop a 3D computational model [2] to predict the bone adaptation around an intramedullary hip stem, to understand the influential of bone adaptation. The bone adaptation presented an increase of density near the distal region of implant. Inhomogeneous redistribution of bone density affects the strain field of the bone especially in the vicinity of the implant. Observed values indicate a decrease in minimum principal strain values in the distal region of the implant in comparison with considering the homogeneous bone.

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1.21 Work A023

Topology Optimization of Rover Wheel Structures Using Meshless Methods

Jure Trdin¹, Daniel Rodrigues^{1,2,3}, and Jorge Belinha^{1,2,*}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, School of Engineering, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal

² Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Portugal

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Aveiro, Portugal

* Corresponding author's email: job@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract:

Reducing the mass of structural components remains a critical objective in the space industry, where launch costs are directly tied to payload weight. Numerical methods for structural analysis and optimization are key to meeting this challenge, enabling the development of lightweight, high-performance components. This work investigates the use of meshless methods as an alternative to the Finite Element Method (FEM), focusing on their applicability to structural optimization tasks. By avoiding predefined mesh connectivity, meshless approaches offer greater flexibility in modeling complex geometries and evolving topologies. A case study is presented involving the topology optimization of a spoke from NASA's Perseverance Rover wheel. The optimized geometry results in a significant mass reduction and improved stress distribution, demonstrating the potential of structural optimization to enhance mechanical performance while lowering material usage. These results also validate the effectiveness of meshless methods in producing accurate and efficient solutions for space applications. Overall, this study contributes to the ongoing integration of advanced discretization techniques into aerospace design workflows, highlighting the potential of meshless methods as powerful tools for designing lightweight and cost-effective structures suitable for demanding environments.

1.22 Work A024

On the 2D and 3D Modelling of Beams and Frames Using meshless methods combined with Material Nonlinear Constitutive Behaviour

Hugo Torres^{1,4}, Daniel Rodrigues^{1,2,4}, Ana I. Pais^{3,4}, and Jorge Belinha^{1,4,*}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, ISEP, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Aveiro, Portugal

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, FEUP, University of Porto, Portugal

⁴ Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering

* Corresponding author's email: job@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract:

The nonlinear analysis of beams and framed structures constitutes a fundamental research topic in computational mechanics, particularly when the onset of plasticity, and three-dimensional effects cannot be neglected. In this work, two- and three-dimensional structural formulations are developed within the framework of meshless methods, aiming to provide a robust and accurate alternative to conventional discretization techniques, such as the Finite Element Method (FEM). The structural response is described by means of a nonlinear elasto-plastic material model, based on an incremental-iterative formulation and integrated with the radial point interpolation method (RPIM) and the natural neighbour RPIM (NNRPIM). The proposed strategy ensures the construction of shape functions with high-order continuity, and satisfying the delta Kronecker property, which allows to directly impose natural and essential boundary conditions. The governing equations are derived from the principle of virtual work, then a nonlinear Newton-Raphson procedure is implemented to allow the elasto-plastic analysis. Benchmark examples involving beam elements subjected to plastic hinges, as well as fully three-dimensional framed structures under combined loading, are employed to assess the accuracy, convergence properties and computational efficiency of the formulations. The results confirm that the meshless strategies exhibit superior stress field representation, satisfying convergence rates, and robustness in the presence of strong nonlinearities, evidencing their potential as a reliable computational tool for advanced structural analysis.

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1.23 Work A025

Physics-Informed Neural Networks for stress/strain prediction in structural parts

Martim Correia ^{*,1,2}, and Sérgio Tavares ^{1,2}

¹ UID Centro de Tecnologia Mecânica e Automação (TEMA), Departamento de Engenharia Mecânica, Universidade de Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

² LASI- Intelligent Systems Associate Laboratory, 4800-058 Guimarães, Portugal

* Corresponding author's email: martimcorreia30@ua.pt

Abstract:

This work presents a physics-informed machine learning framework for predicting stress and deformation distributions in structural parts subjected to different boundary conditions, leveraging NVIDIA PhysicsNeMo Sym. The framework is applied to a range of panel configurations, including single-window, double-window, and riveted fuselage sections- capturing the effects of geometric discontinuities on stress concentration and deformation. Using Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs), it is possible to integrate the governing equations of linear elasticity, such as equilibrium conditions, compatibility relations, and constitutive laws, directly into the loss function during training. This enforces physical consistency across the domain without requiring full-field simulation data. Once trained, the PINNs predict full-field stress and displacement distributions for a given hoop stress input, enabling efficient evaluation of structural behavior. We validate the neural network predictions against finite element simulations from ANSYS, demonstrating strong agreement in both qualitative stress patterns and quantitative error metrics. The proposed method significantly reduces computational cost while maintaining accuracy, making it a powerful tool for rapid design evaluation and structural health monitoring in aerospace engineering. [1, 2, 3, 4].

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Chapter 2

Full papers

Abstract This chapter includes full papers corresponding to oral communications submitted to CCAIMB2025. The full papers reflect a broad range of advances in computational modeling, structural analysis, optimization, and design of engineering systems and biomedical solutions. Several contributions focus on material characterization and its impact on innovative applications: elastomeric thin films were investigated for their relevance in the design and computational modeling of soft robotic actuators, while thermoformed magneto-piezoelectret sensors were dynamically characterized through advanced optical techniques such as laser vibrometry and motionScope. Structural and thermal behavior were addressed in different contexts, including a computational study of wooden connections in single shear and a comparison between finite element and meshfree methods for the impact analysis of adhesive joints. Biomedical and protective applications were also strongly represented. Artificial intelligence-based *in silico* simulations were proposed for predicting clinical outcomes of anterior cruciate ligament reconstructions, highlighting the role of AI in personalized medicine. In parallel, new design approaches were presented for customized protective face masks and helmets, employing reverse engineering and advanced modeling to improve fit and safety. Finally, two works focused on space exploration engineering, addressing the optimization of the Perseverance rover's mobility systems. One study applied a bio-inspired remodeling algorithm to enhance the wheel support system, while another employed a meshless method to structurally optimize the suspension system, both aiming to improve performance and reliability under extreme conditions. Together, these works illustrate the diverse and innovative directions of current research, integrating computational methods, material studies, optimization techniques, and biomedical and aerospace engineering applications.

2.1 Characterization of elastomeric thin films for the design and computational modelling of soft robotic actuators

Authors:

Rui A.F. Pereira
Stefan del Rossi
Elza M.M. Fonseca
Silvia Schintke

Characterization of elastomeric thin films for the design and computational modelling of soft robotic actuators

Rui A. F. Pereira^{1,2}, Stefan del Rossi¹, Elza M. M. Fonseca², Silvia Schintke¹

¹Laboratory of Applied NanoSciences (COMATEC-LANS), Department of Industrial Technologies, HEIG-VD / HES-SO University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland
Avenue des Sports 20, CH-1401 Yverdon-les-Bains, Switzerland
silvia.schintke@heig-vd.ch

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, School of Engineering, Polytechnic of Porto
Rua Dr. António Bernardino de Almeida 431, 4249-015 Porto, Portugal
elz@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract. Thin elastomeric materials, such as thin films or thin membranes of silicone or silicone composites, have promising potential for the use in flexible actuators and sensors, particularly in the field of wearable electronics for health, sports, or robotics applications. For example, in dielectric actuators (DEA), a thin elastomer film is sandwiched between electrodes and deformed by the Maxwell stress when a high voltage is applied between the electrodes. In order to develop thin film sensors and actuators based on elastomers, we combine experimental and modelling approaches. We have determined the hyperelastic properties of various dog-bone-shaped silicone samples by tensile tests, using an adapted motorized test bench equipped with a force sensor. We analyse and discuss the measured force-displacement curves in comparison to three non-linear hyperelastic models, Neo-Hookean, Mooney-Rivlin, and Ogden, in order to obtain the tensile properties of the silicone materials, and then calculate the expected actuation performance of DEAs. We use finite element modelling in Ansys to model 3D deformations of the thin films in DEA configuration, taking into account experimental boundary conditions. Finally, we fabricate DEAs and measure their actuation as a function of high voltage in a dedicated experimental set-up. We discuss the different modelling methods in comparison with the experimental results. This validated experimental and modeling framework lays the foundation for future parametric studies, where the influence of design variables on DEA performance can be systematically explored.

Keywords: dielectric elastomer actuators, hyperelasticity, silicone, tensile tests, finite element modelling

1 Introduction

Thin elastomeric materials, such as thin films or thin membranes of silicone or silicone composites, have promising potential for applications in the field of flexible actuators and sensors, particularly in wearable electronics for health, sports, or robotics applications. For example, in dielectric actuators (DEA), a thin elastomer film is sandwiched between electrodes and deformed by the Maxwell stress when a high voltage is applied between the electrodes [1-3]. The dielectric layer between parallel electrode layers forms a planar capacitor. When applying an electric field, $E=U/d$, between the parallel electrodes of area, A , the force, F , acting between the parallel electrodes is given by $F=-dW/dz$, where W is the electrical energy stored by the capacitor at a given voltage, U , and electrode distance, d , along the axis, z , perpendicular to the electrodes. The distance, d , corresponds to the thickness of the dielectric layer of the DEA. For the planar capacitor, the force is thus

$$F = - \frac{dW}{dz} = \epsilon_0 \epsilon_r A E^2 \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_0 is the electrical permittivity of vacuum and ϵ_r the relative permittivity of the dielectric material [4]. From eq. (1), the Maxwell stress, σ , can thus be expressed as a function of the applied voltage, U , and the thickness, d , of the dielectric layer.

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A} = \epsilon_0 \epsilon_r E^2 = \epsilon_0 \epsilon_r \frac{U^2}{d^2} \quad (2)$$

In an DEA, the Maxwell stress leads to compression of the dielectric elastomer perpendicular to the electrodes of the capacitor, and represents a Cauchy-stress from the mechanical point of view. For soft dielectric materials, i.e. elastomers such as silicone, the compression of the material along the electric field, leads to significant expansion of the material perpendicular to the electric field (i.e. parallel to the electrodes), which is the underlying working principle of dielectric elastomer actuators. It is worth to be noted, that for an optimal actuation parallel to the electrodes, the use of compliant stretchable electrodes is required in practice.

The Maxwell stress is given by the electric field, eq. (2), however, the resulting actuation behaviour of DEAs is rather complex, as elastomeric materials, such as silicone, are materials with hyperelastic behaviour. This means that their response to external stress strongly depends on the relative stretch or compression of the materials. Therefore, in view of an efficient development of thin film sensors and actuators based on elastomers, a combination of experimental and modelling approaches is relevant for determining their hyperelastic properties.

In this work, we have thus determined the hyperelastic properties of elastomeric materials, namely silicones, by tensile measurements of dog-bone-shaped specimens using an adapted motorized test bench equipped with a force sensor. The experimental data are fitted using non-linear hyperelastic models, namely Neo-Hookean, Mooney-Rivlin, and Ogden, in order to determine the mechanical properties. Finally, finite element modelling in Ansys is used to model 3D deformations of DEAs. The modelling data are discussed in comparison to experimental results of DEA actuation. This validated experimental and modelling framework lays the foundation for future parametric studies, where the influence of design variables on DEA performance can be systematically explored.

2 Methods

A combination of experimental testing and mechanical modelling is used to determine the material properties of the used silicones, as well as their actuation properties in DEA configurations, as detailed in the following sections.

2.1 Materials and DEA fabrication

Three types of soft silicone rubbers were used throughout this work, namely Ecoflex 00-10, Ecoflex 00-30, and Dragon Skin 20 (KauPo, Germany). The data shown here concern Ecoflex 00-10. Ecoflex 00-10 has a reported relative permittivity of $\epsilon_r=3.4$ [5], used throughout this work.

For DEA fabrication, thin silicone samples were manufactured on a flat glass substrate, by pouring the premixed two-component silicone material, followed by blade coating using a spacer mask-frame of the desired maximal film thickness. A second flat glass plate was then placed together with a weight onto the samples, while keeping the spacer frame in place. After drying, the silicone thin films were cut into rectangular samples of 30 mm \times 50 mm, and their thickness, $d = 0.54$ mm, was measured with a confocal sensor (IFS2404-1, micro-epsilon). Graphite electrodes, each with an area, A , of 26 mm \times 46 mm, were applied on both sides of the films using graphite powder. Stripes of aluminium tape are used on each side for electrical contacting (Fig. 2a).

2.2 Tensile tests and DEA performance tests

For tensile tests, silicone samples in dog-bone shape, according to ISO 37, were prepared by mould-casting. CAD files of moulds were designed using SolidWorks, and 3D-printed from PLA filament using a Creality CR-10S Pro printer with a precision of 0.12 mm. The dimensions of the moulds were verified prior to usage. With respect to the available load cell and the dimensions of the linear motorized stage, type 3 dog-bone-specimens were chosen. This specimen type features a thickness of 2 mm and a width of 4 mm in the narrow section, resulting in a cross-sectional area of 8 mm².

Figure 1 shows examples of mould-casted specimens, as well as the set-up used for tensile measurements.

Figure 1. Tensile tests: a) Mould CAD design for the manufacturing of dog-bone-shaped specimens according to ISO 37, b) examples of mould-casted silicone samples (Ecoflex 00-10), c) specimen installation for tensile tests with reference marks for video analysis of deformation, d) set-up for tensile tests with Arduino-control for signal read-out (1), motorized stage (LabView-controlled) (2), load-cell (3) and sample holders (4).

The displacement was measured optically using video-recording of the entire test procedure. The video data were subsequently analysed using Tracker software to track the distance between the reference points throughout the deformation process.

Then, the values of the force, F , and the displacement, s , were converted to obtain the Cauchy stress–stretch ratio curve. The stretch ratio, λ , is calculated from the displacement using the following relation, eq. (3).

$$\lambda = \frac{L}{L_0} \Leftrightarrow \lambda = \frac{s}{L_0} + 1 \quad (3)$$

where L is the measured distance between the two reference points of the sample, with L_0 being the initial distance. Assuming the material is incompressible, the true cross-sectional area A can be calculated as a function of L , L_0 , and the initial cross-sectional area A_0 , using the relation of volume conservation, eq. (4).

$$A \cdot L = A_0 \cdot L_0 \Leftrightarrow A = A_0 \cdot \frac{L_0}{L} \quad (4)$$

The Cauchy stress σ , which depends on the instantaneous force, F , and area, A , is then given by:

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A} \Leftrightarrow \sigma = \frac{F}{A_0 \cdot \frac{L_0}{s+L_0}} \quad (5)$$

The tensile-stress tests were performed with a speed of 1.00 mm/s for the three different silicone elastomers. To validate the fabrication process and ensure reproducibility, three samples were tested for each material. Additionally, to assess the reliability of the experimental setup, the obtained results were compared with reference data from the Soft Robotics Materials Database [6], which offers highly detailed and standardized mechanical characterization of soft materials.

Figure 2a shows the set-up used for the analysis of the DEA actuation, with the DEA oriented vertically. The DEA is slightly stretched by a suspended weight. A clamp for attaching the weight to the actuator has been designed in order to keep the actuator aligned and flat (Fig. 2b). The total suspended mass (clamp with weight) used for this study was $m = 5.162$ g.

Figure 2. Test bench of DEA actuation: a) experimental set-up: application of a high voltage to the DEA, leads to a lift-up of the weight, its vertical displacement is measured as a function of voltage, b) CAD design of the clamp to suspend a small weight to the DEA.

The high voltage is then increased from 0.0 kV to 5.0 kV in steps of 500 V, while video-recording of the actuation is performed. The clamp, as well as the upper fixation of the DEA, serve as reference points for the analysis of the length variations of the actuator. Tracker software is used for the analysis of the recorded video data.

2.3 Hyperelastic models and finite element modelling

For the modelling of non-linear hyperelastic properties of the materials, three non-linear elasticity models are applied for comparison, Neo-Hookean, Mooney-Rivlin, and Ogden [7]. Table 1 summarizes the corresponding Cauchy-stress equations, that are obtained for each of the models, by deriving the strain energy equation [7], Ψ , according to eq. (6), applicable for unidirectional stress:

$$\sigma = \lambda \cdot \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \lambda}. \quad (6)$$

Table 1. Summary of Cauchy stress equations of the non-linear elasticity models [7]

Model	Cauchy stress σ
Neo-Hookean	$\sigma = \mu \cdot \lambda^2 - \frac{\mu}{\lambda}$
Mooney-Rivlin	$\sigma = 2C_{10} \left(\lambda^2 - \frac{1}{\lambda} \right) + 2C_{01} \left(\lambda - \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \right) + 6C_{11} \left(\lambda^3 - \lambda^2 - \lambda + \frac{1}{\lambda} + \frac{1}{\lambda^2} - \frac{1}{\lambda^3} \right)$
Ogden	$\sigma = \beta_1 \cdot \lambda^{\alpha_1} - \beta_1 \cdot \lambda^{-\frac{\alpha_1}{2}} + \beta_2 \cdot \lambda^{\alpha_2} - \beta_2 \cdot \lambda^{-\frac{\alpha_2}{2}}$

where μ is the initial shear modulus, C_{10} , C_{01} , and C_{11} are material constants, and β_1 , β_2 , α_1 , α_2 are material constants that are related to the initial shear modulus. Table 2 summarizes their relation to the initial shear modulus [7]:

Table 2. Summary of the initial shear modulus equations of the non-linear elasticity models

Model	Initial shear modulus μ
Neo-Hookean	Curve fitting
Mooney-Rivlin	$\mu = 2(C_{10} + C_{01})$
Ogden	$\mu = \frac{1}{2}(\alpha_1 \cdot \beta_1 + \alpha_2 \cdot \beta_2)$

Ansys is used for finite element modelling of the DEAs, considering experimental boundary conditions. The geometry of the DEA chosen for the numerical analysis is the same as in the experimental and analytical approaches: 50 mm in height, 30 mm in width, and 0.54 mm in depth. For the simulation, a configuration using 6,072 nodes was selected. Figure 3 illustrates how experimental boundary conditions are implemented for numerical modelling. The DEA is held in place by two aluminum contact electrodes (Fig 3a), which also provide mechanical constraint. The geometry of the aluminum stripes corresponds to a rectangular shape, measuring 5 mm in width and 10 mm in length, positioned 5 mm from the edges of the DEA, one on each side. In the numerical model, this boundary condition is implemented by fully constraining all nodes within these regions of the electrodes.

Figure 3b also illustrates, in red, the application of an external force, taking into account the attached clamp and weight in the lower part of the DEA (Fig. 3a). In the numerical model, this force is implemented as a distributed pressure. To apply it accurately, the total force corresponding to the attached mass (clamp with weight) is first calculated and then evenly divided by the number of nodes on the bottom surface of the DEA.

Afterwards, the high voltage is applied. Before this step, node coupling is performed in Ansys to ensure a uniform application of the electric potential across specific surfaces. This coupling, shown in yellow (Fig. 3b), electrically links multiple nodes, such that they share the same potential, effectively eliminating localized variations that may arise due to mesh discretization.

Figure 3. Example of boundary conditions for numerical modelling of DEA actuation; a) example of a suspended DEA with a suspended mass (clamp with weight), b) implemented boundary conditions for numerical modelling of constraints by the aluminium electrode stripes in the upper part (fully constraint), and by the attached mass in the lower part (represented by corresponding force vectors).

3 Results and Discussion

Figure 4 shows, as an example, experimental tensile test results for three Ecoflex 00-10 samples in comparison to data from the material database [6]. The agreement of the experimental data with data from the database [6] is good, and within the range of experimental reproducibility for stretch ratios up to about 2.25. For higher stretch ratios the database indicates slightly higher Cauchy stress values than the measured ones. As for the targeted DEA applications, the expected stretch ratios are, however, typically smaller than 2.25, the obtained experimental results are well satisfactory. Similar results are obtained from tensile tests of Ecoflex 00-30, and Dragon skin 20 (not shown here).

Figure 4. Tensile tests: examples of experimental stress-stretch ratio curves, compared to database values [5] for Ecoflex 00-10 specimens.

Figure 5 shows the corresponding fitting curves of the tensile test using the three non-linear models, again for Ecoflex 00-10, as an example. The experimental data of three samples (Fig. 4) were averaged prior to fitting. The data are best fitted by the Ogden and Mooney-Rivlin models. Similar results are obtained for Ecoflex 00-30 and Dragon skin 20 (not shown here).

Figure 5. Fitting curves of the hyperelastic models for tensile tests of Ecoflex 00-10. Ogden and Mooney-Rivlin models allow best for the fitting of the experimental stress-stretch ratio curves.

The observed fitting behaviour of the hyperelastic models in agreement with observations for other elastomeric materials, e.g. for chloroprene rubber [8].

Figure 6 shows the voltage-displacement curves obtained from DEA actuation (Fig. 3), together with the corresponding analytical modelling, comparing the three hyperelastic models. The experimental data were obtained from 3 DEA samples. The presented data are averaged values, calculated for each voltage. The relative errors between individual samples and plotted average values are in the range of 4% to 16%, which is attributed to differences between DEA samples, besides limited precision in voltage setting (± 0.05 kV) and displacement measurements (± 0.1 mm).

Figure 6. Experimental and analytical modelling results of DEA actuation: voltage-displacement curves (DEA with Ecoflex 00-10).

The results from analytical modelling show higher DEA displacements than the measured ones (Fig. 6). This is partially attributed to simplification of the surface area of the DEAs in the analytical modelling, assuming an electrode surface of 30 mm x 50 mm, that would fully reach up to the edges of the DEA. The Mooney-Rivlin model is in closest agreement with the experimental data, with a relative error of 18%. The relative errors of the Ogden and Neo-Hookean model are 43% and 53% respectively, compared to the average experimental values.

Figure 7 shows the same averaged experimental data in comparison with numerical modelling of the DEA, also comparing the Neo-Hookean, Mooney-Rivlin, and Ogden models.

Figure 7. Experimental and numerical modelling results of DEA actuation: voltage-displacement curves (DEA with Ecoflex 00-10).

The results from numerical modelling show only slightly higher DEA displacements than the measured ones (Fig. 7). Similar to the analytic modelling, the Mooney-Rivlin model shows for the numerical modelling the best agreement with the experimental data, with a relative error of 12%. For the numerical simulation using the Neo-Hookean and Ogden models, the relative errors, compared to the average experimental values, are reduced to 19% and 18% respectively.

From the modelling point of view, we have approximated compressive stress by the data of tensile stress measurements, which may explain the observed discrepancy of absolute displacement values. Additional measurement of compressive stress, will allow to take the experimental data for compression into account. Qualitatively, the actuation behaviour is however, already well simulated by the applied approximation.

4 Conclusions

The experimental tensile test data of the studied hyperelastic soft silicone materials are well fitted using the Ogden or Mooney-Rivlin models. Based on the fitting of the experimental Cauchy stress – stretch ratio data, the actuation behaviour of DEAs is qualitatively well modelled by finite element simulations, taking into account the experimental boundary conditions. Further experimental investigations of compressive stress are expected to improve finite element modelling of DEA actuation. This validated experimental and modelling framework lays the foundation for future parametric studies, where the influence of design variables, and material properties on DEA performance can be systematically explored.

Acknowledgements. This work has been financially supported by HES-SO, project FLEXPAC (grant-number IA-DEPOT23-125). We kindly acknowledge a mobility grant from the Swiss European Mobility Programme, SEMP (R.A.F. Pereira).

R.AF Pereira would also like to thank LAETA/INEGI for the support provided for the conference registration.

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2.2 Computational Thermal and Mechanical Study of Wooden Connections in Single Shear

Authors:

João C.P. Aguiar
Elza M.M. Fonseca

Computational Thermal and Mechanical Study of Wooden Connections in Single Shear

João C P Aguiar¹, Elza M M Fonseca¹

¹*ISEP, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal*
1180795@isep.ipp.pt, elz@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract. This work will focus on a specific type of wooden connections and the available analysis methods, such as numerical methods, including the application of the finite element method, and analytical methods. The objective is to study the behaviour of wooden connections with the other materials that compose them, such as steel and gypsum board, and the external actions to which they will be subjected (fire and general mechanical loading). The wooden connections to be studied aim to guarantee the greatest shear resistance, so they will be made up of steel dowels, chosen according to their diameter. The state of the art for the analysis of this type of connection is still limited; therefore, this study will allow a more in-depth knowledge of single shear connections when subjected to fire. It is intended that the constituent components of the connections to be developed are dimensioned following simplified equations, based on Eurocodes. The design planned for the wooden connection, under certain conditions, will be subject to safety verification through the application of finite element analysis. The models under study will be analysed under thermal and mechanical action to evaluate the resistance capacity of the connection to fire.

Keywords: fire, wood connection, single shear, fire resistance.

1 Introduction

There has been a significant increase in the use of wood in construction solutions, especially in the context of sustainability and carbon emissions mitigation. This trend confirms the need to study the behaviour of wood connections, particularly under fire conditions. Despite being a renewable material with favourable properties, such as the formation of a carbon layer that contributes to fire resistance, the variability of fire conditions and different construction configurations present challenges in regulating its performance.

To carry out a robust bibliographic review aligned with the state of the art, recent articles on the topic in question were identified and analysed [1-6]. For this purpose, VOSviewer, a tool for building and analysing bibliometric networks, was used. A bibliometric analysis of keyword occurrence, shown in Figure 1, allowed us to identify the terms most frequently used related to the present investigation. The resulting map highlights the predominance of terms such as "fire", "timber", "wood", "fire resistance" and "mass timber", reflecting the main areas of research on the topic addressed. However, the absence of relevant connections with the keyword "thermomechanical" stands out, which, despite being used in the search, did not play a central role or have significant connections with other important keywords. This result reinforces the perception that the thermomechanical approach is still little explored, indicating a possible opportunity for future studies.

The models presented in the literature review predominantly address thermal and mechanical analyses separately, highlighting the gap in the joint investigation of the thermomechanical behaviour of timber joints. Although there are studies on fire resistance and the influence of mechanical actions, the simultaneous interaction of these actions and the variables involved in connections protected with gypsum boards is still limited.

Another aspect identified was the relative lack of studies investigating the different configurations of passive fire protection, particularly considering variations in the properties of gypsum boards and their interactions with different types of wood and structural elements.

Recently, M. Audebert, et al. [7-8] developed a numerical model to analyze the thermomechanical behavior of timber-timber connections, using the results of two series of experimental tests to validate the results, which were

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very relevant in this area. According to regulations, in fire exposure, the calculation with Eurocode 5, Part 1-2 [4] is based on a limited number of experimental and numerical results.

Figure 1. Keyword map with VOSviewer

The gaps presented above highlight the importance of deepening the thermomechanical analyses of joints, as well as exploring innovative and sustainable solutions for fire protection. This is the main reason for the subsequent development of this research work. A better understanding of these limitations will contribute to the development of more robust and reliable solutions, promoting greater safety and feasibility in the use of timber joints in structural projects. Thus, the main objective of this work was to consolidate several subjects associated with wooden connections, especially their thermal and mechanical behaviour, as well as the different types of fire protection, with a special focus on gypsum plasterboard.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials and standard fire curve

A glued laminated timber (referred to as glulam) was used for the designed connections in the study, and S275 for steel material used in the dowel connectors. For thermal analysis, heat transfer is governed by material density, thermal conductivity, and specific heat. The wood properties are temperature-dependent, as defined by Eurocode 5, Part 1-2 [4]. For steel, density is assumed to be constant over the entire range of temperatures produced during a fire, while thermal conductivity and specific heat are temperature-dependent, as shown in Figure 1, Eurocode 3, Part 1-2 [1]. The properties of gypsum plasterboard will be obtained from the literature [9-11].

The fire starts with a transient thermal analysis, resulting in the thermal response of the connection during the fire exposure [3]. The nominal temperature-time standard curve ISO 834 [3] will be used in the computational model, described by eq. (1).

$$\theta_{\infty} = 20 + 345 \log_{10}(8t + 1) \quad (1)$$

where t is the time in min and θ_{∞} is the gas temperature in the fire compartment expressed in °C.

2.2 Computational model

For the development of computational work, a previous validation was carried out, based on the analysis of wood joints subjected to fire, according to an experimental study by another author [7]. So, in this work, the calibrated numerical model was used and adapted in the present study. To create the thermomechanical computational model, at first, a thermal and transient analysis with nonlinear materials was performed with ANSYS 2020.R2. Then, it will be needed to use a combined analysis between the thermal process, reading the temperature at the time of fire exposure, and running it through a structural mechanical process, as shown in the flowchart presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Flowchart of the computational model

The calculated temperature in the thermal analysis affects the structural and mechanical analysis, but the mechanical analysis does not affect the temperature field variation. Also, to satisfy the thermal or structural conditions, it is necessary to employ an iterative procedure in each step. The Newton–Raphson method was adopted to solve the problem with an imposed time step and minimum time increment. The thermomechanical analysis will allow the determination of the resistant load of the connections in single shear under fire, comparing the results obtained between connections with and without passive protection.

2.3 Simplified equation for wooden connection in single shear

The presented analytical procedure in eq. 2 follows the Eurocode to determine the dimensions of the connections. Eurocode 5 part 1-1 [2] provides easy equations to calculate the load-carrying capacity in various connection types. For the design of the connection, the aim is to determine the number of dowels and their dimensions, as presented in Figure 3.

$$F_{v,Rk} = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{f_{h,1,k} t_1 d}{1 + \beta} \left[\sqrt{\beta + 2\beta^2 \left[1 + \frac{t_2}{t_1} + \left(\frac{t_2}{t_1} \right)^2 \right] + \beta^3 \left(\frac{t_2}{t_1} \right)^2} - \beta \left(1 + \frac{t_2}{t_1} \right) \right] + \frac{F_{ax,Rk}}{4} \quad (c) \\ 1.05 \frac{f_{h,1,k} t_1 d}{2 + \beta} \left[\sqrt{2\beta(1 + \beta) + \frac{4\beta(2 + \beta)M_{y,Rk}}{f_{h,1,k} d t_1^2}} - \beta \right] + \frac{F_{ax,Rk}}{4} \quad (d) \\ 1.05 \frac{f_{h,1,k} t_2 d}{1 + 2\beta} \left[\sqrt{2\beta^2(1 + \beta) + \frac{4\beta(1 + 2\beta)M_{y,Rk}}{f_{h,1,k} d t_2^2}} - \beta \right] + \frac{F_{ax,Rk}}{4} \quad (e) \\ 1.15 \sqrt{\frac{2\beta}{1 + \beta}} \sqrt{2M_{y,Rk} f_{h,1,k} d} + \frac{F_{ax,Rk}}{4} \quad (f) \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

Equation 2 is used for single shear connections where the main variables are as follows: $F_{v,Rk}$ is the characteristic load-carrying capacity per shear plane per fastener; t_i represents the thickness of the timber side member ($i=1, 2$), respectively, the smaller and the middle member; d is the fastener diameter; β is the ratio between the embedment strength of the members, equal to 1; $F_{ax,Rk}$ represents the characteristic axial withdrawal capacity of the fastener; $f_{h,k}$ is the material characteristic tensile strength; ρ_k characteristic density of the wood; $M_{y,Rk}$ is the characteristic fastener yield moment calculated according to the dowel diameter and the material strength; and $f_{h,i,k}$ is the characteristic embedment strength in the timber member ($i=1, 2$).

2.4 Discussion of results in wooden connection

Figure 3 shows the finite element meshes of the connections without and with protection. The dimension of the edge of each finite element is 6 mm, depending on the minimum size allowed in the model with the gypsum plasterboard.

Figure 3. a) Computational model of wooden connection, b) without, and c) with protection. The blue colour represents the wood element; the violet colour represents the steel dowels, and the red colour is the gypsum

In the thermal analysis, the boundary conditions used are related to the convection and the radiation due to the exposed fire in front of the external surface of the connection. The initial temperature in the numerical model was considered equal to 20 °C. The emissivity of the environment will be taken as a constant value and equal to 1, Eurocode 1, part 1-2 [3]. The external surface of the connection is exposed to the standard fire curve ISO 834 [3] for 3600 seconds. The convection coefficient is equal to 25 W/m²K, according to Eurocode 1, part 1-2, [3]. For thermomechanical analysis, an incremental tensile load was imposed on the free end and a fixed end on the opposite side. The temperature previously obtained in the thermal analysis was added for a corresponding time of exposure to fire.

Figure 4 represents the temperature field obtained with the thermal model for different time instants in fire exposure.

Figure 4. Temperatures of wooden connections without a) and b), and with protection c) and d)

From 300°C onwards, the wood begins to form a char layer. However, as the temperature increases, the thermal degradation of the wood intensifies, leading to cracking and progressive loss of material, which happens in a) with total degradation and b) only a few parts remain at 20 °C. For protected connections, and without a steel dowel directly exposed to fire, the transfer of heat reduces to the interior of the connection, c) and d), retain the intact wood.

Figure 5 represents the level of equivalent stress obtained with the thermomechanical model for different time instants in fire exposure.

Figure 5. von-Mises stresses of wooden connections without a) and b), and with protection c) and d)

In the models at ambient temperature, a) and c), the wood reaches rupture, exhibiting a maximum stress of 25.6 MPa, close to the boundary conditions. At high temperatures, a decrease in the maximum stress is observed in the wooden elements, 10 MPa for the unprotected connection b), and 17 MPa for the protected connection d). Along the length of the elements, the charred layer presents no stress.

The comparison between the thermal models allowed the quantification of the effect of protection over time. There was a more gradual degradation of the protected connection, maintaining the structural load capacity for a substantially longer time. This difference highlights the role of gypsum plasterboard as a passive protection material and highlights the need for sizing methodologies that are more adjusted to the characteristics of the materials used, as well as to the variability of the construction configurations of the wooden connections.

3 Conclusions

Gypsum plasterboards have proven to be an efficient and widely applied solution as passive protection, standing out for their role in improving the fire resistance of connections. On the other hand, numerical analysis has proven to be an essential tool for evaluating different construction solutions, with or without additional protective materials. Despite their complexity, due to the interaction of materials with non-linear behaviours and the transient nature of thermal action, numerical models offer a promising method for predicting the degradation of timber elements and correlating them with fire resistance criteria.

Acknowledgements. JCP Aguiar would like to thank LAETA/INEGI for the support provided for the conference registration.

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2.3 Artificial intelligence-driven in silico simulation for prediction of anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction clinical outcomes

Authors:

Orlando Branco Simões
António Manuel Ramos
Nuno Sevivas
José António Simões

Artificial intelligence-driven in silico simulation for prediction of anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction clinical outcomes

Orlando Branco Simões^{1,3}, António Manuel Ramos², Nuno Sevivas⁴ and José António Simões^{*3}

¹*Unidade Local de Saúde Gaia-Espinho, Vila Nova de Gaia, Portugal*

orlandoabsimoes@gmail.com

²*Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Aveiro, Portugal*

a.ramos@ua.pt

³*ESAD.IDEA – Investigação em Design e Arte, Matosinhos, Portugal*

josesimoes@esad.pt

⁴*Universidade do Minho*

nunosevivas@gmail.com

Abstract. This paper explores the integration of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and *in silico* simulation to develop a predictive model for clinical outcomes following Anterior Cruciate Ligament Reconstruction. By combining patient-specific clinical and surgical data with machine learning algorithms and biomechanical simulations, the aim is to enhance preoperative planning, surgical decision-making, and postoperative management. A key innovation lies in incorporating artificial intelligence-driven *in silico* modelling, offering a multidimensional analysis that goes beyond data-driven approaches alone, particularly valuable for complex surgical cases. The research methodology will also leverage computational finite element data to strengthen correlations between clinical and biomechanical factors.

Keywords: Anterior Cruciate Ligament, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, *In Silico* Simulation.

1 Introduction

Anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction (ACLR) is an orthopaedic procedure aimed at restoring both functional capacity and joint stability (static and dynamic) following ligament injury. The rising incidence of ACLR has been accompanied by an increase in surgical failures, many of which require technically demanding revision procedures. These challenges arise due to factors such as removal of prior implants, optimal tunnel positioning, residual muscle weakness from the primary reconstruction, and a higher rate of concomitant injuries [1,2].

Surgical outcomes in ACLR are frequently assessed using patient-reported outcome measures, and several risk factors associated with poor outcomes have been identified in the literature [3]. While advancements in surgical techniques have improved outcomes following revision ACLR, results remain inferior to those of primary ACLR [2]. Revision ACLR is also associated with a higher failure rate compared to primary reconstruction, underscoring the clinical importance of addressing failed ACLRs [1]. Clinically, ACL graft failure is defined by persistent pain, stiffness, or instability after reconstruction, and may be attributed to multiple underlying causes [4].

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are increasingly being integrated into orthopaedic surgery. A growing body of literature explores their applications and challenges, including specific investigations into ACLR [5]. Predictive modelling of ACLR outcomes has utilized both ML and deep learning (DL) algorithms, as well as clinical scoring systems, to enhance preoperative risk assessment and treatment planning [5]. As AI becomes an integral part of orthopaedic practice, all stakeholders, including surgeons, healthcare providers, policymakers, and patients, must adapt to this evolving landscape. It is now widely accepted that AI has the potential to significantly improve predictive capabilities in orthopaedics. These advanced analytical techniques leverage complex algorithms to model intricate interactions between variables, potentially enhancing our ability to predict surgical outcomes.

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For instance, Martin et al. [6] developed an AI-based calculator to estimate patient-specific risk of subjective failure, thereby aiding in preoperative discussions and expectation management. Their study externally validated the Norwegian Knee Ligament Registry model by testing algorithm performance on patients from the Danish Knee Ligament Registry, demonstrating consistent predictive accuracy. This marks the first externally validated ML model for predicting outcomes in revision ACLR.

AI has also shown promise in musculoskeletal imaging. DL and ML techniques have been successfully applied to Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) analysis for ACL injury detection, classification, and quantitative assessment, illustrating the role of AI in preoperative evaluation [10]. Additional studies have explored ML algorithms to predict ACLR outcomes based on preoperative patient characteristics, imaging data, and surgical variables [11,12]. Ethical and social implications of AI adoption in orthopaedic surgery are also gaining attention [13]. Moreover, finite element analysis (FEA) has been utilized in various ACLR related studies to simulate and understand biomechanical behaviour [14,15].

2 Integration of AI in pre-surgical in planning of ACL reconstruction

Currently, surgical decision-making for ACL injuries primarily relies on patient-specific parameters and the type of lesion. The incorporation of AI and numerical computational simulation models into the preoperative planning process represents a novel and underexplored frontier in ACLR management. Predictive models integrating ML with both clinical outcome data and finite element method-based numerical simulations hold the potential to generate evidence-based forecasts of postoperative results.

Contemporary surgical techniques for ACLR, including considerations around graft selection, surgical approach, and rehabilitation protocols, remain fundamental to understanding the factors that influence clinical outcomes [7]. However, the reliability of AI-driven outcome prediction fundamentally depends on the relevance and quality of the “input data”. The study by Simões *et al.* [9], which examined postoperative pain and sensory alterations, demonstrates how different ACLR techniques intersect with patient-specific characteristics and functional scores such as the Tegner Activity Level Score (TALS) (see Tables 1 and 2). Their cohort study involved 75 athletic patients undergoing one of three anatomical arthroscopic ACLR techniques, with each cohort comprising 25 patients. The groups were categorized based on graft type: bone–patellar tendon–bone (BTB) autograft, quadruple-strand semitendinosus and gracilis (4ST/G) autograft, and all-inside quadruple-strand semitendinosus autograft.

Across all groups, patients reported pain and sensory disturbances postoperatively. The BTB autograft group demonstrated a higher incidence of anterior knee pain, hypoesthesia, and more frequent positive outcomes on the Knee Walking Test (KWT) in the medium-term postoperative period. The ST/G group experienced the shortest duration of anterior knee pain. The All-Inside cohort reported the fewest overall complaints and the shortest duration of postoperative sensory deficits. These findings highlight the variability in clinical outcomes based on surgical technique and patient characteristics, supporting the feasibility of using AI/ML models to distinguish outcome patterns based on preoperative data, potentially even beyond the parameters listed in Table 1.

Several key research questions must be addressed to fully explore the potential of AI and *in silico* models in ACLR management [16,17]:

- How accurately can AI and ML models predict postoperative clinical outcomes of ACLR based on preoperative patient data?
- What are the most significant predictors of ACLR outcomes identified through AI analysis?
- How do AI-based predictive models compare with traditional methods in terms of accuracy and reliability?
- Can ML algorithms effectively stratify patients into risk categories for complications or suboptimal outcomes?
- How do different surgical techniques or graft choices impact the predictive accuracy of AI-guided *in silico* models?
- Can AI-driven *in silico* models personalize rehabilitation protocols to optimize recovery and functional outcomes?
- How generalizable are these predictive models across diverse patient populations and surgical settings?
- What are the inherent limitations and biases of AI-based predictions, and how can these be mitigated?

- How does integrating multi-source data, namely preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative data, enhance predictive model performance?

Table 1 – Population demographics [9].

	BTB	4 ST/G	All-Inside	P-value
Age (years)	25.8 ± 5.3	33.0 ± 8.1	30.8 ± 8.8	<0.001
BMI (kg/m²)	24.4 ± 2.2	23.8 ± 1.8	24.1 ± 2.6	0.630
Lesion to surgery (months)	3.0 ± 2.2	5.2 ± 3.8	5.9 ± 10.0	0.082
Sports aetiology	23 (92%)	20 (80%)	25 (100%)	0.059
Right dominant limb	16 (64%)	15 (60%)	15 (60%)	1.000
TALS preoperative	7.6 ± 1.1	6.6 ± 1.0	7.3 ± 1.1	0.004

BTB - bone-tendon tendon-bone cohort. 4 ST/G – quadruple strand semitendinosus and gracilis cohort. All-Inside – quadruple strand semitendinosus with all-inside technique cohort. BMI – body mass index. TALS – Tegner Activity Level Scale.

Table 2 – TALS and subjective scores [9].

Table 2. TALS and subjective scores				
	BTB	4 ST/G	All-Inside	P-value
TALS postoperative	7.2 ± 1.3	6.0 ± 1.0	7.0 ± 1.3	0.002
TALS preoperative=postoperative	17 (68%)	15 (60%)	21 (84%)	0.169
Sports authorization (months)	6.5 ± 1.8	6.9 ± 1.4	7.6 ± 2.3	0.131
LKSS	97.4 ± 4.1	98.7 ± 2.0	97.6 ± 3.9	0.256
IKDC-SKF	94.6 ± 3.9	95.9 ± 3.4	96.5 ± 2.3	0.072

BTB - bone-tendon tendon-bone cohort. 4 ST/G – quadruple strand semitendinosus and gracilis cohort. All-Inside – quadruple strand semitendinosus with all-inside technique cohort. TALS – Tegner Activity Level Scale. LKSS – Lysholm Knee Scoring Scale. IKDC-SKF - International Knee Documentation Committee-Subjective Knee Form.

To explore these questions, a systemic and iterative methodology can be implemented, consisting of the following steps:

- **Data Collection:** Extract data from electronic health records and institutional orthopaedic databases, including patient demographics, injury characteristics, surgical techniques, and postoperative outcomes;
- **Imaging Analysis:** Use advanced imaging modalities (MRI, CT, X-ray) to assess the extent of injury, anatomical features, and graft suitability;

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- **AI/ML Development:** Apply ML algorithms to predict ACLR outcomes using the compiled clinical and imaging data;
- **Biomechanical Simulation:** Conduct *in vitro* and computational biomechanical simulations (e.g., FEA and multibody dynamics) to evaluate the impact of surgical variables such as graft type, tunnel orientation, and fixation method on joint biomechanics;
- **Validation:** Perform external validation of the AI-based *in silico* models using independent datasets and prospective clinical studies to assess generalizability and clinical relevance.

This process must support the following objectives:

- Develop robust AI-guided *in silico* techniques for surgical planning and patient-specific outcome prediction;
- Enable personalized treatment strategies and improve patient selection based on AI-derived insights;
- Enhance intraoperative decision-making and postoperative care through AI-supported predictive simulations;
- Validate AI applications through clinical trials and integrate them into orthopaedic surgical practice;
- Contribute to the broader advancement of AI-assisted orthopaedic surgery, ultimately improving ACLR success rates and reducing complications.

By combining patient-specific clinical and surgical data with ML and computational simulation models, clinicians can obtain deeper insights that improve patient selection, surgical planning, and postoperative management. AI technologies have already demonstrated their potential in diagnostic imaging by enabling more precise detection of ACL injuries and associated micro-lesions that may be missed by traditional assessment methods. These imaging data can be used to construct patient-specific anatomical models for *in silico* simulations, which allow for the dynamic evaluation of ligament behaviour and enable the comparison of surgical approaches under simulated physiological conditions. This contributes to more informed choices regarding surgical techniques and graft selection.

A promising but largely unexplored area is the virtual simulation of ACL surgery. Advances in computational modelling have significantly enhanced the biomechanical characterization of knee ligaments. FEA, in particular, enables the assessment of stress and strain across all joint components like ligaments, cartilage, and bone, regardless of their material properties. This level of detail allows for scientifically grounded decision-making, particularly in complex or borderline clinical cases. Virtual surgical trials using biomechanical knee models can help forecast potential complications and outcomes, even within the acknowledged limitations of computational modelling.

AI can also play a critical role in postoperative care. ML algorithms can incorporate patient-specific rehabilitation data, enabling continuous monitoring through wearable sensors that track joint mobility and function in real time. This information can guide dynamic adjustments to rehabilitation protocols, helping to prevent reinjury and expedite return to normal or athletic activity. These personalized rehabilitation strategies can be tailored to individual recovery profiles, enhancing both effectiveness and efficiency.

The use of AI in ACLR is not limited to treatment but extends into risk prediction. By analysing large datasets, ML models can identify patterns that distinguish patients at higher risk of surgical failure or recurrence, enabling more effective preventive strategies and personalized follow-up protocols.

Various algorithmic approaches have been proposed for ACLR outcome prediction, including logistic regression [18], support vector machines (SVMs) [19], random forests [20], and artificial neural networks (ANNs) [21]. These models can be developed using powerful data science libraries such as Python [22], TensorFlow [23], and Keras [24]. Regardless of the selected model, rigorous cross-validation is essential to assess generalizability. External validation using independent or published datasets is also crucial to ensure robustness. For clinical implementation, model interpretability is vital and can be enhanced using more transparent algorithms, such as decision trees or linear models.

3 Integration of computational simulation in ACL reconstruction

The incorporation of AI-based *in silico* simulation represents a clear innovation in the management of ACLR. As an advanced design element, it introduces enhanced analytical capabilities that enable a more comprehensive evaluation of ACL surgery, particularly valuable in complex cases where traditional ML models based solely on clinical data fall short. By integrating computational results from FE models or other biomechanical simulations with AI algorithms, it becomes possible to correlate mechanical insights with clinical data. This synergy allows

for the development of predictive tools that consider both patient-specific clinical variables and biomechanical behaviour, thereby improving surgical planning and outcome prediction.

Figure 1. The research methodology. Source: Authors.

A considerable body of experimental and numerical research has already contributed to advancing the realism of digital knee models used in ACLR studies. Today, these models can realistically simulate both static and dynamic biomechanical conditions of the knee, including detailed representations of ligament function and interactions. Figure 2 illustrates a virtual knee joint model previously developed and utilized by the authors in ACLR research [25-28]. Despite these advancements, computational models must be rigorously compared and validated against experimental data to ensure accuracy and reliability. Such validation is critical; only when simulated outputs such as stress, strain, and displacement fall within acceptable deviation margins from experimental or cadaveric benchmarks can these *in silico* models be considered scientifically robust and clinically trustworthy.

Figure 2 – Computational model of the ACLR [28].

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The study presented in [25], along with related works [26–28], investigated ACL biomechanics following reconstruction, with a particular focus on the role of tibial tunnel angle in determining the longevity and success of the procedure. The authors developed high-fidelity digital knee joint models and validated a multibody simulation using *in situ* ACL force curves to define both the tibial tunnel footprint and its inclination. FEA revealed that optimal tibial tunnel inclination angles, those that minimize contact pressures, shear forces, and von Mises stresses on the graft, are approximately 45° in the sagittal-transversal plane and 30° in the coronal-sagittal plane. Furthermore, rounding the tunnel edge corners at graft contact points was shown to reduce local pressures and stresses by roughly 30%, potentially contributing to improved clinical outcomes in ACLR.

The convergence of computational modelling and AI presents a powerful opportunity to infer and predict ACLR clinical outcomes. By integrating simulation data such as tunnel geometry, stress distribution, and ligament loading with patient-specific clinical variables using ML algorithms, it becomes possible to generate predictive insights that guide surgical planning and postoperative management. This multi-domain approach underscores the potential of AI-enhanced *in silico* modelling to optimize both biomechanical performance and clinical success in ACLR.

4 Conclusions

In summary, the integration of AI and *in silico* models into ACL injury management offers a transformative approach to patient care. These technologies enable personalized diagnostics and treatment planning, real-time postoperative monitoring, and predictive modeling of potential complications. Collectively, they contribute to safer, more efficient surgical procedures and improved clinical outcomes. Beyond the direct benefits to patients, who remain at the center of the healthcare process, these innovations also enhance the overall quality of orthopaedic services, particularly in the context of ACL treatment, by supporting evidence-based, data-driven decision-making and fostering precision medicine in surgical practice.

Acknowledgements. This work was carried out under Project No. 15022 (ACLART – *Prediction of Clinical Outcomes of Anterior Cruciate Ligament Reconstruction through In Silico Simulation Combined with Artificial Intelligence*), reference COMPETE2023-FEDER-00867200. The project was co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) under the PORTUGAL2030 program, and by the budget of the Foundation for Science and Technology, I.P. (FCT).

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2.4 Protective Face Masks: An Approach to Customized Designs

Authors:

Inês C.J. Barbosa
Ana S.A. Gonçalves
Maria A.R. Loja

Protective Face Masks: An Approach to Customized Designs

Inês C.J. Barbosa^{1,2}, Ana S.A. Gonçalves¹, Maria A.R. Loja^{1,2}

¹*CIMOSM, ISEL, IPL – Centro de Investigação em Modelação e Optimização de Sistemas Multifuncionais, Av. Conselheiro Emídio Navarro 1, 1959-007 Lisboa, Portugal*

²*IDMEC, Instituto Superior de Engenharia de Lisboa, Instituto Politécnico de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal*
ines.barbosa@isel.pt, A46132@alunos.isel.pt, amelia.loja@isel.pt

Abstract. This study explores the modeling and design of customizable protective face masks that can be fabricated using additive manufacturing techniques. This type of mask is generally needed for athletes, workers, and individuals who have suffered a facial injury, or may potentially sustain an impact in that region. These devices may be considered a preventive measure, part of individual protection equipment, or, in case of a previous local injury, provide protection to enhance the recovery process. This study was initiated with the development of a 3D computational model, using computed tomography images and some specialized open-source software, such as InVesalius, 3D Slicer, and Meshlab. The geometrical modelling of the protective face masks was then developed using SolidWorks. Impact analyses, considering a set of preliminary material solutions, were conducted to simulate the impact of an external object on these devices, considering not only the overall stiffness performance of the mask but also the stress threshold value of 10 kPa, identified by Cao et al. [1], above which brain injuries may occur. The studies conducted demonstrate that, besides the advantages of customizing these masks for a better fit, different purposes and, therefore, different geometrical and material designs should be considered.

Keywords: customizable protective face masks, reverse engineering, computed tomography

1 Introduction

The procedure for the development of a product through reverse engineering and additive manufacturing can be divided and described in different ways. According to Wang et al. [2], this process consists of 3 stages: data acquisition and post-processing; progressive modeling; and product manufacture.

1.1 Data acquisition and post-processing

The reverse engineering technologies available for data capturing include photogrammetry, 3D scanning, and medical exams. In this case, the results of a computed tomography (CT) exam were used to develop the 3D model of the user.

The CT scan consists of an X-ray beam directed at the patient, with an associated computerized system and digital detectors located directly opposite the source, which generate signals that are processed and converted into reconstructed cross-sections of the human body, designated as tomographic images, and provide detailed information about the structure and anatomy of the organs. [3], [4]

The resulting tomographic images are produced in the Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) format, which is an international standard that presents the requirements for medical image formats and guarantees the proper data and quality for clinical use. According to the 'Patient Root Query Model', DICOM files consist of four hierarchical classes of information: patient; study; series; and image. Each is characterized by a numerical label, providing a globally unique value that ensures there's no misidentification between studies. [5]

Subsequently, the data was processed in programs like InVesalius and 3D Slicer, capable of reading the DICOM files and identifying the contained series and their respective objects under analysis.

1.2 Materials

The two primary construction requirements of personal protective equipment (PPE) for mechanical impacts are fracture resistance and impact energy absorption capacity, minimizing the loads experienced by the user [6]. Regarding a protective face mask, these are typically used by athletes after a fracture, providing protection and preventing recurring injuries during the healing process. Additionally, these devices are commonly constructed of Polycarbonate (PC). [7]

The mask functions as a physical barrier that distributes the impact load over a large surface area, allowing the dissipation of this force throughout the surrounding tissues and support structures, according to Farrington et al. [7]. Nevertheless, the authors emphasized the scarcity of scientific evidence published that corroborates this theory.

Even so, there are protective face masks available on the market, namely the Raptor device [8]. This product was developed through 3D scanning techniques, 3D printing, algorithms, and artificial intelligence, resulting in a model with impressive performance that received the 2020 Red Dot award for its innovative design. The Raptor mask is a resistant and lightweight device with a varying surface thickness, which provides adequate protection and ventilation of the user's face. Additionally, the construction of this device includes two layers: an outer rigid shell and an inner layer of padding.

The investigation by Gama et al. [9] presents a study on the incorporation of cork in 3D printed PU foams. The authors' main focus was improving the low thermal conductivity of the rigid PU foams by introducing a second material with the same characteristic. Considering this, cork is a material of vegetal origin with low density, elastic behavior, and, more importantly, low thermal conductivity. To better understand the impact of this combination, a comparison of the mechanical properties of PU foam composites with different quantities of cork incorporated was made. One of the conclusions of this analysis is that the composite is suitable for applications in thermal insulation with damping capabilities.

1.3 Testing

Cao et al. [1] studied the risk of brain injuries and concussions for football players when unintentionally hit with a ball. Bearing that in mind, this investigation included a finite element model (FEM) of the full human body for analyzing the ball impact in six distinct locations of the head and at different impact velocities, ranging from 10 m/s to 60 m/s. It was concluded that the typical maximum ball speed for a powerful shot is between 25 m/s and 35 m/s.

To determine the risks of brain injuries in the conducted simulations, Cao et al. [1] defined threshold values for the analyzed intracranial pressures, Von Mises stresses, and principal strains. In terms of the maximum stress, their research provided the limits of 10 kPa and 20 kPa, above which there's a risk of a short-term and a long-term concussion, respectively.

2 Data post-processing

The protection device development was initiated with the acquired data post-processing. More specifically, this procedure focused on analyzing the CT scan results to reconstruct a 3D model of the patient's head. Therefore, the obtained images were imported into the programs InVesalius and 3D Slicer. The use of both software allowed a comparative analysis of their image processing capabilities and the reconstructed surfaces quality.

2.1 InVesalius

The first analysis began with the CT results segmentation in InVesalius. This procedure consisted of creating a mask, i.e., identifying the image's region of interest, which is a time-consuming task, as it requires multiple tests and adjustments. Thereafter, the surface was developed from the defined region of interest. As shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** (a), the reconstruction result includes the equipment supports and visible layers. Nevertheless, this model exhibits an acceptable level of surface quality, and the small issues identified will be addressed in the next stage of the study.

2.2 3D Slicer

Subsequently, the same DICOM files analysis was performed in 3D Slicer. In this study, similarly to the process in InVesalius, the complete segmentation of the images was achieved, and the reconstructed surface was developed. The resulting model, in **Error! Reference source not found.** (b), includes the supports for the CT equipment, visible layers in the top area, and some cavities on the surface. Despite the discontinuities in the outer layer, this reconstruction presents an adequate surface quality.

2.3 Comparative analysis of the results in InVesalius and 3D Slicer

Analyzing the results achieved in InVesalius and 3D Slicer (Figure 1), it was possible to verify many similarities between the two, such as the reconstructed surfaces from the CT equipment and the visible layers in the top region of the head. However, a substantial difference between these results is the presence of cavities on the surface developed through 3D Slicer, which affects the main goal in this study of obtaining an accurate rendering of the outer layer, i.e., the patient's skin. In addition, the existence of cavities reduces the model's overall surface quality. Considering all these factors, it was concluded that the reconstruction in InVesalius provides a better option to continue developing the product.

Figure 1. Surface reconstruction in (a) InVesalius and (b) 3D Slicer

3 Models Development

The next step involved removing unnecessary surfaces from the model, such as the equipment support and the head interior in the software Meshlab, as shown in Figure 2 (a). Additionally, the result of this exclusion is presented in Figure 2 (b).

Figure 2. (a) selected regions for removal, (b) result of the cleaning process in Meshlab.

Thereafter, the simplified model was imported into SolidWorks, Figure 3 (a), where the slicing tool was applied, Figure 3 (b), and subsequently reconstructed into a surface.

Figure 3. (a) imported 3D model, (b) result of the model slicing in SolidWorks

Following this, the discontinuities in the top and bottom regions of the model were addressed by generating new surfaces. Ultimately, these were all merged and converted into a solid body, as shown Figure 4.

Figure 4. Solid head model in SolidWorks

3.1 Development of the face mask model

The new reconstructed surface was used to obtain the front features of the head and a rough shape of the region of interest for the device. Subsequently, the outer and middle surface layers of the face mask were created from the original model. Thereafter, the three surfaces were trimmed to achieve a consistent format and an approximation of the intended design for the face mask, Figure 5.

Figure 5. Trimmed surfaces for the mask in SolidWorks

At this point, the analysis was divided into two parts: the inner and outer layers of the mask. These were created as solid bodies and combined using an assembly in SolidWorks. Thus, the base model for the face mask was obtained (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Protective face mask model in SolidWorks

3.2 Development of safety straps

To carry out accurate simulations and verifications of the protective face mask, it was necessary to include a safety strap, guaranteeing the proper fixation of the device. Furthermore, this inclusion was essential for conducting a more realistic and accurate performance analysis, as it affects the constraints within the simulated assembly.

Figure 7 presents the developed model, where the areas highlighted in red refer to the contact points of this component with the outer layer of the mask, and the blue area highlights the contact with the head.

Figure 7. Safety strap for the mask in SolidWorks

4 Verification of the model construction

For the verification of the face mask construction, a preliminary selection of materials for each component was necessary, as shown in Table 1. The outer layer and safety strap were based on the investigations by Farrington et al. [7] and Han et al. [10], while the inner layer material and respective properties were derived from Gama et al. [9]. In addition, alternative options were later tested to achieve the best protection performance.

Table 1. Selected materials for the components

Component	Material	Elastic Modulus [MPa]	Poisson's Ratio	Mass Density [kg.m ⁻³]	Tensile Strength [MPa]
Outer layer	PC	2410	0.3897	1070	40
Inner layer	PU-1% cork	0.782	0.3	262	0.792
Safety strap	PET	2960	0.37	1420	57.3

For the following analysis, the use of this device by an elite football player during a match was considered. In particular, the studies conducted replicate the impact of a football on a player's face.

Considering this, it was necessary to construct a model of the ball. These consist of 2 components: an outer layer, typically made of composite panels, and an interior layer of natural rubber. For this study, the panels were replaced by a single layer made of PU foam, selected based on the analysis of FIFA-approved balls on the market. In terms of dimensions, the reference was an official size 5 ball, which included an external diameter of 220 mm, an outer layer thickness of 2.2 mm, an inner layer thickness of 0.8 mm, and an internal pressure of 0.9 bar. [1]

The next step consisted of simulating the ball impact with the head model without the face mask, providing reference values that aided in the evaluation of the device's protection performance. More specifically, a nonlinear dynamic analysis in SolidWorks was used to simulate the collision at 35 m/s, and the resulting Von Mises stress diagram is presented in Figure 8 (a), where the maximum value of 1.675 MPa is identified. Additionally, the stresses experienced at the surface level of the model are shown in Figure 8 (b), with the highest stress being 1.01 MPa. Both results are significantly higher than the limit of 10 kPa, which was defined after an analysis of the different threshold values for brain injuries presented in the investigation by Cao et al. [1].

Figure 8. (a) Von Mises stress distribution diagram, (b) stresses in the surface head for the impact without the mask in SolidWorks

Thereafter, the first simulation with this protection device considered an impact in the central area of the face, Figure 9, with an initial velocity of 35 m/s, and the most important factor was ensuring the contact between the ball and the device. In addition, the other interactions between the components of the mask were also defined.

Figure 9. Central impact of the ball with the mask

With this simulation, the maximum Von Mises stress and the deformation of the device were verified, Figure 10. More specifically, the maximum stress of 30.32 MPa was identified in the outer layer of the face mask, which is below the tensile strength of 40 MPa of the component material. In the deformation graphic, the maximum value of 8.399 mm was observed in the nose region of the outer layer. This result is concerning, seeing as the total thickness of the face mask is only 6 mm. This deformation confirms that the constructed model requires some modifications, in terms of materials or dimensions, to lower this value and improve the protective performance of the device.

Figure 10. (a) Von Mises stress distribution diagram, (b) deformation diagram

The primary concern for the evaluation of the mask performance was the loads experienced by the user. Thereby, the results of the maximum stresses felt in the head and its surface were obtained and shown in Figure 11. As can be seen, both results are above the defined limit of 10 kPa, and although these are very high and pose a risk of brain injury, they present a reduction of approximately 98.4% in the head model and 97.5% in the head surface, compared to the reference values. Therefore, confirming the advantages of using the face mask for the user.

	Value	Unit		Value	Unit
(a) Sum	1,611e+08	N/m ²	(b) Sum	2,366e+07	N/m ²
(a) Avg	2,918e+02	N/m ²	(b) Avg	2,822e+02	N/m ²
(a) Max	2,637e+04	N/m ²	(b) Max	2,492e+04	N/m ²
(a) Min	1,251e+00	N/m ²	(b) Min	1,251e+00	N/m ²
(a) RMS	6,332e+02	N/m ²	(b) RMS	7,488e+02	N/m ²

Figure 11. (a) stresses in the head model, (b) stress in the surface of the head model

Given the results of the first simulation, multiple studies were conducted considering alterations in the components' dimensions and materials.

For the outer layer of the device, 3 studies were performed, taking into account 2 different materials and thicknesses (Table 2). In the case of the increasing the dimension from 2 mm to 4 mm, the analysis with PC showed a substantially lower maximum Von Mises stress on the assembly, higher stresses experienced in the head model and, more importantly, a lower maximum deformation, seeing as the obtained value of 4,652 mm represents roughly a 48% reduction of the original model deformation and is below the total model thickness. Additionally, by altering the PC material with the composite ABS-20% carbon fiber in the 4 mm layer, the analysis presented improvements in the stresses experienced by the user, since the values obtained were the lowest of all 3 studies, and a slight increase in the maximum Von Mises stress and the deformation. Since the focus of the evaluation is the minimization of the loads transferred to the user, the improvements in the stresses experienced in the head model were significant enough to consider this the best design for the outer layer of the face mask.

Table 2. Model variations for the outer layer

Thickness [mm]	Material	Maximum Von Mises stress on the assembly [MPa]	Maximum stress on the head model [kPa]	Maximum stress on the surface of the head model [kPa]	Maximum deformation on the assembly [mm]
2	PC	30.32	26.37	24.92	8.99
4	PC	19.09	33.53	28.11	4.652
4	ABS-20% carbon fiber	19.45	25.80	24.60	4.975

In the analysis of the inner layer of the device, 2 different materials were compared. The results shown in Table 3 prove that, although the material EPS provides a substantial decrease in the maximum deformation of the device, it results in extremely high stresses felt by the head model and, for that reason, this material is considered inadequate for the protection of the user in the considered conditions.

Table 3. Model variations for the inner layer

Thickness [mm]	Material	Maximum Von Mises stress on the assembly [MPa]	Maximum stress on the head model [kPa]	Maximum stress on the surface of the head model [kPa]	Maximum deformation on the assembly [mm]
4	PU-1% cork	30.32	26.37	24.92	8.99
4	EPS	31.97	1688	1345	4.816

5 Conclusions

For every simulation conducted, the focus of the evaluation was the maximum stresses obtained in the head model. In other words, the primary goal was to create a device that minimizes the load transferred to the user.

In the studies of the exterior part of the mask, combining a 4 mm layer with the ABS-20% carbon fiber composite resulted in improvements in all evaluated parameters. Notably, this model presents the lowest stresses experienced in the head. Although it didn't provide the best deformation result, it was still below the device thickness and led to a significant improvement over the original construction.

For the analysis of the inner layer, the material EPS was tested, and the extremely high stress verified in the head model proved that this material doesn't guarantee the user's safety. Consequently, the composite PU-1% cork was considered the best option for the protection performance of the device.

The conducted studies verify that there are still many aspects in the construction of this model to explore. While the simulation results demonstrate the immense impact of the mask in reducing the stresses felt by the user, these values are still very high and present a great risk of brain injuries for the player in the considered conditions. Additionally, these studies show considerably high values of deformation, above the total thickness of the device, which can result in other types of injuries for the user. The increase of the outer layer thickness provided a value of maximum deformation in the assembly more acceptable, seeing as it is inferior to the total thickness of the mask. However, another aspect to note is that these types of devices require the minimization of their thickness to guarantee they don't affect the field of view of the user.

In conclusion, more studies to the face mask must be performed to find the best combination of dimensions and materials that result in the minimization of the loads transferred to the head and the reduction of the maximum model deformation, mitigating the risk of injury for the player, and an adequate thickness that doesn't affect the user's field of view. Additionally, once the optimized model is obtained, further analysis must include an evaluation of the mask's thermal performance and the creation of ventilation areas in the device.

Acknowledgements. The authors acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) for its financial support via the project LAETA Base Funding (DOI: 10.54499/UIDB/50022/2020).

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2.5 Customized Protective Helmets: Reverse Engineering and Design

Authors:

Ana S.A. Gonçalves

Inês C.J. Barbosa

Maria A.R. Loja

Customized Protective Helmets: Reverse Engineering and Design

Ana S.A. Gonçalves¹, Inês C.J. Barbosa^{1,2}, Maria A.R. Loja^{1,2}

¹*CIMOSM, ISEL, IPL – Centro de Investigação em Modelação e Optimização de Sistemas Multifuncionais, Av. Conselheiro Emídio Navarro 1, 1959-007 Lisboa, Portugal*

²*IDMEC, Instituto Superior de Engenharia de Lisboa, Instituto Politécnico de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal*
A46132@alunos.isel.pt, ines.barbosa@isel.pt, amelia.loja@isel.pt

Abstract. This work presents an exploratory study on the modeling and design of customized protective helmets, which can be produced via additive manufacturing. Helmets may be found in different areas, ranging from individual protection devices in industrial environments to athletes' protection and various healthcare aims. In the present study, it was considered the development of a customized helmet to be used in sports. The dataflow of this work started with a combined reverse engineering process using medical computed tomography images and photogrammetry to achieve the required completeness of the computational model. These two acquisition techniques were used along with specialized open-source software, such as InVesalius and MeshLab, to obtain the 3D surface. The protective helmets' geometrical modelling was then developed using SolidWorks. Impact analyses, considering a set of preliminary material solutions, were conducted to simulate the impact of the helmet with an external object. To assess the overall helmet's performance, the stress threshold value of 10 kPa, identified by Cao et al. [1], was adopted as the value above which brain injuries may occur. The studies conducted demonstrate that, besides the advantages of customized helmets, further studies are desirable for enhanced performance and protection characteristics.

Keywords: customized protective helmets, reverse engineering, computed tomography, photogrammetry.

1 Introduction

Generally, the process of developing a product through reverse engineering and additive manufacturing can be divided into three main steps: data acquisition, data post-processing, and 3D printing of the product. [2]

1.1 Data acquisition and post-processing

The required data for developing the device can be obtained in a variety of ways, including photogrammetry, 3D scanning, or medical exams, such as computed tomography (CT) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). In this study, the results of a CT scan composed most of the necessary data, and a secondary group of images was collected to construct a complementary model via photogrammetry.

Photogrammetry is a technique for generating 3D models from multiple two-dimensional (2D) images. This process requires capturing several images from different angles, which, with the use of software like Agisoft, allows the analysis of the surface dimensions and properties and the respective object reconstruction. One advantage of this technique is the possibility of using simple and everyday cameras for data capturing, such as a cellphone. However, it's important to note that by rebuilding a 3D model from 2D images, there's always lost information about the real object. Nonetheless, this issue can be minimized with the capture of more images from different angles. [3], [4], [5]

CT is a diagnostic method that uses X-ray images, associated with a computerized system, to reconstruct cross-sections of the human body and provides detailed information about the structure and anatomy of the organs. More specifically, this equipment consists of a narrow X-ray beam directed at the patient, which moves along the ring-shaped structure, and is read by digital detectors located directly opposite the source. These readings generate signals, which are subsequently processed and converted into tomographic images. [6], [7]

The CT scan results are provided in the Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) format. This is an international standard that specifies medical image formats and ensures the data and quality required for clinical use. A DICOM file consists of four hierarchical classes of information, each characterized by a numerical label:

1. Patient – includes information such as their name, gender, age, etc.;
2. Study – this value is globally unique and guarantees that there's no misidentification between two studies, it includes information like the date and time of the exam, the type of exam, description, etc.;
3. Series – these are divided by unique identifiers (UID), which can be the reference plane or the organ/tissue in focus;
4. Image – information in the moment of the object under analysis. [8]

For the data post-processing phase, it was necessary to resort to programs capable of reading and analyzing DICOM files, such as InVesalius and 3D Slicer. These allow the identification of the different series contained in the files and the reconstruction of a specific layer or organ present in the selected group of images.

1.2 Materials

Personal protective equipment (PPE) for mechanical impacts has two main construction requirements: fracture resistance and impact energy absorption capacity, for minimizing the load transferred to the user. In the case of a protective helmet, they are usually divided into two parts: an external layer made of rigid plastics, like Polycarbonate (PC) or Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS); and an interior layer composed of damping and deformable materials, such as Polyurethane (PU) and Expanded Polystyrene (EPS). [9]

Furthermore, the investigation by Han et al. [10] presents an analysis of a helmet's performance when incorporated with a multidirectional impact protection system (MIPS). This study considered the construction of the outer layer in ABS, the inner layer in EPS, and the safety straps in Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET).

Regarding the cushioning part of the device, it's typically manufactured from EPS. However, an alternative material found in the literature research is a composite of PU foam and cork, which offers damping capabilities and is produced via 3D printing. [11]

Gama et al. [11] studied the influence of incorporating cork on the mechanical properties and damping behavior of 3D printed PU foams. The rigid PU foams are common in insulation applications because of their low thermal conductivity. Nevertheless, this property can be further improved by adding a second material with the same characteristic. Cork is a plant-based tissue that presents low density, elastic behavior, and low thermal conductivity. Moreover, their research proved that cork is capable of reducing vibrations and can be used as an effective passive damping material, due to its viscoelastic properties.

The investigation by Gama et al. [11] included a comparative analysis of PU foams with different percentages of cork incorporated and the respective mechanical properties for each composite. Therefore, this study verified that the addition of cork provides a decrease in density, thermal conductivity, and stiffness without compromising the thermal stability and performance of PU foams. They also concluded that the elastic behavior of these composites allows their application for thermal insulation with damping.

Additionally, the European standard EN 960:2006 defines the dimensional and construction characteristics for the head models used in the testing of protective helmets. According to this standard, the model selection depends on the type of test and the constraints of the assembly helmet/head. More specifically, in the case of a penetration test where the assembly is falling, the head model must be made of a metallic material. [12]

1.3 Testing

In the investigation by Han et al. [10], the helmet model protection performance was evaluated via simulations of impact with an anvil. More specifically, this analysis accounted for different anvil inclinations, 30°, 45°, and 60°, various impact positions, and impact velocities of 5 m/s and 8 m/s, which are considered the typical speeds for bicycle accidents. In terms of evaluation criteria, the authors considered the maximum linear and angular accelerations felt in the head, and, through multiple simulations, it was verified that the results increased with the impact velocity and decreased with the rise of inclination. Therefore, this analysis allowed the identification of the impact at 8 m/s with a 30° anvil as the worst case of protection performance for the device.

Cao et al. [1] investigated the risks of brain injuries and concussions in football players when unintentionally hit with a ball, to define the threshold of impact velocities that can result in these injuries. For that, they analyzed the intracranial pressure, the stresses and strains in the simulation results, and compared these values with the thresholds for brain injuries identified in their research. In particular, for the maximum Von Mises stresses, they concluded that, above 10 kPa, there's a risk of a short-duration concussion, and a risk of a long-duration concussion for stresses above 20 kPa.

2 Data post-processing

The post-processing of the obtained data was the first step in the development of the Protective Helmet, which included the DICOM files analysis and the reconstruction of a 3D model of the user's head using InVesalius.

This study started with the segmentation of the DICOM images. In that regard, the selected region of interest was obtained through multiple adjustments and tests.

Subsequently, this allowed the reconstruction of the intended head model, shown in **Erro! A origem da referência não foi encontrada.** Despite the resulting surface including the CT equipment supports and visible layers, the overall surface quality is adequate, and these small defects can be refined later in the study.

Figure 1. Reconstructed surface in InVesalius

3 Models Development

To initiate the process of developing the protection device, the cleaning of the reconstructed model was necessary. Thereby, the software Meshlab was used to remove the equipment support surfaces and the model interior, both unnecessary for this analysis. Figure 2 presents the selected regions to eliminate.

Figure 2. (a) and (b) selected regions for removal in Meshlab

Afterward, the simplified model was imported into the SolidWorks software, and the next step in this procedure consisted of slicing the model and, through the obtained intersection, reconstructing the surface presented in Figure 3. Ultimately, this new surface enabled the construction of a solid body.

Figure 3. New reconstructed surface in SolidWorks

3.1 Development of the helmet model

The helmet model development used the new reconstructed surface as a baseline mold to obtain an approximate format for the device. The following step included the construction of its outer and middle surfaces. Subsequently, the trimming of these three surfaces ensured an identical format between them and an approximation to the intended design of the helmet.

Thereafter, the solid bodies of the device's layers were constructed, allowing the assembly of the base model for the protection helmet in SolidWorks (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Helmet model in SolidWorks

3.2 Development of complementary models

To carry out accurate simulations and verifications of the helmet, it was necessary to construct additional auxiliary models. In particular, the development of a safety strap and, consequently, the inferior part of the head, i.e., the chin. These models were essential to conduct more realistic and accurate analyses of the helmet performance.

The photogrammetry technique allowed the construction of a complementary head model. This method began with data acquisition, more specifically, 121 images from different angles of the user, which were imported into the software Agisoft to reconstruct the point cloud.

Thereafter, the analysis was moved into Meshlab for the removal of the unnecessary points, while maintaining the areas of interest corresponding to the user's neck, chin, and face, and for the respective reconstruction of a surface.

Subsequently, this result was imported into SolidWorks. Nevertheless, only the lower half of the head has relevance for this study, as it complements the model developed with the DICOM files. Taking this into account, the chin area model was created, shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Trimmed surface of the lower half of the head in SolidWorks

Given this, a third part for the head was generated to provide a connecting component between the two models, and the complete assembly of the user's head was obtained (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Complete head model in SolidWorks

Regarding the safety strap, this component was important to the study due to its impact on the constraints of the device. Its inclusion provides more accurate results for the simulations, in terms of the stresses, deformations, and strains felt in the assembly. Figure 7 presents the developed device, where the areas highlighted in red refer to the contact points of this component with the outer layer of the helmet, and the blue areas highlight the contact with the head model.

Figure 7. Helmet safety strap

4 Verification of the model construction

The next phase of this study included selecting the materials for each component and verifying the developed protective helmet through impact simulations. This selection was provisional, as alternative options were later tested to achieve optimal protection performance of the device.

Table 1 presents the initial materials considered for each component. The inner layer is made of the composite PU-1% cork, based on the properties presented by Gama et al. [11]. For the outer layer and the safety strap, the selection was derived from Shi et al. [9] and Han et al. [10].

Table 1. Selected materials for the components

Component	Material	Elastic Modulus [MPa]	Poisson's Ratio	Mass Density [kg.m ⁻³]	Tensile Strength [MPa]
Outer layer	PC	2410	0.3897	1070	40
Inner layer	PU-1% cork	0.782	0.3	262	0.792
Safety strap	PET	2960	0.37	1420	57.3

In terms of the simulation, the impact of the helmet was studied through a nonlinear dynamic analysis in SolidWorks, with an anvil inclination of 30° and an initial velocity of 8 m/s, indicated by Han et al. [10] as the most critical impact scenario.

The first simulation examined the impact at the collision point represented in Figure 8. Concerning the study parameters, the most important factor was guaranteeing the contact between the anvil and the outer face of the device. In addition, the interactions between the helmet components were also considered.

Figure 8. Helmet impact with a 30° anvil in SolidWorks

The results of this analysis allowed the verification of the maximum Von Mises stress and deformation of the device (Figure 9). More specifically, the maximum stress was identified in the safety strap of the helmet with 23.79 MPa, which is below the tensile strength of 57.3 MPa of the component material. In the deformation diagram, the maximum value of 1.217 mm was observed in the outer layer of the helmet, which is smaller than the 4 mm thickness of this component.

Figure 9. (a) Von Mises stress distribution diagram, (b) deformation diagram in SolidWorks

However, the main concern for this study is the loads experienced by the user. For that reason, the verification of the resulting Von Mises stresses on the head model was required. Figure 10 presents the stresses obtained in this component, where the maximum value of 2.066 kPa is below the limit of 10 kPa, defined after the analysis of the different threshold values for brain injuries presented in the investigation by Cao et al. [1].

	Value	Unit
Sum	3,343e+07	N/m ²
Avg	5,412e+01	N/m ²
Max	2,066e+03	N/m ²
Min	1,313e+00	N/m ²
RMS	6,575e+01	N/m ²

Figure 10. Stresses on the head model

With the first analysis of the helmet successfully concluded, multiple studies were carried out with variations in the components' dimensions and materials.

Starting with the analysis of the inner layer of the helmet, two different materials were tested. Namely, the composites PU-1% cork and PU-5% cork developed by Gama et al. [11], which allowed the evaluation of the percentage influence on the protection performance of the device. As shown in Table 2, the composite PU-5% cork presents lower results for the maximum Von Mises stress and deformation in the assembly. Although the higher maximum deformation is in the PU-1% cork study, this value of 1.217 mm is observed in the outer layer of the helmet, which presents a 4 mm thickness within a total device thickness of 10 mm. Additionally, the focus of the evaluation is the minimization of the loads transferred to the helmet user, and that is verified for this material. Taking all these factors into consideration, the material PU-1% cork was regarded as the most adequate for this application.

Table 2. Model variations for the inner layer

Material	Maximum Von Mises stress on the assembly [MPa]	Maximum stress on the head model [kPa]	Maximum deformation on the assembly [mm]
PU-1% cork	23.79	2.066	1.217
PU-5% cork	17.3	2.668	1.043

The next analysis focused on the thickness variation for the outer layer of the device, more specifically, an increase of 1 mm was considered. In terms of the results (Table 3), the outcome of this alteration is an increase in the maximum stresses, and the only positive point is the reduction of the maximum deformation. Regardless, it's important to note that this is a very small reduction of 0.117 mm, considering the rise in layer thickness of 1 mm. For this reason, the 4 mm option was deemed the best for the user's protection.

Table 3. Model variations for the outer layer

Thickness [mm]	Material	Maximum Von Mises stress on the assembly [MPa]	Maximum stress on the head model [kPa]	Maximum deformation on the assembly [mm]
4	PC	23.79	2.066	1.217
5	PC	24.07	2.595	1.100

The final variation consisted of an increase in safety strap width, changing from 10 mm to 15 mm. All the previous simulations featured a model with 10 mm, that said, in the research conducted for the development of this device, it was found in the standard 1078:2012 [13], focused on the requirements for the construction of cycling and skating helmets, the minimum width allowed for the safety straps is 15 mm. Even though the previous studies prove that the constructed model provides the necessary protection performance for the user, a simulation was executed with a safety strap of 15 mm to verify its influence on the stress and deformation results.

From Table 4, it can be observed that this alteration has a significant impact on the maximum stresses. To be more precise, there's a reduction of approximately 10 kPa in the maximum Von Mises stress on the assembly, and the stress in the head model is minimized to 0.489 kPa. In addition, this alteration also provides a small decrease in the maximum deformation identified in the assembly. Considering this, it was easily concluded that the 15 mm safety strap is the best option for ensuring the user's protection.

Table 4. Model variations for the safety strap

Width [mm]	Maximum Von Mises stress on the assembly [MPa]	Maximum stress on the head model [kPa]	Maximum deformation on the assembly [mm]
10	23.79	2.066	1.217
15	13.11	0.489	1.054

5 Conclusions

The primary focus for every simulation was the evaluation of the identified stresses in the head model, with the objective of minimizing the loads transferred to the user.

In the analysis with different composites for the inner layer of the helmet, the results proved that the PU-1% cork is the best material for the intended application, given that it provided the lowest maximum stress in the head model.

For the outer layer, the assessment of the thickness influence proved that the increase by 1 mm was redundant and resulted in higher maximum stresses felt in the components.

The simulations of the safety straps included two models with different widths, 10 mm and 15 mm. Even though almost all the conducted studies included the 10 mm safety strap and proved the device has adequate protection performance, the results shown for the 15 mm strap present a significant reduction in the maximum stresses verified in the assembly and the head model. Also, as this conforms to the standard, it was concluded that the final model of the helmet must include the 15 mm safety strap.

All things considered, whereas the studies conducted confirmed that the model offers the necessary protection for the user, there are still various areas in this work to explore. More specifically, the next steps in the development of this device should include evaluations on the influence of the different impact angles, on the thermal performance of the helmet, and an analysis focused on the creation of ventilation areas in the model.

Acknowledgements. The authors acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) for its financial support via the project LAETA Base Funding (DOI: 10.54499/UIDB/50022/2020).

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2.6 Comparison between FEM and a meshfree method for impact analysis of an adhesive joint

Authors:

Luis D.C. Ramalho
Diogo C. Gonçalves
Rui D.S.G. Campilho
Jorge Belinha

Comparison between FEM and a meshfree method for impact analysis of an adhesive joint

Luís D.C. Ramalho¹, Diogo C. Gonçalves², Raul D.S.G. Campilho^{1,2}, Jorge Belinha^{1,2}

¹*Department of Mechanical Engineering, School of Engineering, Polytechnic of Porto
Rua Dr. António Bernardino de Almeida, 431, 4200-072, Porto, Portugal
ldr@isep.ipp.pt, raulcampilho@gmail.com, job@isep.ipp.pt*

²*INEGI, Institute of Mechanical Engineering
Rua Dr. Roberto Frias, 4200-465 Porto, Portugal
costa.goncalves.diogo@gmail.com*

Abstract. Considering the widespread use of adhesive joints, it is important to develop tools for their analysis. Currently, The Finite Element Method (FEM) is the most commonly used method to analyse adhesive joints. However, it is also important to explore different numerical methods, like meshfree methods, to learn if it is advantageous to use them in the analysis of adhesive joints. The static behaviour of adhesive joints is a well-studied field. Comparatively, their behaviour under impact is still not as widely understood. Considering some of the applications of adhesive joints, like wind turbine blades, cars, or airplanes, it is important to understand well their behaviour under impact, so it is important that the tools used for numerical analysis are well developed.

This work aims at performing a numerical analysis of an adhesive joint under impact using the FEM and a meshfree method, the Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM). The use of two different numerical methods is related to the goal of comparing them with each other and with experimental results. The comparison includes stress analysis in the adhesive layer and joint strength prediction using the Intensity of Singular Stress Fields (ISSF) criterion. The ISSF criterion consists in predicting joint failure based on the stress singularity that arises at the adhesive/adherent interface corner.

Keywords: Impact, Adhesive Joints, Meshless Methods, RPIM

1 Introduction

There are several joining methods such as bolting, welding, riveting or adhesive bonding. The choice of joining method is dependent on the type of application, nowadays adhesive bonding is used in several industries like the aeronautical, the automotive or the rail industries [1]. This occurs because adhesive joints have some important advantages over most other joining methods like a lower weight and an improved damage tolerance [2]. The increased use of adhesive joints creates a need for the development of tools to perform stress analysis or strength predictions. The oldest and simplest tools used for those purposes are analytical models like the Volkersen model [3] or the Goland-Reissner model [4]. However, these models are usually limited to only some types of joint and contain several assumptions that reduce their accuracy. The review by Ramalho et al. [5] shows that for static analysis the most commonly used method to predict the strength of adhesive joints are Cohesive Zone Models (CZM) in Finite Element Method (FEM) simulations.

In impact loading conditions CZM are also the most commonly used method to predict joint strength, but there are fewer works focused on impact loading conditions than in static loading conditions [6, 7]. Some cohesive properties, namely the cohesive strength in tension (t_n) and shear (t_s), are strain rate dependent, which means that to perform impact simulations new adhesive characterization tests are needed. While other properties like the tensile (G_{Ic}) and shear fracture toughness (G_{IIc}), the Young's modulus (E) and the Poisson's ratio (ν), tend to show no changes with different strain rates, as shown in literature [8–10]. Additionally, some cohesive properties also show dependency on adhesive thickness [11–13]. These limitations of CZM make it relevant the exploration of alternative ways of predicting joint strength. In adhesive joints it is common that failure initiates near the adhesive/adherent interface corner.

As such, analysing the stress singularity in that region, using the Intensity of Singular Stress Fields (ISSF), also referred as Generalised Stress Intensity Factor (GSIF), and using it to predict joint strength can be an alternative to CZM. In static loading conditions this type of singularity analysis has already been performed by some authors. Akhavan-Safar et al. [14] combined experimental tests with numerical simulations to estimate critical ISSF, which was then used to predict joint strength. It was observed that some geometric changes to the SLJ

change the critical ISSF, namely changes to overlap length, adherent thickness, adhesive thickness and free length. However Noda et al. [15] performed a similar analysis for SLJ and found that the critical ISSF does not change as adhesive thickness changes, so more investigation is needed.

The Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM) used in this work is a meshless method. This type of advanced discretization method can be used as an alternative to the commonly used Finite Element Method (FEM). The RPIM was proposed by Wang and Liu [16] and it has previously been used to predict the strength of adhesive joints in static loading conditions [17–19] and once in an impact loading case [20].

The main goal of this work is comparing the FEM and the RPIM in a singularity analysis of an adhesive joint under impact. This includes a comparison of the force and the ISSF over time, a comparison of the radial stress around the singularity corner and a comparison of the strength predictions using the ISSF criterion. To achieve that goal this work is divided into three sections, in addition to the introduction. Section 2 presents the formulation behind the RPIM, the Central Difference Method (CDM) and the ISSF. In Section 3 the joint being analysed is described and the results of the numerical analysis are discussed. The conclusions of this work are presented in Section 4.

2 Methodology

2.1 RPIM

A detailed description of the RPIM formulation is provided in reference [21]. However, since the RPIM is not as commonly used as the FEM, it is also important to provide a summarised description of this method in this section. The RPIM is able to discretize a given domain with only nodes, but it requires a background integration grid to create the integration points needed to solve the global system of equations. Figure 1 displays some of the basic concepts of the RPIM: the large dots represent the nodes of the domain, and the smaller dots represent the integration points which were created with a background integration grid and a 2×2 Gauss-Legendre quadrature, the same type of scheme used in Section 3. The RPIM, instead of having elements, has influence domains assigned to each integration point. In the approach used in this work each integration point has an influence domain made of the 10 nodes closest to the integration point. Two example influence domains are shown in Figure 1, as it can be seen there are nodes belonging to both influence domains, this is called domain overlapping and it is what ensures domain connectivity. Any given node will always belong to the influence domain of at least two different integration points.

Adhesive joints have an interface where the two materials, the adhesive and the adherent, join. To solve the global system of equations it is necessary to have domain connectivity in this region as well. However, if the influence domains in this region are created without any special care the results will not be as accurate. This occurs because the influence domain of the integration points of one material will have nodes inside the other material, this can be seen in the example of Figure 2a. To solve this issue the solution is to limit the influence domains to nodes of the same material of the integration point and to interface nodes, as exemplified in Figure 2b.

Figure 1. Creation of integration points and influence domains in the RPIM with an regular nodal distribution

Figure 2. (a) No restriction, (b) and restriction of the influence domains at a material interface

Another difference between the RPIM and the FEM are the shape functions. In the RPIM, these are created using a combination of a polynomial and a Radial Basis Function (RBF). In this work a linear polynomial was used, i.e. $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_i) = [1 \ x_i \ y_i]$, being x_i and y_i the coordinates of point i . The RBF used was the Multi-Quadratics RBF (MQ-RBF), which is one of the most common for the RPIM, it is defined as $r_i(x_j) = (d_{ij}^2 + (\gamma \cdot d_a)^2)^p$, where γ and p are function shape parameters, d_a is the weight of the integration point, and d_{ij} is the Euclidean norm between points i and j . Liu and Wang [22] concluded in their investigation that the ideal parameters for the RPIM are $p = 1.03$ and $\gamma = 1.42$, so those values were used in this work. The overall shape function that combines both the polynomial and the RBF is determined as follows:

$$\left\{ \Phi(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \quad \Psi(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \right\} = \left\{ \mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \quad \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \right\} \mathbf{M}_T^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_I)$ and $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_I)$ are column vectors of the RBF and the polynomial basis, respectively, obtained for the integration point \mathbf{x}_I and:

$$\mathbf{M}_T^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{R} \\ \mathbf{P}^T & \mathbf{Z} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

being \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{P} matrices built with the RBF and polynomial function values at each node. In equation 1, $\Phi(\mathbf{x}_I)$ is the vector containing the shape functions of integration point \mathbf{x}_I and $\Psi(\mathbf{x}_I)$ is a by-product vector with no relevant meaning. The full development leading to these shape functions is presented in reference [21]. The imposition of boundary conditions, the determination of the displacement, strain and stress fields in the RPIM is similar to the FEM and it is thoroughly described in many books and articles such as reference [21].

2.2 Dynamic Analysis

Since impact problems require a time integration with an explicit method, in this work the Central Difference Method (CDM) was used to perform that task. An explicit method calculates the equilibrium conditions at time $t + \Delta t$ using the equilibrium conditions at time t . The CDM has the advantage of only requiring the calculation of the displacements for each time step, the velocities and accelerations can be calculated but they are not mandatory. However, the CDM is only conditionally stable, this means that the time step has to obey a stability condition; otherwise, the solution is unstable. The CDM stability condition is $\Delta t \leq 2/\varphi_{max}$, being Δt the time step and φ_{max} the largest natural angular frequency of the structure. For a dynamic analysis, like an impact problem, the equilibrium equations are the following:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{R} \quad (3)$$

being \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{K} the mass, damping and stiffness matrices, respectively; while $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}$, $\dot{\mathbf{u}}$ and \mathbf{u} are the acceleration, velocity and displacement vectors; and \mathbf{R} is the vector of external forces. To perform the integration using the CDM it is necessary to follow the procedure shown in the flowchart of Figure 3. Considering a domain Ω , the mass, damping, and stiffness matrices referred in the flowchart are defined as:

$$\mathbf{M} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}^T \rho \mathbf{N} d\Omega \tag{4}$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}^T c \mathbf{N} d\Omega \tag{5}$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} d\Omega \tag{6}$$

where ρ is density, c is the damping factor, \mathbf{D} is material constitutive matrix, \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{N} in the 2D case are:

$$\mathbf{N} = \varphi \mathbf{I} \tag{7}$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix} \tag{8}$$

being φ the shape functions and \mathbf{I} the identity matrix. Two of the initial displacement, velocity, and acceleration are then defined according to the problem studied, and the other is calculated with equation 3 to maintain consistency. In this work the time step was defined as $\Delta t = 0.99 \Delta t_{crit}$, to ensure that the stability condition is obeyed. To initialize the problem it is necessary to calculate the displacement at $-\Delta t$, which is done as follows:

$$-\Delta t \mathbf{U} = {}^0 \mathbf{U} - \Delta t {}^0 \dot{\mathbf{U}} + \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} {}^0 \ddot{\mathbf{U}} \tag{9}$$

Then, considering the following integration constants [23]:

Figure 3. CDM flowchart

$$a_0 = \frac{1}{\Delta t^2}; \quad a_1 = \frac{1}{2\Delta t}; \quad a_2 = 2a_0; \quad a_3 = \frac{1}{a_2}; \quad (10)$$

the final step of the initialization process is the calculation of the effective mass matrix:

$$\mathbf{M}_{\text{ef}} = a_0 \mathbf{M} + a_1 \mathbf{C} \quad (11)$$

The iterative process starts by determining ${}^t\mathbf{R}_{\text{ef}}$ [23]:

$${}^t\mathbf{R}_{\text{ef}} = {}^t\mathbf{R} - (\mathbf{K} - a_2 \mathbf{M}) {}^t\mathbf{U} - (a_0 \mathbf{M} - a_1 \mathbf{C}) {}^{t-\Delta t}\mathbf{U} \quad (12)$$

it is important to note that for the first time step ${}^{t-\Delta t}\mathbf{U}$ is ${}^{-\Delta t}\mathbf{U}$, calculated using equation 9, for the other time steps it is simply the displacement of the previous time step. Finally, the system of equations $\mathbf{M}_{\text{ef}} {}^{t+\Delta t}\mathbf{U} = {}^t\mathbf{R}_{\text{ef}}$ is solved for ${}^{t+\Delta t}\mathbf{U}$. Then the time is updated and it is checked if the end of the simulation has been reached, if so it stops, otherwise it continues into the next time step.

2.3 ISSF

In a three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system the constitutive law of a material can be defined as $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, where \mathbf{C} is the following symmetric matrix:

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/E_1 & -\nu_{12}/E_1 & -\nu_{13}/E_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{21}/E_2 & 1/E_2 & -\nu_{23}/E_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{31}/E_3 & -\nu_{32}/E_3 & 1/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{23} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{13} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

being $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ the stress vector and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ the strain vector, in Voigt notation. Given that \mathbf{C} is symmetric, the following must be true: $\nu_{12}/E_1 = \nu_{21}/E_2$, $\nu_{12}/E_1 = \nu_{21}/E_2$ and $\nu_{12}/E_1 = \nu_{21}/E_2$. The Stroh formalism [24] is defined by the following eigensystem:

$$\mathbf{N}\boldsymbol{\xi}_\alpha = p_\alpha \boldsymbol{\xi}_\alpha \quad (14)$$

where p_α are the eigenvalues and $\boldsymbol{\xi}_\alpha$ the eigenvectors of this system. This system has 6 eigenvectors and eigenvalues, and \mathbf{N} is defined as:

$$\mathbf{N} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{N}_1 & \mathbf{N}_2 \\ \mathbf{N}_3 & \mathbf{N}_1^T \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

being $\mathbf{N}_1 = -\mathbf{T}^{-1}\mathbf{R}^T$, $\mathbf{N}_2 = -\mathbf{T}^{-1}$ and $\mathbf{N}_3 = -\mathbf{R}\mathbf{T}^{-1}\mathbf{R}^T - \mathbf{Q}$, and:

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{11} & C_{16} & C_{15} \\ C_{16} & C_{66} & C_{56} \\ C_{15} & C_{56} & C_{55} \end{pmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{R} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{16} & C_{12} & C_{14} \\ C_{66} & C_{26} & C_{46} \\ C_{56} & C_{25} & C_{45} \end{pmatrix}; \quad \mathbf{T} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{66} & C_{26} & C_{46} \\ C_{26} & C_{22} & C_{24} \\ C_{46} & C_{24} & C_{44} \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Since the eigenvalues and eigenvectors from equation 14 are complex, if p_α and $\boldsymbol{\xi}_\alpha$ are valid for Equation 3, so are \bar{p}_α and $\bar{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_\alpha$, with the overbar representing the complex conjugate. The eigenvectors can be divided into two parts, $\boldsymbol{\xi}_\alpha = [\mathbf{a}_\alpha^T \ \mathbf{b}_\alpha^T]$, the first part (\mathbf{a}_α) is proportional to the displacement vector and the second part (\mathbf{b}_α) is proportional to the traction vector. Transverse isotropic materials, like the unidirectional fibre-reinforced polymer used in Section 3, have three different eigenvalues and three linearly independent eigenvectors and their corresponding conjugates. However, isotropic materials, like the adhesive used in Section 3, have a single eigenvalue $p = i$ and two linearly independent eigenvectors. Therefore, a modification to the Stroh formalism, presented in Equation 14, is needed [25]:

$$\mathbf{N}\boldsymbol{\xi}_1 = p\boldsymbol{\xi}_1; \quad \mathbf{N}\boldsymbol{\xi}_2 = p\boldsymbol{\xi}_2 + \boldsymbol{\xi}_1; \quad \mathbf{N}\boldsymbol{\xi}_3 = p\boldsymbol{\xi}_3 \quad (17)$$

this means Equation 14 is used to determine ξ_1 and ξ_3 , but $\xi_2 = [\mathbf{a}_2^T \ \mathbf{b}_2^T]$ is determined as follows [25]:

$$-[\mathbf{Q} + (\mathbf{R} + \mathbf{R}^T)p + \mathbf{T}p^2]\mathbf{a}_2 = (2p\mathbf{T} + \mathbf{R} + \mathbf{R}^T)\mathbf{a}_1 \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_2 = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{a}_1 + (\mathbf{R}^T + p\mathbf{T})\mathbf{a}_2 \quad (19)$$

A vector $\mathbf{w}(r, \theta)^T = [\mathbf{u}(r, \theta)^T \ \varphi(r, \theta)^T]$, where \mathbf{u} is the displacement vector and φ is the stress function vector, can be defined as [25]:

$$\mathbf{w}(r, \theta)^T = r^\lambda \mathbf{X} \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{q} \quad (20)$$

being \mathbf{q} a constant vector, $\mathbf{X} = [\xi_1 \ \xi_2 \ \xi_3 \ \bar{\xi}_1 \ \bar{\xi}_2 \ \bar{\xi}_3]$ and, for materials with three linearly independent eigenvectors and three eigenvalues [25], $\mathbf{Z}(\theta)$ is given by:

$$\mathbf{Z}(\theta) = \begin{Bmatrix} \langle \zeta_\alpha^\lambda(\theta) \rangle & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \langle \bar{\zeta}_\alpha^\lambda(\theta) \rangle \end{Bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

where the angle brackets represent diagonal matrices. For materials with just two linearly independent eigenvectors and one eigenvalue, $\mathbf{Z}(\theta)$ also depends on λ and it is defined as [25]:

$$\mathbf{Z}(\theta, \lambda) = \begin{Bmatrix} \Psi(\theta, \lambda) & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \bar{\Psi}(\theta, \lambda) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

with:

$$\Psi(\theta, \lambda) = \begin{Bmatrix} \zeta_1^\lambda(\theta) & K(\theta, \lambda)\zeta_1^\lambda(\theta) & 0 \\ 0 & \zeta_1^\lambda(\theta) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \zeta_3^\lambda(\theta) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

being $K(\theta, \lambda)\zeta_1^\lambda(\theta) = \lambda \sin(\theta)\zeta_1(\theta)$ and $\zeta_\alpha^\lambda(\theta) = [\cos(\theta) + p_\alpha \sin(\theta)]^\lambda$. Considering a material m in a bi-material wedge, defined by an initial angle θ_{m-1} and an end angle θ_m , the following relation can be established [25]:

$$\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_m)^T = \mathbf{E}(\lambda, \theta_m, \theta_{m-1})\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_{m-1}) \quad (24)$$

being:

$$\mathbf{E}(\lambda, \theta_m, \theta_{m-1}) = \mathbf{X} \mathbf{Z}^\lambda(\theta_m) [\mathbf{Z}^\lambda(\theta_{m-1})]^{-1} \mathbf{X}^{-1} \quad (25)$$

where $\mathbf{Z}^\lambda(\theta_m) [\mathbf{Z}^\lambda(\theta_{m-1})]^{-1}$ can be simplified to $\mathbf{Z}^\lambda(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1})$, which for materials with three linearly independent eigenvectors and three eigenvalues gives [25]:

$$\mathbf{Z}^\lambda(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1}) = \begin{Bmatrix} \langle \zeta_\alpha^\lambda(\theta, \theta_{m-1}) \rangle & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \langle \bar{\zeta}_\alpha^\lambda(\theta, \theta_{m-1}) \rangle \end{Bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

while for materials with just two linearly independent eigenvectors and one eigenvalue it is also dependent on λ and is defined as [25]:

$$\mathbf{Z}^\lambda(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1}) = \begin{Bmatrix} \Psi(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1}, \lambda) & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \bar{\Psi}(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1}, \lambda) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

with:

$$\Psi^\lambda(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1}, \lambda) = \begin{Bmatrix} \zeta_1^\lambda(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1}) & K(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1}, \lambda)\zeta_1^\lambda(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1}) & 0 \\ 0 & \zeta_1^\lambda(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \zeta_3^\lambda(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1}) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

where $\zeta_1^\lambda(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1}) = \zeta_1^\lambda(\theta_m)/\zeta_1^\lambda(\theta_{m-1})$ and:

$$K(\theta_m, \theta_{m-1}, \lambda) = \frac{\lambda \sin(\theta_m - \theta_{m-1})}{\zeta_1(\theta_m) \zeta_1(\theta_{m-1})} \quad (29)$$

In a wedge made of two perfectly bonded materials, as in Figure 4, it is possible to relate $\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_0)$ with $\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_2)$. If $\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_1) = \mathbf{E}(\lambda, \theta_1, \theta_0) \mathbf{w}(r, \theta_0)$ and $\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_2) = \mathbf{E}(\lambda, \theta_2, \theta_1) \mathbf{w}(r, \theta_1)$:

$$\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_2) = \mathbf{K}_W(\lambda) \mathbf{w}(r, \theta_0) \quad (30)$$

being $\mathbf{K}_W(\lambda) = \mathbf{E}(\lambda, \theta_2, \theta_1) \mathbf{E}(\lambda, \theta_1, \theta_0)$ called the transfer matrix. Now, it is necessary to impose the boundary conditions. In adhesive joints, both outer faces of the interface wedge are free, thus $\varphi(r, \theta_0) = \varphi(r, \theta_2) = \mathbf{0}$ must be imposed. Thus, the following boundary condition matrices are used [26]:

$$\mathbf{D}_0 = \mathbf{D}_2 = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

These boundary condition matrices are used to modify the transfer matrix [26]:

$$\mathbf{K}_{WBC}(\lambda) = \mathbf{D}_0 \mathbf{K}_W \mathbf{D}_2^T \quad (32)$$

Considering the boundary conditions, the system of equations is rewritten as [26]:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1} \\ \mathbf{u}(r, \theta_2) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{WBC}^{(1)}(\lambda) & \mathbf{K}_{WBC}^{(2)}(\lambda) \\ \mathbf{K}_{WBC}^{(3)}(\lambda) & \mathbf{K}_{WBC}^{(4)}(\lambda) \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1} \\ \mathbf{u}(r, \theta_0) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

From Equation 33, the following is verified: $\mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1} = \mathbf{K}_{WBC}^{(2)}(\lambda) \mathbf{u}(r, \theta_0)$. Therefore, a non-trivial solution is found if and only if:

$$|\mathbf{K}_{WBC}^{(2)}(\lambda)| = 0 \quad (34)$$

This is how the characteristic exponents of the bi-material corner are obtained. In any corner the number of λ that can be obtained is infinite. However, only $\lambda < 1$ are essential to study the singularity, because they are the ones characterizing the singularity. With λ , it is now possible to determine the stress and displacement functions around the interface corner. For a given angle (θ) inside a material (m) the stress functions are [25]:

$$f_{rr} = -\mathbf{s}_r^T(\theta) \varphi_{,\theta}(r, \theta)/r; \quad f_{\theta\theta} = \mathbf{n}^T(\theta) \varphi_{,r}(r, \theta); \quad f_{r\theta} = -\mathbf{n}^T(\theta) \varphi_{,\theta}(r, \theta)/r = \mathbf{s}_r^T(\theta) \varphi_{,r}(r, \theta); \quad (35)$$

and the displacements are [25]:

$$g_r = -\mathbf{s}_r^T(\theta) \mathbf{u}(r, \theta)/r; \quad g_\theta = \mathbf{n}^T(\theta) \mathbf{u}(r, \theta); \quad (36)$$

where $\mathbf{s}_r^T = [\cos(\theta) \quad \sin(\theta) \quad 0]$ and $\mathbf{n}^T = [\sin(\theta) \quad -\cos(\theta) \quad 0]$. To determine the components in Equations 35 and 36, it is first necessary to determine $\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_0)$ and $\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_1)$ for each λ . First, it is known that $\varphi(r, \theta_0) = \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3}$, due to the boundary conditions, and \mathbf{u}_0 is determined by solving $\mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} = \mathbf{K}_{WBC}^{(2)}(\lambda) \mathbf{u}(r, \theta_0)$. So, $\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_0)$ can

Figure 4. Angles of the materials and angular coordinates at the interface corner

be assembled as $\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_0)^T = [\mathbf{u}(r, \theta_0)^T \ \boldsymbol{\varphi}(r, \theta_0)^T]^T$. Knowing $\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_0)$, $\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_q)$ is determined by simply using Equation 24. Then, the components of equations 35 and 36 for each λ , and its derivatives in order to r and θ , in a material (m) and at a given angle (θ), inside m , can be determined using equation 24, being the angle θ_m substituted by θ . The components of equations 28 and 29 have to be standardized, because if $\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_0)$ is a solution so is $c\mathbf{w}(r, \theta_0)$, where c is any constant. In this work, this standardization was performed by finding the maximum value of the components in the angle range encompassing the whole corner and dividing all the components by that value. With the singularity components (λ), and the stress (f) and displacement (g) functions near the singularity already calculated, the stress and displacement are:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n H_k r^{\lambda_k - 1} f_{ij}(\lambda_k, \theta) \quad (37)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_j = \sum_{k=1}^n H_k r^{\lambda_k} g_j(\lambda_k, \theta) \quad (38)$$

where n is the number of singularity exponents (λ), which depends on the interface corners geometry and materials. H_k is the ISSF or GSIF, which is a scalar value related to the singularity component k . There are several ways to determine the ISSF. For example, Qian and Akisanya [27] used a line integral encircling the interface corner to determine the ISSF. The approach used in this work is similarly to the method used by Klusák et al. [28], where the ISSF was determined by extrapolating it to the corner from values near the corner. This method requires a n number of points at different angles (α) and at a fixed radius (r) to determine a n number of ISSF, e.g., if there are two singularity components λ_1 and λ_2 , two different angles are needed. Therefore, H can be determined at r using the following equation:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} r^{\lambda_1 - 1} f_{\theta\theta}(\lambda_1, \alpha_1) & \cdots & r^{\lambda_n - 1} f_{\theta\theta}(\lambda_n, \alpha_1) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r^{\lambda_1 - 1} f_{\theta\theta}(\lambda_1, \alpha_n) & \cdots & r^{\lambda_n - 1} f_{\theta\theta}(\lambda_n, \alpha_n) \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} H_1 \\ \vdots \\ H_n \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{\theta\theta}(r, \alpha_1) \\ \vdots \\ \sigma_{\theta\theta}(r, \alpha_n) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (39)$$

where $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ is extracted from the RPIM simulations. The solution of Equation 39 is obtained for several different r , and it is then extrapolated to $r = 0$ mm, from an r interval where it is stable, to obtain H at the interface corner.

3 Results

3.1 Geometry and properties

Figure 5a shows the SLJ subjected to an impact load analysed in this work. The SLJ dimensions are also shown in Figure 5a. In this work three different overlap lengths (L_O) are tested: 12.5 mm, 25 mm and 50 mm, to assess the influence of this parameter on joint strength. The adhesive used in this joint was Araldite® AV138, with the following properties: 4.89 ± 0.81 GPa, $\nu = 0.35$ and $\rho = 1700$ kg/m³ [29]. The adherent is a Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) pre-preg SEAL® (SEAL® Texipreg HS 160 RM) with a [0]₂₀ lay-up, with the following mechanical properties: $E_x = 109$ GPa, $E_y = E_z = 8.819$ GPa, $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{xz} = 0.342$, $\nu_{yz} = 0.380$, $G_{xy} = G_{xz} = 4315$, $G_{yz} = 3200$ and $\rho = 1227$ kg/m³ [30]. The impact material, to which an initial velocity is imposed, is a fictitious material to achieve an impact energy of 40 J, and it has the following properties: 1000 GPa, $\nu = 0.3$ and $\rho = 23,22 \times 10^6$ kg/m³. The initial imposed velocity is 1.75 m/s, which combined with the density of the impact material ensures the desired impact energy of 40 J, equal to the experimental tests done by Peres et al. [31], and are used to compare with the numerical results obtained in this work.

To perform the ISSF analysis it is better to have a radial discretization at the adherent/adhesive interface corner, so the discretization in that region was as shown in Figure 5b. That region was discretized in the same manner, regardless of the L_O , with the number of nodes shown in Figure 5b, meaning that it had a total of 1646 nodes. The rest of the joint has small differences in the discretization depending on L_O , but it is similar for all L_O . As such, the complete joint had 6776, 6992 and 7448 nodes in the L_O of 12.5, 25, and 50 mm cases, respectively. The simulations were all performed assuming plane strain conditions.

3.2 Determination of the Critical ISSF

Each interface corner has different singularity exponents, depending on the angle and the materials. In this case, using Equation 34, it was observed that this corner has three singularity exponents, i.e. exponents lower than

Figure 5. (a) Scheme of the SLJ, measurements in mm (not to scale), (b) Radial discretization near the material interface corner, (c) and number of nodes in the interface corner region

one, $\lambda_1 = 0.6072$, $\lambda_2 = 0.7416$ and $\lambda_3 = 0.9879$. Of those, λ_2 is not considered because it is an anti-plane exponent, which is not relevant in this analysis since it is 2D plane-strain analysis. Therefore, in further texts and figures $\lambda_2 = 0.9879$, the previous λ_3 .

Considering that there are two exponents, to determine the ISSF using Equation 39 it is necessary to use the stresses at two different angles. For that purpose the angles used were: $\alpha_1 = \pi/4$ rad and $\alpha_2 = -3\pi/4$ rad, the same angles used in a previous study of this type of joint under static loading [29]. To obtain the actual ISSF at the corner it is necessary to extrapolate from the values near the corner. This was done using the ISSF values between $r = 0.01$ mm and $r = 0.1$ mm, with an example of this process being shown in Figure 6. In a dynamic simulation this process is repeated for every time step where the displacements and stresses are saved, which in this work was at each 1×10^{-6} s of simulation time. Figure 7 shows how the force and the ISSF evolve throughout the simulation. There, it is possible to observe that the differences between the FEM and the RPIM are small, thus

Figure 6. Extrapolation of the first ISSF to the corner for the joint with $L_0 = 25$ mm (FEM)

Table 1. Critical ISSF determined with the different overlap lengths

L_O (mm)	H_{1c} FEM (Mpa mm ^{1-λ₁})	H_{1c} RPIM (Mpa mm ^{1-λ₁})
12.5	268.29	270.83
25	307.23	309.90
50	357.35	359.68

validating the latter. The dots in Figure 7 represent the point where the experimentally determined failure force was reached in the simulation. It is also important to notice that the curves in Figure 7 have been smoothed with a moving average consisting of the 40 closest points. The H_1 for all L_O evolves similarly until a displacement of around 0.35 mm where the H_1 of joints with longer L_O starts to increase more rapidly.

To obtain the critical ISSF a combination of the experimental data from reference [31] and the data from Figure 7 is used. Essentially, the smoothed force is checked at every time step and compared to the experimentally determined strength, when both are equal the smoothed H_1 is determined to be the critical ISSF (H_{1c}), which are the values represented by the dots in Figure 7. The H_{1c} values determined using this process are shown in Table 1. Comparing both numerical methods the differences between the FEM and the RPIM are very small and the H_{1c} are essentially the same for both numerical methods. In Table 1 is also possible to observe that joints with longer L_O have higher estimated H_{1c} , indicating that joints with longer L_O are able to withstand larger stress singularities. This type of increase in H_{1c} with increases in L_O was also observed for static loading conditions by references [14, 32].

Figure 8 shows the radial stress components around the adhesive/adherent interface corner. The comparison between the analytical stress values from the formulas presented in Section 2.3 and both numerical methods shows very small differences, which can be attributed to the influence of non-singular exponents. It is also possible to observe that both numerical methods also have similar stress values. Finally, as it was expected due to the distance from the corner being only 0.0029 mm, the first singularity exponent plays a larger role in the stress when compared to the second singularity exponent.

Figure 7. Smoothed (a) force (b) and ISSF progression over displacement

Figure 8. Stress in angular coordinates at the adhesive corner in the $L_O = 50$ mm joint, at the critical ISSF, at $r = 0.0029$ mm

3.3 Strength Prediction

The estimated H_{1c} presented in Table 1 were used to predict the strength of SLJ with L_O different from the one used to estimate the H_{1c} . These strength predictions are shown in Figure 9. As in the case of the radial stress and the estimated H_{1c} values, the strength predictions using the FEM and the RPIM are very similar.

One of the main takeaways from Figure 9 is that the real strength increase by increasing L_O is higher than the predicted strength increase using the ISSF criterion. This results in underpredictions or overpredictions depending on the L_O used to estimate the H_{1c} , this behaviour was also seen in static loading by Ramalho et al. [29]. The

Figure 9. Strength prediction, experimental data from reference [31]

largest strength underprediction occurred when using the H_{1c} estimated with the joint with $L_O = 12.5$ mm to predict the strength of the joint with $L_O = 50$ mm. In that case the predicted strength was around 20% lower than the real strength. On the opposite end, the largest strength overprediction occurred when using the H_{1c} estimated with the joint with $L_O = 50$ mm to predict the strength of the joint with $L_O = 12.5$ mm. In that case the predicted strength was around 34% higher than the real strength. The smallest difference between predicted strength and real strength occurred when using the H_{1c} estimated with the joint with $L_O = 12.5$ mm to predict the strength of the joint with $L_O = 25$ mm. With that combination the predicted strength was only around 14% lower than the experimental strength.

4 Conclusions

This work aims at comparing the FEM and the RPIM applied to the stress singularity analysis of an adhesive SLJ under impact. It was observed that the SLJ studied in this work has three singularity exponents, $\lambda_1 = 0.6072$, $\lambda_2 = 0.7416$ and $\lambda_3 = 0.9879$, and of those λ_2 is anti-plane thus not relevant for the 2D plane strain analysis performed in this work. The comparison between the FEM and the RPIM shows no significant differences between the two methods in terms of radial stress around the adhesive/adherent interface corner, estimated H_{1c} or predicted joint strength. A comparison with analytical stress values also validated this approach of determining the ISSF and the numerical methods. Regarding the H_{1c} determined with the combination of experimental tests and numerical simulations, it seems that joints with longer L_O are able to withstand larger stress singularities, which was observed in previous works for static loading conditions [14, 32]. This results in joint strength underpredictions when using a H_{1c} determined with a shorter L_O to predict the strength of joints with longer L_O , and strength overpredictions in the opposite case.

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2.7 Graph Visualization and Centrality Analysis of Discrete Variables Correlation from Whole-Body Center of Mass Movement During Standard MVJ

Authors:

Carlos Rodrigues
Miguel Correia
João Abrantes
Marco Rodrigues
Jurandir Nadal

Graph Visualization and Centrality Analysis of Discrete Variables Correlation from Whole-Body Center of Mass Movement During Standard MVJ

Carlos M.B. Rodrigues^{1,2}, Miguel V. Correia^{1,2}, João M.C.S Abrantes³, Marco A.B. Rodrigues⁴, Jurandir Nadal⁵

¹Doctoral Program in Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto
Rua Dr. Roberto Frias, s/n, 4200-465, Porto, Portugal
c.rodrigues@fe.up.pt, mcorreia@fe.up.pt

²Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science, University of Porto
Rua Dr. Roberto Frias, s/n, 4200-465, Porto, Portugal
carlos.b.rodrigues@inesctec.pt, miguel.velhote.correia@inesctec.pt

³Lusófona University, Lisbon
Campo Grande, 376, 1749-024, Lisboa, Portugal
joao.mcs.abrantes@ulusofona.pt

⁴Department of Electronic and Systems, Federal University of Pernambuco
Av. Prof. Moraes Rego, 1235 - Cidade Universitária, 50670-901, Recife - PE, Brazil
marco.rodrigues@ufpe.br

⁵Biomedical Engineering Program, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro
Av. Horácio Macedo, 2030, 21941-914, Rio de Janeiro - RJ, Brazil
jn@peb.ufrj.br

Abstract. Lower limb force development is determinant for human walking ability with impact on our autonomy, self-esteem and health preservation. On natural human movement, the neuromuscular system presents a central role at the control of the muscles acting the skeletal system, along with the proprioceptive system to ensure kinesthesia. Although isolated isometric, concentric and eccentric forms of muscle action have gathered larger research attention, natural form of muscle function involves the use of muscle stretch-shortening cycle (SSC) with preactivated muscle stretch preceding muscle contraction for efficient muscle action at submaximal activities such as gait and powerful actions at maximal activities such as running and jumping. Thus, despite muscle SSC can be observed at gait and running, its higher expression and accessibility is performed on standard maximum vertical jump (MVJ) using whole-body (WB) weight for long countermovement (CM) on countermovement jump (CMJ) and short CM on drop jump (DJ) from 40 cm step for comparison with squat jump (SJ) and no CM, assessing long and short lower limb muscle SSC contribution in relation to no SSC condition for lower limb force development to propel WB center of mass (COM). Data processing pipeline focused on a set of 53 dynamic and kinematic variables from WB movement on a sample of 198 trials with the selection of the highest MVJ from 3 CMJ, DJ and SJ repetitions performed by a group of 6 untrained (U) and 16 trained (T) subjects. These variables, grouped into three communities of (i) time-force-impulse ($t-F-I$), (ii) force-velocity-power ($F-v-P$), and (iii) force-displacement-work ($F-z-W$) were subjected to bivariate correlation for each sample of U, T and MVJ type. Statistically significant correlations were detected at 5% significance level and graph analysis was performed with degree of centrality and graph density assessment. Whereas the global subgraphs densities presented similar profiles for U and T associated to the variable structure at each MVJ type, individual subgraphs densities presented clear differences at CMJ, DJ, and SJ for U and T. Thus, while F , $t-F$, I , $t-F-I$, $v-P$ and $F-W$ presented similar comparisons of CMJ, DJ and SJ graph densities at U and T, the remaining variable combinations presented distinct graph densities at U and T for CMJ, DJ, SJ.

Keywords: graph visualization, correlation centrality, density, whole-body center of mass, discrete variables.

1 Introduction

Human motion and posture are critically dependent on muscle action under central nervous system (CNS) control and musculoskeletal system actuation according to Winter [1]. Despite isolated isometric, eccentric and concentric muscle action received larger research attention, muscle stretch-shortening cycle (SSC) is a common element at lower limbs on gait, running and jumping as an anticipating stretch mechanism at onset support to increase force production during shortening at later stance, Komi and Zatsiorsky [2,3].

Although lower limbs muscle SSC can be observed on walking, running, and jumping [2], its higher expression and accessibility under controlled experimental conditions is more accurately performed *in vivo* and non-invasively on standard maximum vertical jump with long countermovement (CM) and SSC at countermovement jump (CMJ), and short CM at drop jump (DJ) for comparison with squat jump (SJ) without CM and SSC, Huijing and Sale [4,5]. Thus, the standard maximum vertical jump (MVJ) has been increasingly applied since Asmussen, Bosco and Bobbert et al. [6-9] for comparison of SJ, CMJ and DJ. Plyometrics, with muscle lengthening on eccentric action preceding concentric contraction and muscular force increase presents as an established method to train and assess lower limb muscular strength as the ability to exert maximal force on external body with reversible action a common element at many sport movements [3].

Nature of assessed standard MVJ has been defined according to [7] with SJ associated to explosive force depending on higher rate of fast twitch (FT) muscle fibers determining positive concentric work, whereas CMJ is associated to explosive force with nervous recruitment as an expression of the FT rate and reuse of elastic energy and intra, and intermuscular coordination. As regards to DJ main research features are related to muscle stiffness resulting from neuromuscular ability of very high force levels development on short CM, viscoelastic properties of extensor muscles, myotatic stretch reflex and the inhibitory proprioceptors of the Golgi tendon organs.

Dominant approach at different MVJ corresponds to the comparison of kinematic and dynamic variables [9-13], with reduced number of studies on the association of these variables at nonparametric level, despite the interest of these relations assessment for efficiency and performance [3]. Nevertheless, biomechanical analysis of standard MVJ studies led to the discovery of a large number of time dependent and highly correlated kinematic and dynamic parameters with an open issue on statistically significant relations between these parameters at different MVJ and subjects condition [14,15], along with limitation of classical statistical techniques to address uneven distributions corresponding to a large number of relations concentrated at reduced nodes and large number of nodes with reduced number of relations similarly to what has been detected in other phenomena [16]. Also, whereas elite male performers have received larger research attention, lower skill untrained subjects received lower research attention [17], with an open issue on trained and untrained comparison, and the central variables with higher node density and most frequent relations pointing for biomechanical variables with potential training interest.

Parametric relations are described as the known relations from classical mechanics [3]. Nevertheless, the relations known as nonparametric present as an open issue with innumerable postulated associations between force and velocity, displacement, and time for force development on MVJ. For this reason, the main purpose of this study is to assess nonparametric relations between kinematic and dynamic variables for comparison of different MVJ at trained and untrained groups as well as detection of central variables with higher correlation densities and preferential variable coupling based on graph tools.

2 Materials and Methods

Assessed data corresponds to selected best trials on standard MVJ of SJ, CMJ and DJ based on higher flight time method of two sample groups of trained and untrained subjects. Trained sample is composed by a group of sixteen athletes of the Portuguese male volleyball team, ages (21.4 ± 3.1) years, (85.2 ± 5.8) kg mass and (1.93 ± 0.04) m height. Untrained sample is composed by a group of six voluntary students of sports and physical education degree, ages (21.5 ± 1.4) years, (76.7 ± 9.3) kg mass and (1.79 ± 0.06) m height. The study was conducted according to the guidelines of the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki of 1975, as revised in 2000 and 2008, with written informed consent obtained from the subjects participating in the study.

Each subject performed 3 SJ, 3 CMJ and 3 DJ with a total of one hundred and ninety-eight tests and the selection of each subject best SJ, CMJ and DJ based on higher flight time. Tests were performed according to corresponding protocols as presented at Figure 1, on SJ starting from squat rest position with knees bending at 90° (t_1) and upward movement without countermovement (t_2, t_3), and CMJ starting from orthostatic position (t_1), initiating downward movement, and reversing descending movement at 90° knee flexion (t_2) after long countermovement with ascending movement (t_3). Regarding DJ trials, those were performed with subject depth jump from standing position on a 40 cm step, entering downward movement (t_1) with short countermovement immediate reverse (t_2) from descending to fast ascending movement (t_3). On SJ, CMJ and DJ trials, subjects were instructed to start with upright torso, maintain the hands at the hip during the tests to avoid its influence on long and short countermovement assessment in relation to no countermovement.

Figure 1. Human torso and lower limbs stick-figure at t_1 , t_2 and t_3 time sequence on SJ, CMJ and DJ, with whole-body (WB) center of mass (CoM) trajectory during impulse phase.

During MVJ trials ground reaction force was acquired with AMTI BP2416-4000CE force plate at 1000 Hz coupled to Mini Amp MAS-6, using Simi Motion 3D (Simi Reality Motion Systems GmbH, Germany). Vertical ground reaction force (GRF_z) was selected according to the interest study on MVJ assessment. Flight time (t_f) was determined from the time interval with null GRF_z corresponding to the flight phase and best SJ, CMJ and DJ trials were selected for each subject according to highest MVJ height $h = 1/8 g t_f^2$. Vertical resultant force was computed $RF_z = GRF_z - mg$ with m the subject mass and $g = 9.81 m/s^2$ the local gravity acceleration. Vertical acceleration of whole-body (WB) center of mass (CoM) was computed $a_z = RF_z/m$ as well as the corresponding

2.7 Graph Visualization and Centrality Analysis of Discrete Variables Correlation from Whole-Body Center of Mass Movement During Stand

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vertical velocity from initial vertical velocity v_{0z} and a_z time integration $v_z = v_{0z} + \int a_z dt$ during impulse phase. Whole-body CoM vertical displacement was also computed from its vertical velocity time integration $\Delta z = \int v_z dt$ during impulse phase. Developed mechanical power during vertical displacement of whole-body CoM was computed from its vertical velocity and vertical resultant force $P = RF_z \cdot v_z$ and corresponding mechanical work from its vertical displacement and vertical resultant force $W = RF_z \cdot \Delta z$.

Figure 2 presents typical time profiles of WB CoM vertical acceleration a_z , velocity v_z , displacement Δz , and developed power P and mechanical work W during vertical movement of tested subject on SJ, CMJ and DJ performed experimental trials, with eccentric, concentric and take-off phases delimited with vertical dashed lines.

Figure 2. Time profiles of whole-body center of mass vertical acceleration a_z , velocity v_z , displacement Δz , developed power P and mechanical work W during vertical movement of tested subject on SJ, CMJ and DJ experimental trials.

According to delimited eccentric, concentric and take-off phases, discrete values of kinematic and dynamic signal with research interest were selected for specific time moments and periods. Thus, selected variables from vertical resultant force (RFz) were considered for analysis, corresponding to the minimum ($RFz\ min\ imp$), maximum ($RFz\ max\ imp$), mean ($RFz\ mean\ imp$) during impulse phase, mean on descending ($RFz\ mean\ down$), ascending ($RFz\ mean\ up$) and transition from descending to ascending ($RFz\ start\ up$) phases. Complementary vertical resultant force on take-off ($RFz\ take-off$) and maximum vertical resultant force on reception phase ($RFz\ max\ land$) were considered. Each of the previous selected variables presents a specific characteristic supporting its potential for performance prediction on different MVJ.

Thus, lower $RFz\ min\ imp$ and $RFz\ mean\ down$ can be associated to a more pronounced countermovement with increase descending velocity responsible for higher $RFz\ max\ imp$, $RFz\ mean\ up$ and $RFz\ mean\ imp$ associated to larger ascending and take-off velocity [10]. On the other hand, lower $RFz\ min\ imp$ and $RFz\ mean\ down$ associated to a more pronounced countermovement and larger descending velocity point to the need for higher intensity of vertical resultant force towards reversal of movement direction from downward to upward movement. Additionally, $RFz\ start\ up$ force level corresponding to the start of upward impulse also presents a high potential predictor of performance since it constitutes the starting force level at the force time integration to obtain vertical impulse determining the take-off velocity. The variable $RFz\ take-off$ corresponding to the level of vertical ground reaction force at the time of *take-off* may be associated with the position of the foot at this moment, with maximum level $RFz\ max\ land$ may be related to greater flight height and lower limb stiffness at reception and absorption of impact energy.

The time intervals $\Delta t\ imp$ for the impulse phase, $\Delta t\ down$ for downward phase and $\Delta t\ up$ for the upward phase as well as their relative counterpart $\Delta t\ down / \Delta t\ imp$, $\Delta t\ up / \Delta t\ imp$ and $\Delta t\ up / \Delta t\ down$ were also included for detection of nonparametric relations with kinematic and dynamic variables on different MVJ due to the importance of time for force development [3] and the contribution of the downward and upward time interval on absolute and relative terms at each MVJ type. In this regard, the time intervals during impulse for minimum and maximum vertical resultant force $\Delta t\ RFz\ min\ imp$ and $\Delta t\ RFz\ max\ imp$ as well as their relative values $\Delta t\ RFz\ min\ imp / \Delta t\ imp$ and $\Delta t\ RFz\ max\ imp / \Delta t\ imp$ were also included for relation detection as measures of the necessary time intervals for force development. Additionally, flight time $\Delta t\ imp$ was included as a central variable for relation detection with kinematic and dynamic MVJ variables, along with the time interval on reception for maximum vertical resultant force $\Delta t\ RFz\ max\ land$ as an indicative measure of impact.

The relations of the net effect of force development over time was assessed through the inclusion of the impulse of resultant vertical force variable $I(RFz)\ imp$, impulse on descending $I(RFz)\ imp\ down$ and ascending phases $I(RFz)\ imp\ up$, with the effect of the impulse on whole-body CoM assessed by imposed vertical velocity to its minimum $vz\ min\ imp$, maximum $vz\ max\ imp$, mean during impulse $vz\ mean\ imp$, descending $vz\ mean\ down$ and ascending $vz\ mean\ up$ subphases, transition from downward to upward movement $vz\ start\ up$ and take-off $vz\ take-off$. The effect of developed velocity was assessed through vertical CoM displacement on downward phase $\Delta z\ down$, upward phase $\Delta z\ up$, take-off displacement $\Delta z\ toff$ and maximum vertical displacement $\Delta z\ max$ in relation to MVJ starting position, as well as maximum vertical jump height by the flight time $h(flight)$, the impulse method $h(imp)$ and partial displacement method $h(\Delta z)$.

Combined effect of applied vertical resultant force and developed vertical velocity was assessed through mechanical power variables developed during CoM vertical movement, specifically the minimum $P\ min\ imp$, maximum $P\ max\ imp$, mean during impulse $P\ mean\ imp$, descending $P\ mean\ down$ and ascending $P\ mean\ up$ subphases, the transition from downward to upward movement $P\ start\ up$ and take-off $P\ take-off$, as well as the landing maximum $P\ max\ land$ and minimum $P\ min\ land$ developed power. The net mechanical energy transfer from applied vertical resultant force during CoM vertical displacement was assessed by the mechanical work performed during impulse $W\ imp$, downward $W\ imp\ down$ and upward $W\ imp\ up$ subphases, as well as the maximum $W\ max\ imp$ during impulse and $W\ max\ land$ reception.

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Selected variables were grouped on three complementary communities of (i) force-time-impulse, (ii) force-velocity-power, and (iii) force-displacement-work during WB CoM vertical displacement at different MVJ, according to their original physical quantity. Kinematic and dynamic variables were bivariate correlated at untrained and trained groups for each MVJ type, SJ, CMJ, DJ, and variable community (i, ii and iii). Statistically significant correlations were detected at 5% significance with node centrality and preferential attachment assessed through graph density.

Figure 3 presents fifty-three different grouped variables extracted from corresponding physical quantity, namely vertical resultant force RFz , time intervals during impulse phase Δt_1 , time intervals from peak RFz (Δt_2), selected absolute time intervals from Δt_1 and Δt_2 (Δt_{12}), vertical impulse $I(RFz)$, WB CoM vertical velocity vz , developed mechanical power P during CoM vertical movement, CoM vertical displacement Δz and mechanical work W done during WB CoM vertical movement.

RFz (8 VARS)	Δt_1 (6 VARS)	Δt_2 (6 VARS)
RFz min imp (N)	Δt down (s)	Δt (RFz min imp) (s)
RFz max imp (N)	Δt up (s)	Δt (RFz max imp) (s)
RFz mean imp (N)	Δt imp (s)	Δt (flight) (s)
RFz mean down (N)	Δt down / Δt imp	Δt (RFz max land) (s)
RFz mean up (N)	Δt up / Δt imp	Δt (RFz min imp) / Δt imp
RFz start up (N)	Δt down / Δt up	Δt (RFz max imp) / Δt imp
RFz take-off (N)		
RFz max land (N)		

Δt_{12} (7 VARS)	$I(RFz)$ (3 VARS)	vz (7 VARS)
Δt down (s)	$I(RFz)$ imp (N*s)	vz min imp (m/s)
Δt up (s)	$I(RFz)$ imp down (N*s)	vz max imp (m/s)
Δt imp (s)	$I(RFz)$ imp up (N*s)	vz mean imp (m/s)
Δt (RFz min imp) (s)		vz mean down (m/s)
Δt (RFz max imp) (s)		vz mean up (m/s)
Δt (flight) (s)		vz start up (m/s)
Δt (RFz max land) (s)		vz take-off (m/s)

P (9 VARS)	Δz (7 VARS)	W (5 VARS)
P min imp (W)	Δz down (m)	W imp (J)
P max imp (W)	Δz up (m)	W imp down (J)
P mean imp (W)	Δz toff (m)	W imp up (J)
P mean down (W)	Δz max (m)	W max imp (J)
P mean up (W)	h (flight) (m)	W max landing (J)
P start up (W)	h (imp) (m)	
P take-off (W)	h (Δz) (m)	
P max landing (W)		
P min landing (W)		

Figure 3. Dynamic and kinematic variables extracted from vertical resultant force (RFz), time impulse subphases (Δt_1), time of peak force values (Δt_2), time of impulse subphases and peak forces (Δt_{12}), impulse of the vertical resultant force ($I(RFz)$), WB COM vertical velocity (vz), mechanical power (P), WB COM vertical displacement (Δz) and mechanical work (W).

Bivariate correlations were performed on variables at intra and inter physical quantities, with graph density determined by the ratio of statistically significant correlations at 5% significance to the maximum number of possible correlations. The uneven degree of correlations was assessed through the Fisher 3rd order normalized coefficient of asymmetry of the node's distribution and correlations.

3 Results

Illustrative graphs of statistically significant time correlations at 5% significance are presented in Figure 4 for untrained and trained trial groups at SJ, CMJ and DJ, with the graphs of remaining physical quantities detailed on Annex [18].

3.1 Time correlations

Time impulse phase and subphases. Untrained test group (G1) and trained control group (G2) presented different graph structures of statistically significant correlations at 5% significance for Δt_1 time impulse phase and subphases, Figure 4. Thus, whereas Δt_{down} and Δt_{up} are associated with Δt_{imp} at SJ, CMJ and DJ on G1, at G2 and SJ only Δt_{up} and Δt_{imp} are associated, with Δt_{down} , Δt_{up} and Δt_{imp} associated at CMJ and DJ. Also, the corresponding ratios of Δt_{down} , Δt_{up} and Δt_{imp} associated at SJ, CMJ and DJ on G1 are only associated at CMJ and DJ on G2. Finally, whereas at G1 Δt_{down} is associated with relative time span on SJ, at G2 this association occurs at DJ, with CMJ association of Δt_{imp} and Δt_{down} with corresponding ratios of Δt_{down} , Δt_{up} and Δt_{imp} . G1 presented on SJ higher density of statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$), with G2 presenting higher densities on CMJ and DJ, Table 1. Additionally, higher centrality was registered for G1 at Δt_{down} on SJ due to the tendency for countermovement at untrained subjects, with higher centrality on G2 detected at Δt_{imp} on CMJ and Δt_{down} on CMJ and DJ, Figure 4 and Annex [18] – 3.1.1.

Figure 4. Graphs of time impulse phase and subphases (Δt_1) statistically significant correlations at 5% significance for (a) G1 – untrained test group; (b) G2 – trained control group.

Negative asymmetry was detected for the time impulse phase and subphases Δt_1 at G1 on SJ, CMJ and DJ, as well as at G2 on CMJ pointing to a larger number of nodes with higher correlations, whereas SJ and DJ presented at G2 positive asymmetry pointing to a larger number of nodes with the lower number of statistically significant correlations, Table 2.

Time of peak force values. Time of peak force values Δt_2 presented at untrained test group G1 higher densities of statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) at SJ than DJ both higher than CMJ, with the opposite at the trained control group (G2) higher correlation densities at CMJ than DJ, both higher than SJ, Table 2. Thus, whereas SJ presented at G1 higher Δt_2 correlation density than G2, CMJ and DJ presented at G2 higher Δt_2 correlation densities than G1, pointing this as a distinguishing feature between untrained test group and trained control group.

G1 and G2 presented at Δt_2 different graph structures of statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) with higher centrality of $\Delta t(RFz \text{ max imp})$, $\Delta t(RFz \text{ max imp}) / \Delta t \text{ imp}$ and $\Delta t(RFz \text{ max land})$ at SJ on G1, whereas G2 presented higher centrality at $\Delta t(RFz \text{ min imp})$, $\Delta t(RFz \text{ min imp}) / \Delta t \text{ imp}$ for CMJ, DJ and $\Delta t(RFz \text{ max imp})$, $\Delta t(\text{flight})$ at CMJ as well as $\Delta t(RFz \text{ max land})$ on DJ, Annex [18] – 3.1.2. SJ presented at G1 symmetric distribution of Δt_2 correlations per node, with CMJ at G1 and SJ at G2 positive asymmetries and larger number of nodes without significant correlations, whereas DJ at G1 and CMJ, DJ at G2 presented negative asymmetries and larger number of nodes with higher correlations, Tables 2.

Time of impulse subphases and peak forces. Jointly considered time of impulse subphases and peak force values (Δt_{12}) presented at G1 untrained test group higher densities of statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) at SJ than CMJ both higher than DJ, with G2 trained control group higher correlation densities at CMJ than DJ both higher than SJ, Table 1. Therefore, Δt_{12} presents a common tendency to Δt_1 and Δt_2 with SJ higher correlation density at G1 than G2, whereas CMJ and DJ presented at G2 higher Δt_{12} correlation densities than G1, corresponding to higher association level of time variables at G1 on SJ and at G2 on CMJ and DJ. Untrained test group and trained control group presented also different graph structures of Δt_{12} significative correlations, [18] – 3.1.3, with G1 higher centrality at $\Delta t \text{ imp}$ on SJ and $\Delta t \text{ RFz max imp}$ on SJ and CMJ, whereas G2 higher centrality was detected at $\Delta t \text{ RFz max imp}$ on CMJ and $\Delta t \text{ RFz min imp}$ on DJ. Jointly considered the time variables Δt_{12} presented dominant positive symmetries at G1 and G2 corresponding to a higher number of nodes with reduced correlations and the exception on CMJ at G2 with larger number of nodes with higher significant correlations

Table 1. Densities of statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$).

Density	G1 (Test – Untrained group)			G2 (Control – Trained group)		
	SJ	CMJ	DJ	SJ	CMJ	DJ
Δt_1	0.53	0.33	0.33	0.07	0.80	0.60
Δt_2	0.23	0.08	0.15	0.08	0.38	0.31
Δt_{12}	0.25	0.17	0.00	0.17	0.42	0.25
RFz	0.14	0.14	0.25	0.32	0.29	0.36
$RFz - \Delta t_1$	0.04	0.00	0.17	0.25	0.21	0.71
$RFz - \Delta t_2$	0.03	0.06	0.09	0.13	0.16	0.25
$I - I$	0.33	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.33	1.00
$\Delta t_{12} - I$	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.19	0.14
$RFz - I$	0.26	0.19	0.30	0.41	0.37	0.22
$\Delta t_{12} - RFz - I$	0.12	0.10	0.17	0.23	0.27	0.33
vz	0.14	0.19	0.33	0.43	0.19	0.48
$vz - RFz$	0.14	0.09	0.07	0.04	0.25	0.36
$P - P$	0.14	0.17	0.08	0.25	0.22	0.36
$RFz - P$	0.21	0.18	0.18	0.25	0.29	0.42
$vz - P$	0.13	0.03	0.16	0.25	0.25	0.38
$RFz - vz - P$	0.16	0.12	0.16	0.23	0.26	0.38
Δz	0.33	0.10	0.48	0.33	0.38	0.48
$\Delta z - RFz$	0.07	0.00	0.04	0.13	0.29	0.36
$W - W$	0.40	0.50	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.40
$RFz - W$	0.20	0.25	0.08	0.18	0.33	0.10
$\Delta z - W$	0.40	0.20	0.31	0.40	0.40	0.46
$RFz - \Delta z - W$	0.26	0.15	0.19	0.22	0.33	0.34

Table 2. Asymmetries of the node distributions and statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$).

Asymmetry	G1 (Test – Untrained group)			G2 (Control – Trained group)		
	SJ	CMJ	DJ	SJ	CMJ	DJ
Δt_1	-0.666	-0.968	-0.968	0.968	-1.369	1.369
Δt_2	0.000	0.968	-0.968	0.968	-0.666	-0.857
Δt_{12}	0.353	1.115	-	1.115	-0.235	1.520
RFz	0.000	0.000	-0.267	-1.675	0.000	-0.644
$RFz - \Delta t_1$	1.923	-	0.661	0.466	0.856	0.032
$RFz - \Delta t_2$	2.055	0.812	2.211	1.733	1.479	2.800
$I - I$	-1.732	-1.732	-	-1.732	-1.732	-
$\Delta t_{12} - I$	-	-	1.658	1.658	0.484	1.959
$RFz - I$	0.499	0.868	0.871	0.197	0.984	0.661
$\Delta t_{12} - RFz - I$	-0.041	-0.230	-0.278	-0.594	-0.779	-0.335
vz	-2.646	-0.353	-0.651	-1.000	-0.353	-1.177
$vz - RFz$	0.004	1.214	1.074	2.273	-0.055	0.044
$P - P$	0.508	0.698	0.606	0.000	0.088	-0.617
$RFz - P$	0.503	0.379	0.503	-0.695	-0.060	-0.524
$vz - P$	0.507	1.278	0.268	0.124	0.268	-0.212
$RFz - vz - P$	-0.099	-0.036	0.311	-1.258	-0.004	-0.554
Δz	-0.321	-0.374	-1.230	-1.569	-0.029	0.366
$\Delta z - RFz$	2.805	-	1.672	0.849	-0.447	0.952
$W - W$	-0.609	-1.361	-0.609	-0.609	-0.609	-0.405
$RFz - W$	0.221	0.481	2.327	1.593	-0.124	2.597
$\Delta z - W$	-0.491	0.392	0.745	0.143	-0.495	-0.446
$RFz - \Delta z - W$	0.234	0.320	-0.128	-0.725	-0.337	-0.866

3.2 Vertical resultant force

Vertical resultant force (RFz) variables presented similar relation of bivariate graph densities on untrained test group (G1) and trained control group (G2) with higher values at DJ and similar lower values at SJ, CMJ, Table 1. Higher densities of RFz at G2 than G1 on SJ, CMJ and DJ points for stronger association of vertical resultant force variables at trained control group than untrained test group at long, short and no countermovement. Higher centrality is associated to a larger number of RFz correlations at SJ and DJ on G2, whereas on G1 larger number of RFz correlations is registered at DJ, Annex [18] – 3.2. Thus, whereas higher RFz centrality is associated on SJ at G1 with RFz start up and RFz mean up, at G2 it is associated with RFz min imp, RFz mean down, RFz start up and RFz take-off. The same occurs at DJ with higher centrality associated on G1 with RFz mean down, RFz mean up, RFz mean imp and RFz max imp, whereas at G2 it is associated to RFz mean down, RFz mean up, RFz mean imp, RFz max imp and RFz start up. At CMJ higher centrality is associated on G1 with RFz min imp, RFz max imp and RFz start up, whereas G2 higher centrality is associated to RFz max imp and RFz mean imp. Whereas the distribution of the statistically significant correlations per node of the RFz variables presented at SJ on G1 and CMJ on G1 and G2 symmetric distributions, SJ presented at G2 and DJ on G1 and G2 negative asymmetries with a larger number of nodes with higher number of correlations, Table 2.

Vertical resultant force and time impulse subphases. The association of variables from vertical resultant forces RFz and time impulse subphases Δt_1 presented at G1 and G2 groups higher densities of statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) for DJ than SJ and CMJ, as well as higher densities at G2 trained control group than G1 untrained test group, Table 1. Thus, G1 presents very high sparsity with larger number of RFz and Δt_1 variables with no statistically significant correlations and reduced number of variables with $p < 0.05$ linear correlations. As regards to G2, SJ and CMJ presented a larger number of RFz and Δt_1 variables without statistically significant correlations, whereas DJ presents a higher number of variables with linear correlations $p < 0.05$ and Δt up, Δt imp concentrating larger centrality, [18] – 3.2.1. The association of the vertical resultant force RFz and time phases Δt_1 presented dominant positive asymmetric distributions and larger number of nodes with reduced correlations and the exception at DJ on G2 with near symmetric distribution and larger number of nodes with higher correlations.

Vertical resultant force and time of peak force values. Vertical resultant force RFz and time of peak force Δt_2 joint variables presented on G1 untrained test and G2 trained control group higher density at DJ than CMJ both higher than SJ, with higher densities at G2 than G1 on SJ, CMJ and DJ, Table 2. Thus, the untrained test group presented larger sparsity of RFz and Δt_2 variables correlation with $\Delta t RFz max imp$ higher centrality at DJ, whereas the trained control group presented higher centrality, with $\Delta t RFz min imp$ concentrating at DJ higher significant correlations ($p < 0.05$), Annex [18] – 3.2.2. Regarding also the association of the vertical resultant force RFz and the time intervals Δt_2 variables there is a dominant positive asymmetry at SJ, CMJ and DJ on G1 and G2 with a larger number of nodes presenting a reduced number of statistically significant correlations, Table 2.

3.3 Impulse of vertical resultant force

Selected variables from the impulse I of the vertical resultant force presented similar densities of statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) at G1 untrained test and G2 control group with higher values at DJ than SJ and CMJ, Table 1. Thus, whereas DJ presented significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) between $I(RFz) imp$, $I(RFz) imp down$ and $I(RFz) imp up$ at the impulse phase and its subphases, SJ and CMJ presented significant correlations restricted to $I(RFz) imp up$ and $I(RFz) imp$ with the correlation of the upward subphase and the impulse phase at SJ, CMJ and DJ, Annex [18] – 3.3. Separately, the correlations between the impulse variables I presented a larger number of nodes with higher correlations at G1, G2 and negative asymmetries for SJ and CMJ, Table 2.

Impulse and time of impulse subphases and peak forces. The impulse I and the time of impulse subphases and peak force variables Δt_{12} presented different behavior at untrained group G1 and trained group G2, without statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) at SJ, CMJ and reduced density at DJ on G1, and higher densities at CMJ than DJ and SJ on G2, Table 1, as well as higher centrality of $\Delta t(RFz max imp)$ at DJ on G1 and $\Delta t flight$ at SJ, CMJ and DJ on G2, Annex [18] – 3.3.1. The distributions from the association of the impulse I and time variables Δt_{12} thus presented positive asymmetries with a larger number of nodes with reduced correlations.

Impulse and vertical resultant forces. The Impulse I and vertical resultant force RFz variable correlations present opposite relation at G1 untrained group and G2 trained group, with SJ and CMJ higher densities of statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) than DJ on G2 and higher correlation densities at DJ than SJ and CMJ on G1, Table 1. In terms of centrality G1 test group presents larger number of significant correlations for $I(RFz) imp$ and $I(RFz) imp down$ at DJ, whereas G2 control group presents larger number of significant correlations for $I(RFz) imp$ and $I(RFz) imp up$ on SJ and CMJ as well as for $I(RFz) imp down$ on SJ, [18] – 3.3.2, with uneven distributions of significant correlations at SJ, CMJ, DJ on G1 and CMJ, DJ on G2 corresponding to a higher number of variables without statistically significant correlations, and lower skewness distribution at SJ on G2.

Impulse, time and vertical resultant force. Impulse, time and vertical resultant force variable correlations presented higher densities at G2 trained group than G1 untrained group, with similar density relations and higher values at DJ than CMJ and SJ on G1 and G2, Table 1. Untrained test group G1 and trained control group G2 presented however different behavior of higher centrality on impulse, time and vertical resultant force variable correlation. Thus, whereas SJ presents at G1 higher centrality for $RFz max imp$ and $\Delta t imp$ as determinants of the impulsion and $RFz max land$ as a result of the impulsion at the landing phase, G2 presents on SJ higher centrality for $RFz mean imp$ and $RFz mean up$ corresponding to determinants of the impulsion. Similarly, CMJ presented at G1 lower centrality levels at larger number of impulse, time and vertical resultant force variables with G2 higher centrality on CMJ at larger number of variables. Also, whereas DJ concentrates at G1 higher centrality at a reduced number of impulse, time and vertical resultant force variables, G2 presents higher centrality at larger number of variables, particularly at $\Delta t up$ and $\Delta t RFz max imp$, Annex [18] – 3.3.3.

3.4 Vertical velocity

WB CoM vertical velocity presented different behaviors at G1 untrained and G2 trained groups, with higher correlation densities at DJ for both groups and higher densities at CMJ than SJ for G1, with opposite higher densities on SJ than CMJ for G2, as well as higher densities on G2 than G1 at SJ, DJ and similar densities at G1 and G2 on CMJ, Table 1. Higher centrality of vertical velocity correlation was registered at G1 untrained group for DJ on $vz max imp$, $vz mean imp$, $vz mean up$ and $vz take-off$ whereas at G2 trained group higher centrality was

detected for SJ, DJ on *vz min imp*, *vz mean down*, *vz mean up* and *vz take-off*, as well as *vz mean imp* for SJ and *vz max imp* and for DJ, Annex [18] – 3.4. Thus, *vz max imp*, *vz mean up* and *vz take-off* presents higher centrality at DJ for untrained and trained groups, whereas *vz min imp* higher centrality at DJ was registered exclusively at trained group, with DJ higher centrality of vertical velocity at trained than untrained group. The association of the vertical velocity variables presented dominant negative asymmetries corresponding to a larger number of nodes with higher number of statistically significant correlations.

Vertical velocity and vertical resultant force. The correlation densities of WB CoM vertical velocity and vertical resultant force variables presented opposite behavior at untrained and trained groups with higher value on SJ than CMJ both higher than DJ on G1, whereas G2 presented higher density on DJ than CMJ both higher than SJ, Table 1. Thus, G1 presents on SJ higher *vz - RFz* correlation density than G2, while G2 presents at CMJ and DJ higher correlation density than G1. Higher centrality of *vz - RFz* correlation density is shared on G1 for *vz min imp* at SJ, CMJ and DJ, *RFz start up* at SJ, CMJ and *RFz max land* at SJ, DJ, Annex [18] – 3.4.1, whereas higher centrality at CMJ is centered at *vz mean down* and *RFz min imp*. As regards to G2 higher centrality of *vz - RFz* correlation density is distributed by a larger number of variables namely at *vz mean down*, *vz min imp*, *vz mean up*, *RFz mean down*, *RFz mean up* and *RFz mean imp* on DJ and *vz mean up*, *vz max imp*, *vz take-off*, *RFz start up*, *RFz max imp* and *RFz mean up* on CMJ, [18] – 3.4.1. Furthermore, joint higher correlation centrality of *vz - RFz* at G1 and G2 was detected on *vz min imp* for CMJ, DJ as well as *RFz start up* on CMJ, with higher correlation centrality of *vz min imp*, *vz mean down*, *RFz mean down* at DJ on G2, Annex [18] – 3.4.1 and dominant higher centrality of *vz - RFz* at G2 than G1 for CMJ and DJ. Also, regarding the association of the vertical velocity and the vertical resultant force, G1 presented at CMJ and DJ, as well as G2 at SJ larger asymmetries corresponding to larger number of nodes with higher number of statistically significant correlations.

3.5 Mechanical power

Mechanical power variables presented opposite trends at untrained and trained groups, with higher correlation densities at CMJ than SJ and DJ for G1 and higher densities at DJ than SJ and CMJ for G2, as well as higher densities on G2 in relation to G1 for SJ, CMJ and DJ, Table 1. Lower power values were statistically tested for comparison to zero, with detected correlations evolving *P min imp* and *P mean down* discarded due to near zero power values, maintaining detected correlations with *P start up* due to non-statistically null power value. Higher centrality of power variables correlation was detected on G1 for *P min landing* at CMJ, *P max imp* at SJ, CMJ and *P mean up* at SJ, whereas higher centrality was detected on G2 for *P max imp* at CMJ, DJ and *P mean up* at SJ, CMJ and DJ, as well as *P min imp*, *P mean down* and *P start up* on DJ and *P mean imp* on SJ, [18] – 3.5. Thus, whereas *P max imp* and *P mean up* present higher correlation centrality at untrained and trained groups on SJ, CMJ and DJ along with *P take-off* on SJ, CMJ, *P min landing* on CMJ presents higher centrality exclusively at untrained group, with higher centrality of power variables on DJ for trained than untrained group, [18] – 3.5.

Vertical resultant force and mechanical power. Vertical resultant force and mechanical power variables presented higher correlation densities on trained group G2 in relation to untrained group G1, with higher values at DJ than CMJ both higher than SJ at G2 and similar densities for SJ, CMJ and DJ at G1, Table 1. Higher centrality of mechanical power and vertical force variables correlation at G1 were registered for *P start up*, *RFz take-off* on SJ *RFz max land* on CMJ and *P mean down*, *P mean up* on DJ. As regards to G2 higher centrality of mechanical power and vertical force variables with statistically significant correlation were registered for a large number of variables on DJ, with the highest degree of correlation centrality for *RFz mean up* on DJ and *RFz mean up*, *P mean imp* on CMJ, Annex [18] – 3.5.1. Thus, higher joint centrality on G1 and G2 was detected for *P mean down*, *P mean up*, *RFz mean up*, *RFz mean imp* on DJ and *RFz mean up* on CMJ, with higher centrality at G2 than G1 for a larger number of *RFz-P* variables on DJ and CMJ than SJ, Annex [18] – 3.5.1. The association of the vertical resultant force and developed mechanical power during vertical impulse presented opposite behavior with positive asymmetries at SJ, CMJ and DJ corresponding to a larger number of nodes with lower number of statistically significant correlations, whereas G2 presented negative asymmetries at SJ, CMJ and DJ corresponding to a larger number of nodes of a higher number of statistically significant correlations.

Vertical velocity and mechanical power. The test and the control groups, G1 and G2, of untrained and trained subjects presented similar comparisons for the correlation densities between discrete variables of the vertical velocity and the mechanical power developed during vertical impulse, with higher densities at DJ in relation to SJ and CMJ, as well as higher densities at G2 than G1, Table 1. Regarding the centralities of the correlation between vertical velocities and mechanical power developed during vertical impulse, the test and control groups present distinct behavior, Annex [18] – 3.5.2. Thus, whereas the test group G1 presented higher centrality on SJ for *P start up*, the control group G2 presented higher centrality for a larger number of variables, namely on DJ for *vz take-off*, *vz mean up*, *P mean down* and *P mean up*, as well as *vz max imp* on SJ and CMJ. Thus, G1 presented greater asymmetry for the distribution of nodes and correlations, with a larger number of *vz* and *P* variables without statically significant correlations, as well as positive asymmetries with decreasing amplitudes at SJ and DJ, whereas G2 presented at SJ and CMJ positive asymmetries with lower amplitudes, and negative asymmetry also with reduced amplitude at DJ corresponding to a larger number of variables with higher degree of correlations.

Vertical resultant force, vertical velocity and mechanical power. Jointly considered, the discrete variables from the vertical resultant force, vertical velocity and developed mechanical power presented distinct behavior for the correlation densities at the test and control groups. Thus, whereas the test group of untrained subjects presented similar densities at SJ and DJ higher than CMJ, the control group of trained subjects presents higher correlation density at DJ in relation to CMJ, both higher than SJ, Table 1. Also, the control group presented higher correlation densities of the *RFzç-vz-P* variables than the test group on SJ, CMJ and DJ. As regards *RFz-vz-P* discrete variables, the test and control groups share at DJ higher degree of centrality on *P mean up*, *RFz mean down*, *RFz mean up*, *P max imp* and *P mean down* pointing these variables as common features on untrained and trained groups with higher impact at the control of MVJ short countermovement, Annex [18] – 3.5.3. Finally, the asymmetry of the *RFz-vz-P* distributions presented on both groups dominant negative values with different amplitudes, pointing to a larger number of nodes with higher level of statistically significant correlations, and the exception of DJ at G1 with positive asymmetry and higher number of nodes with moderate correlations.

3.6 Vertical displacement

The density corresponding to the number of statistically significant correlations between the discrete variables of the CoM vertical displacement Δz and the maximum number of possible correlations presented different behaviors at the test and the control groups. Thus, whereas both groups presented higher Δz densities at DJ in relation to SJ and CMJ, the test group presented higher Δz density at SJ than CMJ, with the opposite higher density at CMJ than SJ for the control group, Table 1. Regarding the centrality associated with the number of statistically significant correlations between the variables of the CoM vertical displacement, whereas the test group presented at SJ and DJ larger number of variables with higher centrality, the control group concentrates at Δz max on CMJ and DJ the larger number of correlations, Annex [18] – 3.6. Thus, the test group presented larger centrality at Δz toff, Δz max and $h(imp)$ on SJ and DJ, Δz up on SJ, and $h(flight)$, $h(\Delta z)$ on DJ, whereas the control group presented larger centrality at Δz up on DJ, Δz max, $h(flight)$ and $h(imp)$ on CMJ, DJ and $h(\Delta z)$ on SJ, CMJ and DJ. For this reason, the distributions on the number of nodes and statistically significant correlations between the CoM vertical displacement variables presented strong negative asymmetry at DJ for the test group, as well as on SJ for the control group, with the distribution of a larger number of statistically significant correlations by a larger number of variables.

Vertical displacement and vertical resultant force. The densities of the statistically significant correlations between discrete variables from CoM vertical displacement and vertical resultant force presented opposite behaviors with higher density at the control group on DJ than CMJ, both higher than SJ, whereas the test group presented higher Δz -*RFz* correlation density at SJ than DJ, both higher than CMJ with no statistically significant correlations, Table 1. Also, the control group presented on SJ, CMJ and DJ higher correlation densities between Δz -*RFz* in relation to the test group. According to the reduced number of statistically significant correlations of Δz -*RFz* variables at the test group, the distribution of the number of nodes and correlations presented positive asymmetries with strong intensity at SJ and DJ, without statistically significant correlations at CMJ. Thus, the control group concentrates at Δz down, Δz up and *RFz take-off* on DJ higher degree of centrality with moderate positive correlation asymmetry at SJ, DJ and weak negative asymmetry at CMJ corresponding to the distribution of higher number of statistically significant correlations by a large number of nodes, Annex [18] – 3.6.1.

3.7 Mechanical work

Statistically significant correlations between discrete variables from the mechanical work W developed by the CoM during the impulse phase presented at the test group higher density at CMJ in relation to SJ both higher than DJ, and the opposite behavior at the control group with higher density at DJ in relation to SJ and CMJ, Table 1. Whereas the test group presented higher correlation centrality at $W imp$ and $W max imp$ for CMJ, the control group presented higher centrality at $W imp up$ for DJ, Annex [18] – 3.7. The distributions of the number of W nodes and correlations presented negative asymmetries, corresponding to the distribution of higher number of correlations at several nodes, with the strongest negative asymmetry at CMJ for the test group and moderate asymmetries at the remaining MVJ for both groups.

Vertical resultant force and Mechanical work. The test and the control groups presented similar densities for the statistically significant correlations between mechanical work and vertical resultant force variables with higher values at CMJ than SJ, both higher than DJ, Table 1. Regarding the centrality between $RFz -W$ variables, the test group presented higher centralities for $RFz take-off$ and $RFz max land$ on SJ and CMJ as well as for $W imp down$ on CMJ and DJ, whereas the control group presented higher centralities for $RFz take-off$ on SJ and DJ as well as for $W imp$, $W imp down$ and $W max imp$ on CMJ, Annex [18] – 3.7.1. The distribution of the number of nodes and correlations between $RFz -W$ variables presented on DJ for the test and control groups, as well as on SJ for the control group, positive asymmetries with large amplitudes corresponding to the concentration of a higher number of correlations at lower number of nodes.

Vertical displacement and mechanical work. Regarding the densities of the statistically significant correlations between mechanical work and CoM vertical displacement variables, the control group presented higher values than the test group, as well as higher density at DJ in relation SJ and CMJ, whereas the test group presented higher density at SJ than DJ and CMJ, Table 1. Regarding the centrality, whereas the test group presented a larger number of statistically significant correlations at $W imp$, $W imp up$ and $W max imp$ on SJ and $W imp$, $W imp up$ on DJ, the control group presents higher centrality at $W max imp$ on SJ and DJ, Annex [18] – 3.7.2. Thus, whereas SJ at the test group and CMJ, DJ at the control group presented negative asymmetry corresponding to the distribution of a larger number of nodes with higher number of statistically significant correlations, CMJ, DJ at the test group and SJ at the control group presented positive asymmetry corresponding to the concentration of a larger number of nodes with reduced number of statistically significant correlations.

Vertical resultant force, vertical displacement and mechanical work. Jointly, statistically significant correlations of the vertical resultant force, vertical displacement and mechanical work developed during vertical impulse phase presented higher density on SJ in relation to CMJ and DJ for the test group and the opposite behavior at the control group with higher density CMJ and DJ in relation to SJ, thus with higher densities at the control group in relation to the test group on CMJ and DJ, Table 1. Thus, whereas the test group presented higher centrality on SJ for a larger number of $RFz -\Delta z -W$ variables, the control group presented higher centrality on CMJ for a larger number of variables including $RFz max imp$, $\Delta z max$, $W imp$, $W imp up$, $W max imp$ and $RFz start up$ and DJ for $\Delta z up$ and $\Delta z max$, [18] – 3.7.3. The distributions of the number of nodes and correlations between $RFz -\Delta z -W$ variables presented thus reduced asymmetries for the test group on SJ, CMJ and DJ, whereas the control group negative asymmetries on SJ, CMJ and DJ correspond to a larger number of nodes with higher number of correlations.

4 Discussion

The asymmetries of the distributions from the number of nodes and correlations conduced to clear distinction at each MVJ type between the test and the control groups, with these differences detected at each variable's communities. The relevance of these findings supports the importance of graph tools and the selected metrics to assess highly correlated kinematic and dynamic parameters, particularly due to the limitations of classical statistical techniques to address uneven distributions corresponding to the concentration of a larger number of correlations at a reduced number of nodes, and a larger number of nodes with reduced statistically significant correlations. Thus, whereas the time variables presented at the test group dominant higher asymmetries at CMJ, the control group presented opposite higher asymmetries at SJ and DJ, pointing to higher number of nodes with reduced correlations and higher correlations at reduced number of nodes.

As regards to the distribution of RFz nodes and correlations, negative asymmetries were detected at DJ for the test group and SJ, DJ for the control group, pointing at these conditions to a larger number of nodes with higher correlations. The association of $RFz-\Delta t$, $\Delta t-I$ and $RFz-I$ variables shared at the test and control groups positive asymmetries for the distribution of the number of nodes and correlations, pointing to a larger number of nodes with reduced number of correlations, whereas the associations $I-I$, $\Delta t-RFz-I$ and vz shared at the test and the control groups negative asymmetries corresponding to a larger number of nodes with higher correlations. Regarding the associations of $vz - RFz$, $RFz - P$, $vz - P$ and $P - P$ variables, whereas the test group presented exclusively positive asymmetries corresponding to higher number of nodes with lower correlations, the control group presented dominant negative asymmetries corresponding to higher number of nodes with higher correlations. Nevertheless, $RFz-vz-P$ share at the test and control groups dominant negative asymmetries thus pointing to a larger number of nodes with higher correlations. The distributions of the CoM vertical displacement Δz and mechanical work W shared dominant negative asymmetries at the test and the control groups, thus pointing to larger number of nodes with higher correlations, whereas $\Delta z - RFz$ and $RFz - W$ variables shared at both groups dominant positive distributions corresponding to a larger number of nodes with reduced correlations and the concentration of larger correlations at lower number of nodes. Finally, $\Delta z - W$ and $RFz - \Delta z$ presented on SJ, CMJ and DJ opposite behavior at the test and the control groups symmetries pointing to differences of these distributions at each group.

The control group presented globally higher centrality in relation to the test group, corresponding to a larger level of association of each node. Also, whereas the test group presented higher centrality at SJ and DJ in relation to CMJ, the control group presented larger centrality at DJ in relation to CMJ and SJ. Thus, the centrality metric conduced to both differentiation of the test and the control groups, and at each of the groups between MVJ with long, short and no countermovement. This is particularly relevant, thus despite the same underlying relations from classical mechanics, differences were detected at nonparametric relations between the control and the test group, as well as between each MVJ type at the test and the control groups. Detected nodes with higher centrality at the control group correspond to a set of variables of interest for assessment by the strength and conditioning coaches on potential training advantage, particularly for those variables with lower centrality at the test group. Also, higher centrality nodes present as potential biomarkers with interest for assessment at the physiological level on each SSC condition and MVJ type for each of the trained and untrained groups.

Regarding the holistic systemic approach with the analysis of comprehensive biomechanical variables, the differences on the densities at each variable communities point also to groups of variables with similar comparison of the SJ, CMJ and DJ densities at the test and the control group, whereas other variable groups presented different comparison of the SJ, CMJ and DJ densities at the test and the control groups. Thus, whereas the (i) force-time-impulse variables presented larger number of groups F , $t-F$, I and $t-F-I$ with similar densities at the comparison of SJ, CMJ and DJ densities for the test and the control groups, the (ii) force-velocity-power and (iii) force-displacement-work presented lower number of groups, respectively $v-P$ and $F-W$, with similar densities at the comparison of SJ, CMJ and DJ densities for the test and the control groups. For this reason, the differentiation of the test and the control groups based on the comparison of SJ, CMJ and DJ densities, points to the need for complementary analysis of the (i) force-time-impulse variables with the (ii) force-velocity-power and (iii) force-displacement-work variables. This is particularly relevant due to the dominance of the SJ, CMJ and DJ comparison on previous studies based on force-time-impulse variables, since it points to the ability of the force-velocity-power and force-displacement-work variables as better discriminants between the trained and untrained groups in terms of correlation densities.

5 Conclusions

Whereas previous biomechanical studies, namely on lower limb muscle SSC and standard MVJ, were mainly focused on comparison of the mean values and standard deviations, accounting at the most for individual factor in isolation with no general interaction and underlying distribution assessment, this study presents a holistic systemic approach addressing comprehensive selected biomechanical variables and their bivariate statistically significant correlations at 5% significance. Assessed metrics presented also a complementary role. Thus, the assessment of asymmetries of the distributions from the number of nodes and correlations based on quantitative metric led to detection of differences at each MVJ between the test and the control groups. To the best of our knowledge this is the first study using a quantitative metric for assessment of the graph nodes and correlations distribution asymmetries and detection of the uneven distributions. This is particularly relevant due to the limitations of the

classical statistic metrics of the mean and variances to capture the nature of the inter-relation network, namely at uneven distributions with positive asymmetries, corresponding to a larger number of nodes with reduced correlations and the concentration of a larger number of correlations at a small number of nodes, as detected here.

Complementing the parametric underlying relations between the corresponding physical quantities, graph tools and associated metrics of density, centrality and asymmetries of the nodes and correlation distributions presented as an adequate method to assess nonparametric relations at highly correlated kinematic and dynamic parameters for detection of differences at each MVJ type between the test and the control group. Implemented data processing pipeline presents thus as an innovative methodological tool for holistic systemic approach with the analysis of comprehensive biomechanical variables and the detection of differences at each variable communities between SJ, CMJ and DJ at untrained and trained subjects, pointing to new variables with potential training interest as well as potential biomarkers with interest for assessment at the physiological level on each SSC condition and MVJ type. At the current stage of development, data processing pipeline includes the features for selection of different levels of significance, namely 1%, 5% and 10%, positive and negative linear correlations, nonlinear association, new dataset analysis, density, centrality and asymmetries of the nodes and correlation distributions, visualization, cluster detection, shared and specific group nodes with higher centralities.

Acknowledgements. Acknowledgments are due to the participants in the study.

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2.8 Dynamic characterization of thermoformed magneto-piezoelectret sensors using laser vibrometry and motionScope

Authors:

Leonardo S. Caires
Amélia M. Santos
Elvio P. Silva
Ronaldo M. Lima
Polyane A. Santos
Rui. A.S. Moreira
Sérgio M.O. Tavares
Ruy A.P. Altafim

Dynamic characterization of thermoformed magneto-piezoelectret sensors using laser vibrometry and motionscope

Leonardo S. Caires^{*1,2}, Amélia M. Santos¹, Elvio P. Silva^{1,2}, Ronaldo M. Lima^{1,3}, Polyane A. Santos^{1,2}, Rui A. S. Moreira¹, Sergio M. O. Tavares¹, Ruy A. P. Altafim⁴

¹*Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Aveiro*

Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193, Aveiro, Portugal

leonardocaires@ua.pt, ameliams@ua.pt, elvioprado@ua.pt, ronaldo.lima@ua.pt, polyane@ua.pt, rmoreira@ua.pt, smotavares@ua.pt

²*Department of Electrical Engineering, Federal Institute of Bahia*

Avenida Sérgio Vieira de Mello, 3150, Zabelê, Vitória da Conquista, 45078-300, Bahia, Brazil

³*Department of Physics, Federal Institute of Sergipe*

Avenida Engenheiro Gentil Tavares, 1166, Bairro Getúlio Vargas, Aracaju, Brazil

⁴*Computer System Department, Federal University of Paraíba*

Campus I Lot. Cidade Universitaria, Paraíba, 58051-900, Brazil

altafim@gmail.com

Abstract. This study addresses the technical challenge of dynamically characterising thermoformed magnetic piezoelectrets (TMPs), whose vibrational response remains poorly understood, thereby hindering their optimisation and application in advanced sensing technologies. To investigate this issue, two complementary methodologies were employed: MotionScope, for visualising the vibrations, and Laser Vibrometry, for quantifying deformations at 144 spatial points under electrical excitation ranging from 0 to 4 kHz. The results indicate that the piezoelectric coefficients (d_{33}) vary significantly with both frequency and spatial location, reaching higher values in the central regions of the channels. Three-dimensional analyses revealed localised resonant behaviours associated with the geometry and the non-uniform distribution of internal charges. This detailed dynamic characterisation enabled the identification of response patterns that may guide the geometric optimisation of the sensors. It is concluded that the vibrational response of TMPs is highly dependent on both excitation frequency and internal morphology, which is essential for the development of more sensitive and efficient sensors.

Keywords: Vibrational Behavior analysis, piezoelectric coefficient, inverse piezoelectric effect and energy harvesters applications.

1 Introduction

Applications based on electromechanical effects frequently employ piezoelectric materials, such as piezoceramics and electroactive polymers, among which electrically charged polymer foams are included. These materials, known as ferroelectrets or piezoelectrets, stand out due to their ability to generate electrical responses and retain high charge levels. Additionally, their low-density results in piezoelectric coefficients that surpass those found in natural piezoelectric polymers [1, 2].

Materials with piezoelectric properties have garnered significant interest within the scientific community because of their remarkable characteristics. These materials maintain electrical balance through a symmetric arrangement of opposite charges. When subjected to mechanical stresses, this balance is disrupted, leading to the displacement of internal charges and resulting in the generation of an electric potential within the material [3, 4].

Significant advances in materials science have demonstrated that combining polymers with distinct elastic and thermal properties, along with specific chemical treatments, can optimize charge-trapping efficiency and electromechanical sensitivity. These approaches have allowed the development of materials with piezoelectric coefficients that exceed those of advanced ceramics [1, 5, 6].

Among the various polymers used, fluoropolymers such as polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and its copolymer fluoroethylene propylene (FEP) stand out for their effectiveness in the manufacture of thermoformed piezoelectrets, due to their remarkable thermal stability [7].

A notable application of fluoropolymers involves the creation of structures with open tubular channels. Using PTFE molds, the methodology developed by Altafim [8] allows the formation of perfectly aligned tubular cavities in thermally laminated FEP films. This technique enables the customization of cavity geometries, resulting in

organized multilayered structures that can potentially optimize piezoelectric performance [9–11].

The combination of polymers with distinct properties has led to the development of a new type of multifunctional material: thermoformed magnetic piezoelectrets (TMPs). These materials are composed of multiple electret layers with open tubular channels, to which a magnetic layer is added. The presence of this magnetic layer enables the electrically charged tubular channels to contract or expand under the influence of an external magnetic field. This mechanical deformation disrupts the material's electrical equilibrium, generating an electrical response that is directly proportional to the intensity of the applied magnetic field [12].

Given that TMPs undergo mechanical deformation when exposed to an external magnetic field, it is plausible that they exhibit similar responses when subjected to electrical stimuli. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in polymer-based piezoelectrics [13], not only due to their flexibility and low cost, but also because of their wide applicability in energy harvesting systems and biomedical devices, particularly with the development of wearable sensors based on advanced ferroelectrets [14]. Advances in cellular and porous architectures have enhanced the electromechanical properties of fluoropolymers, extending their use in applications ranging from wearable electronics to tissue engineering [15–17]. The purpose of this study is to analyze the vibrational behavior of TMPs, making a comparison between two distinct techniques to gain a deeper understanding of their functional properties and assess potential applications in sensor technologies and energy harvesting.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Development of TMPs

The procedure described in [12] was adopted for the fabrication of TMPs. Initially, two FEP films, each $50\ \mu\text{m}$ thick, were joined by lamination at 300°C to form a multilayer structure. A PTFE template, $100\ \mu\text{m}$ thick and with rectangular cutouts, was placed between the FEP layers before the lamination process. This template guided the fusion process, creating organized channels in the structure. For this study, the template was designed to produce four parallel channels, each $2\ \text{mm}$ wide with a uniform spacing between them.

The subsequent stage of the process involved applying magnetic tape strips to cover each of the channels. These strips were laser-cut into rectangular dimensions ($1.5\ \text{mm} \times 15\ \text{mm}$) from a $300\ \mu\text{m}$ thick laminated magnetic adhesive mat provided by Fermag-BR. The introduction of the magnetic layer caused surface irregularities, which made electrode formation challenging. To overcome this issue, a third FEP film, also $50\ \mu\text{m}$ thick, was laminated over the magnetic strips at 300°C . Finally, the PTFE template was carefully removed, leaving open channels embedded within the FEP matrix. The entire layer composition process is schematically illustrated in Fig. 1. After producing the multilayer structure aluminum electrodes were applied to the external FEP layers using a vacuum deposition process, establishing the conductive surfaces. Subsequently, the TMP devices were electrically charged by applying a voltage of $3.5\ \text{kV}_{\text{DC}}$ for 10 s.

Figure 1. Fabrication procedure for TMPs with open tubular channels and piezoelectric-magnetic response. (a) Electrode, (b) FEP, (c) Magnetic layer, (d) Air cavity and (e) PTFE template removed.

2.2 Evaluation of Vibrational Oscillations

For the vibrational study of TMPs, two types of analysis were carried out: a visual analysis using MotionScope technology and a vibrational analysis using the laser vibrometer, both set within the frequency range of 0 to 4 kHz. Fig. 2 illustrate the main points investigated in this experiment: (a) the TMP at scale, providing an overview of the sample; (b) the presentation of the measurements obtained with the MotionScope, allowing a dynamic analysis of the material's behavior; (c) the representation of the measured points with the laser vibrometer, highlighting

the data collection locations for the vibrational analysis; and (d) the displayed channels and valleys, which aid in a better understanding and analysis of the results, enabling a more detailed visualization of the system's vibrational characteristics.

Figure 2. Measurement methodology of the points: (a) TMP on a scale, (b) visualisation of the points from the MotionScope, (c) positioning of the measurements using the Vibrometer and (d) representation of the channels (C_a , C_b , and C_c) with lengths of 2 mm and the valleys (V_1 , V_2 , and V_3) with lengths of 3 mm.

(i) Laser Vibrometer

The mechanical response of the TMP due to the electrical excitation was assessed using a Polytec Laser Vibrometer (model OFV-5000), coupled with a decoder. Vibrational measurements were recorded with the vibrometer's integrated software and subsequently processed using a Spectral Dynamics analyzer (model SigLab 2042) and a UNI-T oscilloscope (model UT3102C). To stimulate the material, an external electrical excitation consisting of a white noise signal, with a frequency range of 0 to 4 kHz and a signal was applied using a signal generator. This signal was amplified using a high-voltage, high-speed linear amplifier (model A-301, TREK), resulting in a final excitation amplitude of ± 160 V ($320 V_{pp}$) directed applied to the TMP aluminum electrodes. The mechanical deformation was measured at 144 spatial points subdivided between the channels and valleys (fused areas) of the TMP.

The experimental setup, illustrated in Fig. 3, provides a schematic view of the system, detailing the components involved, including the excitation source, measurement instruments, and the TMP sample. The vibrometer laser was configured with the following parameters: a sensitivity of $5 \text{ mm s}^{-1}/V$, frequency range between 0 and 4 kHz, and a low-pass filter set at 20 kHz. The TMP sample was secured in an acrylic holder mounted on an XY micrometric stage, enabling precise positioning and control over the measurement points.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the experiment: (a) Laser vibrometer, (b) Spectral analyzer, (c) Oscilloscope, (d) Dynamic signal analyzer, (e) High voltage amplifier and (f) TMP.

(iii) The piezoelectric coefficient d_{33}

The piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} , which quantifies the mechanical deformation of the material in response to the applied electric field, is obtained by using the displacement measurement and the excitation voltage [18]. The excitation voltage V_{ex} is represented as a sinusoidal function:

$$V_{ex} = V_{max} \cdot \sin(\omega t), \quad (1)$$

where V_{max} is the maximum excitation voltage and ω is the angular frequency of the excitation. The measured displacement μ_{out} is represented as:

$$\mu_{out} = \mu_{max} \cdot \sin(\omega t + \phi), \quad (2)$$

where μ_{max} is the maximum displacement and ϕ is the phase shift of the excitation signal. The piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} is calculated as expressed in (3):

$$d_{33} = \frac{\mu_{max}}{V_{max}}. \quad (3)$$

The direct output is a voltage signal from the vibrometer velocity decoder. The maximum displacement is calculated using the voltage output and sensitivity of the velocity decoder:

$$\mu_{max} = \frac{V_{amp} \cdot \delta}{\omega}, \quad (4)$$

where V_{amp} is the amplitude voltage output from the velocity decoder, and δ is the decoder sensitivity (mms^{-1}/V).

(ii) MotionScope

MotionScope is a sophisticated motion analysis technique that employs image processing algorithms to identify and visualize vibrations in objects. Its high precision and sensitivity make MotionScope an essential tool for the detailed analysis of vibrational patterns.

The experiment utilised a 150 fps camera to capture high-resolution videos of the TMP, as shown in Fig. 4(a), followed by a lighting system to assist the experiment, depicted in Fig. 4(b). In Fig. 4(c), the TMP is encapsulated within a shielded structure that receives signals of specific frequencies and exhibits subtle displacements indicative of vibrations. These vibrations represent the inverse response of the piezoelectric effect in the TMP, similar to the experiment conducted with the vibrometer. These small displacements are then represented through colour mapping, facilitating a more intuitive visualisation of their amplitudes. The videos obtained in this experiment were uploaded to MATLAB and processed to separate them into a sequence of 30 image frames for analysis. This method enabled the precise analysis of the sensor's vibrations, covering a frequency range from 0 to 4 kHz, corresponding to the operational limit of the equipment.

Figure 4. Experiment conducted with MotionScope: (a) 150 fps video camera, (b) Lighting system and (c) Encapsulated TMP.

3 Results and Discussion

The tests conducted in both experiments provided frequency response data from 0 to 4 kHz, due to the operational limits of the MotionScope. Nevertheless, this amount of data had to be reduced for this paper and only response from 50 Hz, 1 kHz, and 4 kHz are presented.

By mapping 144 points using the laser Vibrometer, it was possible to represent the three-dimensional surface of the piezoelectric coefficient (d_{33}). Each laser positioning point recorded an average of at least 100 readings from a complex matrix containing magnitude and phase components. These values were processed in MATLAB. The three-dimensional surface map of the frequency variation of d_{33} for the TMP at a frequency of 50 Hz is presented in Fig. 5(a). The peaks on the surface represent regions with higher piezoelectric coefficient values, while the

valleys indicate areas with reduced activity, lacking the presence of air cavities. The two-dimensional top view is presented in Fig. 5(b).

This non-uniform distribution indicates structural differences in the construction of the TMP. The heterogeneity of d_{33} can be attributed to the anisotropic coupling between the different materials that make up the TMP. Moreover, a non-uniform charge distribution may amplify these observed effects.

The Fig. 6(a) presents the behaviour of d_{33} at a frequency of 1 kHz. The distribution of mechanical deformation between the channels (C_a , C_b , and C_c) and valleys (V_1 , V_2 , and V_3) of the TMP regions can be observed. This demonstrates that the behaviour of the TMP is influenced by the frequency. The two-dimensional top view presented in Fig. 6(b) highlights that the amplitude peaks occur in the channels of the TMP. The red colour represents the highest values observed at this frequency, while the blue colour, concentrated in the valleys, indicates the lowest deformations in the structure.

The spatial distribution of d_{33} at the frequency of 4 kHz is presented in Fig. 7(a). This map reveals that the piezoelectric response is more concentrated in this frequency range within the first channel. This may indicate specific resonance effects or dynamic alignment of domains in that region. The sharper features, as visualized in Fig. 7(b), may highlight areas with enhanced piezoelectric coupling, demonstrating greater response sensitivity.

The observed distributions also emphasize the importance of frequency in modulating the expected piezoelectric response of the TMP, highlighting regions where its activity is more pronounced. Tab. 1 presents the maximum d_{33} values measured at the frequencies evaluated during the experiment, corresponding to the highest peaks of the obtained curves.

Table 1. Maximum Values of the Piezoelectric Coefficient by Frequency.

Frequency	d_{33}
50 Hz	25.59 $\mu V/m$
1 kHz	14.38 nV/m
4 kHz	16.49 nV/m

These results suggest the presence of resonance effects or frequency-specific alignment of the material domains, enhancing piezoelectric performance in specific areas. The irregular vibration behaviour observed in the TMP structural mapping can partially be attributed to the non-uniform distribution of electric charges on the internal surfaces of the cavities.

Figure 5. Surface map of the experiment. (a) 3D map of the measured d_{33} matrix (m/V) of the 144 measurement points at a frequency of 50 Hz and (b) top view of the matrix points.

The experiment using the MotionScope technique allows for the analysis of the vibrational behaviour and displacement of the TMP structure. The visualisation obtained after processing the video for a frequency of 50 Hz is show in Fig. 8. The concentration of red at this frequency in the lower-left area of the frames, followed by a transition to blue in the same region, indicates a resonance point or an area with a higher amplitude of motion. The colour shift reflects the sensor's dynamic response to this resonance. This result supports the quantitative values obtained in the experiment conducted with the laser vibrometer.

The results obtained for the 1 kHz frequency are presented in Fig. 9. At this intermediate frequency, a broader distribution of colours is observed, reflecting the mechanical displacement of the TMP structure. It is notable that red and blue colours are specifically concentrated in the regions corresponding to the channels (C_a , C_b , and C_c), although the widths of the coloured traces are relatively narrow. This behaviour suggests that the sensor responds differently across various frequency ranges.

2.8 Dynamic characterization of thermoformed magneto-piezoelectret sensors using laser vibrometry and motionScope

Figure 6. Surface map of the experiment. (a) 3D map of the measured d_{33} matrix (m/V) of the 144 measurement points at a frequency of 1 kHz and (b) top view of the matrix points.

Figure 7. Surface map of the experiment. (a) 3D map of the measured d_{33} matrix (m/V) of the 144 measurement points at a frequency of 4 kHz and (b) top view of the matrix points.

Figure 8. Visualization of TMP sensor vibration captured by MotionScope, representing 30 frames illustrating the sensor's vibration behavior at a frequency of 50 Hz.

Figure 9. Visualization of TMP sensor vibration captured by MotionScope, representing 30 frames illustrating the sensor's vibration behavior at a frequency of 1 kHz.

Fig. 10 illustrates the behaviour of the TMP at the 4 kHz frequency range, where greater sharpness is observed in the areas corresponding to the channels. The transition of colours from blue to red and back to blue indicates a change in the direction of the channel's displacement. This variation in colour and direction may suggest the presence of a damping zone before reaching resonance. Within this range, the sensor's motion appears to be damped, resulting in lower oscillation amplitudes. As the frequency approaches the resonance point, the amplitude of the motion increases significantly, leading to changes in direction and, consequently, to the observed colour transitions.

Figure 10. Visualization of TMP sensor vibration captured by MotionScope, representing 30 frames illustrating the sensor's vibration behavior at a frequency of 4 kHz.

The high frame rate videos enables precise visualization of extremely small or rapid displacements between the channels (C_a , C_b , and C_c) and valleys (V_1 , V_2 , and V_3) of the TMP sensor. The obtained result reinforces previous observations and aligns with the quantitative d_{33} data collected in the experiment with the laser Vibrometer. This type of analysis is essential for studying vibrational phenomena in dynamic systems, particularly when investigating oscillation modes and the effects of different frequencies or excitations. This technique provided valuable insights for adjusting and detecting patterns in the mechanical response, as well as optimizing the geometry and the sensor behavior. This contributes to improved performance and sensitivity, benefiting the development of future versions.

4 Conclusion

The TMPs constitute an innovative class of multifunctional materials not yet commercially available, combining magnetoelectric and piezoelectric properties in an integrated manner. This study investigates the behavior of the inverse piezoelectric effect, utilizing a laser vibrometer to analyze the deformations of the channels and valleys, and employs the motionScope technique to visualize these deformations by applying electrical stimuli to the TMP. The frequency range used in the experiments varied from 0 to 4 kHz, enabling the creation of detailed 3D and 2D maps of the TMPs vibration modes, as well as the visualization of deformation frames.

The results revealed distinct piezoelectric behaviors in the channels and valleys of the TMP, highlighting the critical role of the structural geometry and material properties. The channels exhibited pronounced resonance peaks and greater variability in d_{33} values, reflecting their high sensitivity and localized piezoelectric activity. However, this variability also indicates structural heterogeneity, which may impact uniform performance. In contrast, the valleys demonstrated smoother and more uniform responses, with higher damping that provides stability and efficient energy dissipation.

The use of MotionScope allowed for precise visualization of the vibrations, facilitating the interpretation of the data and revealing that the vibrations occur in a pattern within the air channel cavities of the TMP sensor, as expected. It also demonstrated that along the channels, the effect is not consistent in amplitude, revealing that the charge distribution or mechanical deformation does not occur uniformly.

In summary, the study made a significant contribution to understanding the functional properties of TMPs and demonstrated the potential of these materials in advanced applications. The combination of vibrational analysis techniques and optimization of sensor geometry allows for the enhancement of the performance of these devices. These advancements are promising for the development of more efficient and sensitive sensors, which can be used in various technological fields.

Acknowledgements. The authors express their gratitude to the Department of Mechanical Engineering of the

University of Aveiro and the Centre for Mechanical Technology and Automation (TEMA) for their invaluable support. This work is funded by the PRR and NextGenerationEU under the project “ATE—Alliance for Energy Transition” (ref. C644914747-00000023), and also supported by project UID 00481.

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2.9 Optimizing the Perseverance rover's wheel support system using a bio-inspired remodelling algorithm

Authors:

Rui Monteiro

Daniel Rodrigues

Ana Pais

Jorge Belinha

Optimizing the Perseverance rover's wheel support system using a bio-inspired remodelling algorithm

Rui Monteiro^{1,4}, Daniel Rodrigues^{1,2,4}, Ana Pais^{3,4}, and Jorge Belinha^{1,4,*}

¹ *Department of Mechanical Engineering, ISEP, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal*

² *Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Aveiro, Portugal*

³ *Department of Mechanical Engineering, FEUP, University of Porto, Portugal*

⁴ *Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering*

*Corresponding author's email: job@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract: Nowadays, in space exploration, the limiting factors are the launch cost of devices into space, as well as the payload and volume limit of launch devices. For this, in order to reduce the launching cost, it is necessary that the components sent to space, in addition to fulfilling their function, are reliable, with a reduced mass. The remodelling process used is a Bio-Inspired Remodelling Algorithm (BIRA), which is based on the remodelling of bone tissue. In the remodelling procedure, a mechanical stimulus will trigger the remodelling process, increasing the density of areas under a higher stress and decreasing the density of areas under lower stress [1]. To this end, numerical methods have been used such as Finite Element Method (FEM) and two meshless methods: the Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM) and Natural Neighbour Radial Point Interpolation Method (NNRPIM). Although some of these methods need a background mesh, the ones categorized as truly meshless methods, like NNRPIM, do not need a mesh at all. In order to validate the methods used in this work, some benchmark problems were conducted showing very similar results to the ones previously observed in the benchmark problems. This culminated in the analysis and optimization of the Perseverance rover part that connects the wheel to the suspension system. The results obtained showed that there is room for improvement in the design of the rover part which would result in a decrease in its weight. This optimization can translate into a lower cost of launching of the rover to Mars thus helping to overcome one of the major obstacles to space exploration.

Keywords: Space exploration, Finite Element Method, Meshless method, Natural neighbour radial point interpolation method, Radial Point Interpolation Method; Bio Inspired Remodelling Algorithm.

1 Introduction

Technological innovation has been fuelled by space exploration, leading to important milestones and improvements in gadget performance. In order to increase efficiency, usefulness, and dependability, and enable more ambitious missions, it is imperative that the structural components of space exploration instruments be optimized. The use of sophisticated numerical techniques for the structural analysis and design of space components, such as the Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM) and the Natural Neighbour Radial Point Interpolation Method (NNRPIM), is one viable strategy. As an alternative to the widely utilized Finite Element Method (FEM), these sophisticated discretization approaches have the significant benefit of simulating larger deformations and more intricate structures without experiencing mesh distortions. While some of these techniques require a background mesh, others, such as NNRPIM, fall under the category of truly meshless techniques, which require no mesh at all. Optimized component models can be created by combining these numerical techniques with the Bio-Inspired Remodelling Algorithm (BIRA).

In this work, the component that connects the wheel to the suspension in NASA's Perseverance is studied. The main objective is to develop a new design with higher stiffness than the original design using the FEM, RPIM and NNRPIM as discretization techniques. In order to accomplish this, the steps are: understanding the mathematical formulation of the meshless methods RPIM and NNRPIM, benchmark problems resolution and remodelling analyses on the component.

2 Numerical methods

This work will focus on the meshless methods RPIM and NNRPIM paired with BIRA and in this chapter is presented the mathematical formulation of these methods and algorithms.

2.1 RPIM

Despite being categorized as a meshless method, this is a misleading classification since the set of integration points is independent of the initial nodal distributions. In this method, the nodal connectivity is established by the influence domain and then shape functions are constructed, making it possible to approximate/interpolate the variable field at an integration point \mathbf{x}_I with Equation (1)

$$u(\mathbf{x}_I) = \sum_{i=1}^n \varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot u(\mathbf{x}_i) = \boldsymbol{\phi}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{u}_s = \{\varphi_1(\mathbf{x}_I), \varphi_2(\mathbf{x}_I), \dots, \varphi_n(\mathbf{x}_I)\} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u(\mathbf{x}_1) \\ u(\mathbf{x}_2) \\ \dots \\ u(\mathbf{x}_n) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where n is the number of nodes within the influence-domain of the integration point \mathbf{x}_I , \mathbf{u}_s is a vector that contains the field variable components of each node \mathbf{x}_i inside the influence domain of \mathbf{x}_I , and $\varphi_i(\mathbf{x}_I)$ is the i^{th} component of the shape function constructed for \mathbf{x}_I [1],[2].

The influence-domains are found by searching enough nodes inside a fixed area when the problem is 2 dimensional or a fixed volume for the 3-dimensional problems. This is a simple approach to the problem, although it can lead to inaccurate solutions due to size or shape variation of the influence-domains along the problem domain. The influence-domains must contain approximately the same number of nodes in order for them to have the same degree of complexity. In the 2-dimensional problems, generally these influence domains can be rectangular or circular, with the rectangular ones being fixed sized (fixed rectangular influence-domain) and the circular ones being fixed (fixed circular influence-domain) or variable sized (flexible circular influence-domain). A dimension d is applied to the influence domains following the Equation (2):

$$d = k \times h \quad (2)$$

where h is the average nodal spacing in the surroundings of \mathbf{x}_I and k a dimensionless parameter with values between 1.5 and 2.5 [3].

To establish the background integration points, this method employs a background mesh that partitions the problem domain into regular integration cells. These cells are then mapped onto an isoparametric square, where the integration points are defined according to a Gauss–Legendre integration scheme. After that it becomes possible to integrate a function $f(x, y)$, defined inside a quadrilateral domain Ω_h , using a Gauss–Legendre integration scheme with $2 \times 2 = 4$ integration points:

$$F = \int_{\Omega_h} f(x, y) d\Omega_h = \sum_{I=1}^4 f(x_I, y_I) \cdot \hat{\omega}_I \quad (3)$$

With $\hat{\omega}_I$ being the Cartesian integration weight of each integration point.

This process is repeated for each integration cell, obtaining a background integration mesh of n_Q integration points. Since the background integration cell is coincident with the problem's domain, it is possible to calculate the area of the problem domain using:

$$A_{\Omega} = \sum_{I=1}^{n_Q} \hat{\omega}_I \quad (4)$$

2.2 NNRPIM

Although being developed from RPIM, this is a truly meshless method being able of autonomously construct all the requirements to solve the problem using only the nodal distribution.

For the nodal connectivity this method uses a concept of a natural neighbour requiring a construction of the Voronoï diagram of the problem's nodal discretisation. In a 2-dimensional problem domain, $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^2$ discretised with N nodes, $\mathbf{X} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\} \in \mathbb{R}^2$, the Voronoï diagram, V , of \mathbf{X} is formed by subsections V_i closed and convex, defined in and defining the same sub-space $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^2$ with each node x_i possessing its own cell V_i where all points in the cell are closer to x_i than any other given node $x_j \in \mathbf{X}$. The Voronoï diagram of \mathbf{X} , $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_N\}$ and the Voronoï cells V_i do not overlap nor leave gaps between each other so they verify: $\Omega = \sum_{i=1}^N V_i \therefore V = \Omega$ [1].

For the integration points to be created, a given Voronoï cell V_i is divided into quadrilaterals with each one being transformed into a unit isoparametric square where the distribution of integration points respect the Gauss–Legendre integration scheme. In order to integrate an assumed function $f(x, y)$, located inside a quadrilateral sub-area domain, Ω_s , a Gauss–Legendre integration scheme with $2 \times 2 = 4$ integration points is used Equation (5) [1].

$$F = \int_{\Omega_s} f(x, y) d\Omega_s = \sum_{i=1}^4 f(x_i, y_i) \cdot \hat{\omega}_i \quad (5)$$

2.3 Shape functions

Both RPIM and NNRPIM share the same process, using the radial point interpolating technique. In this technique is assumed a 2D domain, $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^2$, in which a field function $u(x)$ is discretised with N nodes, $\mathbf{X} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\} \in \mathbb{R}^2$, the interpolation value $u(x_i)$ of a given integration point, $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^2 \wedge x_i \in X$, can be calculated by

$$u(x_i) = \left\{ \mathbf{r}(x_i)^T, \mathbf{p}(x_i)^T \right\} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

with $\mathbf{r}(x_i) = \{r_1(x_i), r_2(x_i), \dots, r_n(x_i)\}^T$ being a Radial Basis Function (RBF), $\mathbf{p}(x_i) = \{p_1(x_i), p_2(x_i), \dots, p_m(x_i)\}^T$ being a polynomial basis function and the vectors of the non-constant coefficients of $\mathbf{r}(x_i)$ and $\mathbf{p}(x_i)$ defined as, $\mathbf{a}(x_i) = \{a_1(x_i), a_2(x_i), \dots, a_n(x_i)\}^T$ and $\mathbf{b}(x_i) = \{b_1(x_i), b_2(x_i), \dots, b_m(x_i)\}^T$ [1].

Following a Multiquadric Radial Basis Function (MQ-RBF) of Hardy,

$$r_j(x_i) = r_{ij} = \left(d_{ij}^2 + (\hat{\omega}_i \cdot c)^2 \right)^p = \left(\left(\sqrt{(x_j - x_i)^2 + (y_j - y_i)^2} \right)^2 + (\hat{\omega}_i \cdot c)^2 \right)^p \quad (7)$$

with c and p being two constants of the MQ-RBF with recommended values close but different from zero for c and close but different from one for p (generally $c = 10^{-4}$ and $p = 1 - 10^{-4}$) [1]. In order to ensure a unique solution, there is the need to add the following equation:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n p_j(x_i) a_i(x_i) = 0 \quad (8)$$

Where $j = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$. Joining together the Equations (6) and (8), a new equation matrix is obtained:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{P} \\ \mathbf{P}^T & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{G} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_s \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Where \mathbf{u}_s is the vector of nodal parameters, \mathbf{R} is the RBF matrix and \mathbf{P} is the polynomial basis matrix. Analysing Equation (9), it is obtained:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{G}^{-1} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_s \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

That when inserted in Equation (6) the interpolation at \mathbf{x}_i can be defined as:

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_i) = \left\{ \mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_i)^T, \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_i)^T \right\} \mathbf{G}^{-1} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_s \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \left\{ \phi(\mathbf{x}_i), \Psi(\mathbf{x}_i) \right\} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_s \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Where $\phi(\mathbf{x}_i)$ is the interpolation function of \mathbf{x}_i :

$$\left\{ \phi(\mathbf{x}_i), \Psi(\mathbf{x}_i) \right\} = \left\{ \mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_i)^T, \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_i)^T \right\} \mathbf{G}^{-1} = \left\{ \phi_1(\mathbf{x}_i), \dots, \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_i), \Psi_1(\mathbf{x}_i), \dots, \Psi_m(\mathbf{x}_i) \right\} \quad (12)$$

The integro-differential equations ruling elasticity require the calculation of the partial derivatives of $\phi(\mathbf{x}_i)$, so if a general direction ζ is assumed:

$$\phi_\zeta(\mathbf{x}_i) = \left\{ \mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_i)_{\zeta}^T, \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_i)_{\zeta}^T \right\} \mathbf{G}^{-1} \quad (13)$$

2.4 System of equations

The system of equations is also defined in the same way for the RPIM and the NNRPIM. Considering a solid domain Ω , bounded by a surface boundary Γ that contain natural boundaries Γ_t and essential boundaries Γ_u , the solid domain is constricted at Γ_u and suffer a body force \mathbf{b} and forces $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$ on Γ_t . Defining that work of external forces equals work of internal forces $W_{int} = W_{ext}$, it is obtained [2]:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_i)^T \cdot \mathbf{b} d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_t} \delta \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_i)^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} d\Gamma \quad (14)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the deformation tensor and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the strain tensor. In 2-dimensional problems, Equation (14) requires two displacement components $\{u, v\}$, that can be defined as:

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_i) = \begin{Bmatrix} u(\mathbf{x}_i) \\ v(\mathbf{x}_i) \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_i) \cdot \mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_1(\mathbf{x}_i) & 0 & \dots & \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_i) & 0 \\ 0 & \phi_1(\mathbf{x}_i) & \dots & 0 & \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_i) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ v_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \\ v_n \end{Bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

With the representation of the deformation vector:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}_i) = \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_i) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \phi(\mathbf{x}_i) \cdot \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_i) \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ v_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \\ v_n \end{Bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_i)$ being the deformation matrix defined as:

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_i) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \phi_1(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial x} & 0 & \dots & \frac{\partial \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial \phi_1(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial y} & \dots & 0 & \frac{\partial \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial \phi_1(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial \phi_1(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial x} & \dots & \frac{\partial \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

The stress can be calculated at the integration point \mathbf{x}_i Assuming Hooke's law:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u} \quad (18)$$

In a 2D plane, material constitutive matrix $\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I)$ is defined as:

$$\mathbf{c} = \frac{E_2}{1 - \alpha_1 \cdot \nu_{21}^2} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_1 \cdot \nu_{21} & 0 \\ \alpha_1 \cdot \nu_{21} & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_2 \cdot (1 - \alpha_1 \cdot \nu_{21}^2) \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{if plane stress considered} \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{c} = \frac{E_2}{\alpha_3 \cdot \alpha_4} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 \cdot (1 - \alpha_1 \cdot \nu_{21}^2) & \alpha_1 \cdot \nu_{21} \cdot \alpha_3 & 0 \\ \alpha_1 \cdot \nu_{21} \cdot \alpha_3 & 1 - \nu_{12}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_2 \cdot \alpha_3 \cdot \alpha_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{if plane strain considered} \quad (20)$$

With $\alpha_1 = E_1/E_2$, $\alpha_2 = G_{12}/E_2$, $\alpha_3 = 1 + \nu_{12}$ and $\alpha_4 = 1 - \nu_{12} - 2 \cdot \alpha_1 \cdot \nu_{21}^2$ where G_{ij} the elastic shear modulus in the plane O_{ij} , E_i is the Young's modulus in material direction i and ν_{ij} the Poisson's coefficient in the plane O_{ij} .

With the manipulation of the equation (14) replacing the stress and strain vectors it is obtained:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta(\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u})^T \cdot (\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u}) d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta(\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u})^T \cdot \mathbf{b} d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \delta(\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u})^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} d\Gamma \quad (21)$$

That when considering the small strains $\delta\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) = 0$ and $\delta\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I) = 0$, can be simplified to:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \delta\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u} d\Omega &= \int_{\Omega} \delta\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{b} d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \delta\mathbf{u}^T \cdot \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} d\Gamma \\ \Leftrightarrow \delta\mathbf{u}^T \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot d\Omega \cdot \mathbf{u} &= \delta\mathbf{u}^T \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot d\Omega + \delta\mathbf{u}^T \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \cdot d\Gamma \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Making it possible to define the global displacement field of the problem:

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{K}^{-1} \cdot (\mathbf{f}_b + \mathbf{f}_t) \quad (23)$$

Where global stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} in its discretised form is defined as:

$$\mathbf{K} = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) d\Omega = \sum_{I=1}^{N_{\theta}} \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \hat{\omega}_I \cdot h(\mathbf{x}_I) \quad (24)$$

And the external force vector \mathbf{f}_t and the global body vector \mathbf{f}_b :

$$\mathbf{f}_t = \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \cdot d\Gamma = \sum_{J=1}^{N_{\theta}} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_J)^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \cdot \hat{\omega}_J \quad (25)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_b = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot d\Omega = \sum_{I=1}^{N_{\theta}} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot \hat{\omega}_I \cdot h(\mathbf{x}_I) \quad (26)$$

Where $h(\mathbf{x}_I)$ is the thickness of the 2D solid at the location of the integration point \mathbf{x}_I [1],[2].

3 Results

In this chapter, are presented the numerical results for the benchmark problems analysed and also the obtained optimized model for the rover component.

3.1 Cantilever Beam

A 2-dimensional analysis over a beam is performed in this study. With a length (L) of 2 m, a width (W) of 1 m and a thickness (t) of 1 m, the beam is constrained in the left side and a distributed load (P) of 1 N/m is applied along the right side, as shown in Figure 1. For the material properties used in this study, it was chosen a Young's modulus (E) of 1 kPa and a Poisson's ratio (ν) of 0.3. In the points A, B and C will be analysed the displacement along y (v), shear stress (τ_{xy}) and stress (σ_{xx}) respectively. The results are then compared with the analytical solutions that follow the Equations (28), (29), (30), (31) and (32) [3].

$$\sigma_{xx} = -\frac{P \cdot (L-x) \cdot y}{I} \quad (27)$$

$$\sigma_{yy} = 0 \quad (28)$$

$$\sigma_{xy} = \frac{P \cdot D^2}{8 \cdot I} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{4y^2}{D^2}\right) \quad (29)$$

with $I = D^3 / 12$, and $D = W = t$ as the side length of the beam's cross section.

$$u(x) = -\frac{2P}{E \cdot D^3} \left[3x \cdot (2L-x) \cdot y + (2+\nu) \cdot \left(y^2 - \frac{D^2}{4} \right) \cdot y \right] \quad (30)$$

$$v(x) = \frac{2P}{E \cdot D^3} \left[x^2 \cdot (3L-x) + 3\nu \cdot (L-x) \cdot y^2 + x \cdot (4+5\nu) \cdot \frac{D^2}{4} \right] \quad (31)$$

A triangular mesh with 3 nodes and a quadrangular mesh with 4 nodes shown in Figure 2 are used in this work with divisions along x and y as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Divisions along x and y and respective number of nodes

x-axis divisions	y-axis divisions	number of nodes
4	2	15
8	4	45
16	8	153
32	16	561
64	32	2145
128	64	8385

Figure 1. Cantilever Beam.

Figure 2. a) Quadrangular mesh with 4 nodes b) Triangular mesh with 3 nodes.

The parameters used in the RPIM analysis are: 16 nodes within each influence domain, constants to be used in the MQ-RBF are $c = 1.42$ and $p = 1.03$. In the NNRPIM analysis, the parameters to be used in the MQ-RBF are $c = 0.0001$ and $p = 0.9999$.

Presented in Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5 are the results for the convergence analyses. In Figure 3, the displacement along y direction converges faster using meshless methods in comparison with the FEM, when a grid composed of triangular elements with 3 nodes. In the shear stress analysis, shown in Figure 4, it is also noticeable that the meshless methods converge earlier than FEM and, when looking at the analysis performed using triangular mesh with 3 nodes, it is showcased that FEM cannot obtain a result as accurately as meshless methods even when using the mesh with higher number of nodes. In Figure 5, contrary to what was shown in the previous analyses, FEM converge earlier than meshless methods when using the triangular mesh with 3 nodes.

Figure 3. Displacement along y analysis a) using quadrangular mesh with 4 nodes; b) using triangular mesh with 3 nodes.

Figure 4. Shear stress analysis a) using quadrangular mesh with 4 nodes; b) using triangular mesh with 3 nodes.

Figure 5. Stress analysis a) using quadrangular mesh with 4 nodes; b) using triangular mesh with 3 nodes.

3.2 Remodelling analysis

The analyses presented in this chapter are performed over a 2-dimensional beam with length (L) of 0.6 m and width (W) of 0.2 m constrained along the width on the left side and with a force (F) of 3 kN in the centre of the right side with direction along the width. For the beam material was chosen the EN AW-6060 T66 aluminium alloy with Young's modulus (E) of 70 GPa, Poisson's ratio (ν) of 0.3 and Yield strength (σ_{ced}) of 150 MPa [4]. A quadrangular mesh with 4 nodes, similar to the one presented in Figure 2 a), is used, with divisions as shown in Table 2. For the BIRA analyses, the Belinha material law [1] and the effective Von Mises stress optimal criterion are used. The maximum times a point can remodel is considered 2, and the stop criterion is 38% the initial mass (m). The selected parameters are: growth rate (α) = 0 and decrease ratio (β) = 0.01; 0.02; 0.05. Thus, this means

the mass of the beam will only be decreased. The final results are selected when a final mass around 45% is achieved. The results are then compared with the solutions presented in the Figure 6 by M.P. Bendsøe [5]. The analysis used paired with BIRA the methods: FEM, RPIM and NNRPIM.

Table 2. Divisions along x and y, respective number of nodes and designation of meshes

x-axis divisions	y-axis divisions	number of nodes	designation
60	20	1281	M60x20
90	30	2821	M90x30
120	40	4961	M120x40

Figure 6. Remodelling results presented by M.P. Bendsøe [5].

The best results for each method were obtained when using decrease ratio (β) = 0.05 and using the M120x40 mesh with results shown in Figure 7. All the methods used obtained results similar to the ones presented by M.P. Bendsøe [5], showing some difference between them. The FEM method presented more a defined structure than the meshless methods that shown some structures with lower density close to the centre of the beam.

Figure 7. Remodelling analyses results.

3.3 Component remodelling

For the analysis of the component, first it was designed an initial model, as shown in Figure 8 with open space on left leaving room for the wheel and material on right providing space for possible remodelling. Two loads, L1 and L2 are applied to the structure with L1 = 2000 N and L2 = 200 N. The mesh used is the triangular mesh with 3 nodes size equal to 8 mm and the material used in the component was the same material used in the remodelling analysis, the EN AW-6060 T66 aluminium alloy.

The best result was achieved by using NNRPIM paired with BIRA, and it is shown in Figure 9(a). It achieved a stiffness (k) of 10.71 kN/mm calculated through Equation (33). This result was then compared with the original model, Figure 9(b), with k = 4.20 kN/mm. Although with higher stiffness, the obtained model has higher mass than the original one, but when comparing the mass normalized stiffness, the obtained model 438.97 N/mm/kg

was still higher than the original model 205.86 N/mm/kg. This shows an improvement in the original model structure.

$$k = \frac{F}{\delta} \quad (32)$$

Figure 8. Initial model design

Figure 9. (a) Obtained model design; (b) Original model design.

4 Conclusions

This work showed new possibilities for the design of structures using methods that differ from the usual FEM, which can provide different and possibly better solutions. The meshless methods RPIM and NNRPIM proved to be very capable numerical methods, obtaining better results for most of the analysis in the Cantilever Beam benchmark problem. BIRA showed good results for the remodelling analysis benchmark problem with solutions similar to the intended ones. Lastly, the component remodelling can be considered a success, obtaining a model design with a mass normalized stiffness more than 2 times higher than the original model.

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2.10 Structural optimization of the Perseverance rover's suspension system using a meshless method approach

Authors:

João Silva

Daniel Rodrigues

Ana Pais

Jorge Belinha

Structural optimization of the Perseverance rover's suspension system using a meshless method approach

João Silva^{1,4}, Daniel Rodrigues^{1,2,4}, Ana Pais^{3,4}, and Jorge Belinha^{1,4}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, ISEP, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Aveiro, Portugal

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, FEUP, University of Porto, Portugal

⁴ Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering

Abstract. This work optimizes the Perseverance rover's suspension to decrease von Mises stresses and increase stiffness, using the Bi-directional Evolutionary Structural Optimization (BESO) method with structural analysis via the Natural Neighbour Radial Point Interpolation Method (NNRPIM). Validation with a cantilever beam test confirmed the method's accuracy. Applied to the rover suspension, the approach produced a design similar to the original but geometrically more complex, with lower von Mises stresses and significantly higher normalized stiffness, demonstrating its potential for efficient aerospace component design.

Keywords: Meshless methods, Perseverance rover, Structural optimization

1 Introduction

This work focuses on the structural optimization of NASA's Perseverance rover suspension system using the Natural Neighbour Radial Point Interpolation Method (NNRPIM). NNRPIM is a meshless numerical method in which the geometry is represented by scattered nodes, and shape functions are constructed through natural neighbour interpolation. Unlike traditional mesh-based methods, it eliminates issues related to mesh distortion, making it particularly suitable for complex geometries and large deformations. In this study, NNRPIM was employed in combination with the Bi-directional Evolutionary Structural Optimization (BESO) optimization algorithm to enhance the rover's suspension design, aiming to reduce von Mises stresses and significantly increase normalized stiffness, thereby improving structural performance for demanding extraterrestrial environments.

2 Numerical methods

When solids and structures are subjected to forces, stresses arise, producing strains that cause deformation or internal displacement. Solid and structural mechanics study the relationship between stress, strain, and resulting displacements under specific boundary conditions. In computational structural mechanics, these relationships are computed numerically using discretization methods.

Meshless methods, unlike the Finite Element Method (FEM), discretize the domain using nodes that can be irregularly distributed, enabling the analysis of complex geometries. Accuracy depends on nodal density, with higher density giving more precise results. Examples include: Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM), Element-Free Galerkin (EFGM), Meshless Local Petrov-Galerkin (MLPG), the Natural Neighbour Radial Point Interpolation Method (NNRPIM), and Reproducing Kernel Particle Method (RKPM).

2.1 RPIM

The RPIM solves differential and integral equations by combining radial basis functions (RBFs) with polynomial basis functions to address singularity issues in polynomial-based PIM. Although polynomial augmentation is not essential, relying solely on RBFs can cause instability and ill-conditioned systems, requiring regularization [3].

Recent advances include weighted nodal RPIM for 2D linear elasticity, normalized RBFs for nonlinear thermal buckling in graded plates, and adaptations for nonlinear coupled Burger's equations using spectral methods. Simplified RPIM versions improve efficiency in approaches like MLPG for bending plate analysis under Reissner's theory. RPIM offers high accuracy and computational efficiency, particularly in nonlinear analyses when combined with iterative methods such as Newton-Raphson [3]. Regarding the nodal connectivity for the RPIM, influence domains must overlap around each node to create the necessary connections. For accuracy, each domain should typically include 9 to 16 nodes [1]. Their size is based on a reference dimension d , obtained from the average node spacing h and a scaling factor k between 1.5 and 2.5. These influence domains can be either rectangular, selecting nodes within a defined width and height, or circular, selecting nodes within a specified radius, present from Figure a) to Figure c). In both cases, domains near boundaries may contain fewer neighbouring nodes, which can reduce accuracy [1].

Figure 1. a) Fixed rectangular shape domain. b) Fixed circular domain. c) Flexible circular domain [1].

Regarding the numerical integration of the RPIM, the Gauss-Legendre method is applied by dividing the solid domain into equal parts using a regular grid, where integration points are positioned according to the Gauss-Legendre quadrature rule [1]. Each quadrilateral cell is transformed into an isoparametric square (Figure 1a), within which quadrature points are distributed and their Cartesian coordinates determined through isoparametric interpolation. Figure 1b) illustrates a 2x2 quadrature arrangement in such a square. The integration weight for each point is obtained by multiplying its isoparametric weight by the inverse of the Jacobian determinant for that cell, as shown in Figure 1c). When the grid aligns perfectly with the domain, no adjustments are required, and integration points located outside the solid domain are excluded. This procedure enables the numerical integration of a function $F(x)$ over the domain Ω , as presented in eq. (1) [1].

$$\int_{\Omega} F(x) d\Omega = \sum_{i=1}^{n_q} w_i F(x_i) \tag{1}$$

Figure 1. a) First quadrilateral from the grid cell. b) isoparametric square shape from the initial quadrilateral. c) Return to the initial shape [1]

2.2 NNRPIM

The creation of interpolating shape functions has been a central topic in computational mechanics, driving important progress in meshless methods. One notable advancement is the NNRPIM, which merges the natural neighbour connectivity from the Natural Element Method (NEM) with the interpolation technique of RPIM. Being fully meshless, NNRPIM only requires the Cartesian coordinates of the nodal distribution to determine the positions and weights of the background integration points and to define nodal connectivity through the natural neighbour principle. This combination significantly improves result accuracy and increases efficiency, making NNRPIM a highly effective tool within meshless methodologies [4].

The NNRPIM defines integration points and nodal connectivity using the natural neighbour concept, based on the Voronoï diagram of the nodal discretization [4]. For a 2D domain Ω with N nodes, the Voronoï diagram divides Ω into convex, non-overlapping cells V_i , each containing points closer to node x_i than to any other, ensuring $\Omega = \sum_{i=1}^N V_i$. Natural neighbours of x_i are nodes whose Voronoï cells share an edge with V_i , forming the basis for automatic connectivity. Instead of traditional influence domains, NNRPIM uses “influence cells”: first-degree cells include x_i and its natural neighbours, while second-degree cells include x_i , its first neighbours, and their neighbours. This eliminates the need for searching nearby nodes, as connectivity comes directly from the Voronoï diagram. The duality between the Voronoï diagram and the Delaunay triangulation is used to generate background integration meshes, improving efficiency and accuracy, allowing for a robust, fully meshless analysis [1].

Regarding numerical integration, the process begins by constructing Voronoï cells for each node in a 2D domain $X \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ [24]. In irregular nodal distributions, these cells are polygonal and subdivided into quadrilateral sub-cells using the midpoints between the central node and its natural neighbours. In regular nodal distributions, the Voronoï cells are square and divided into triangular sub-cells following a similar midpoint procedure. The cell area A_{V_i} is then obtained by summing the areas of its sub-cells, A_{S_n} , as expressed in eq.(2).

$$A_{V_i} = \sum_{n=1}^n A_{S_n}, \quad \forall A_{S_n} \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

An initial integration method assigns one integration point at the geometric centre of each sub-cell, with coordinates calculated accordingly and weights equal to the sub-cell area (Figure 2). A more refined approach further subdivides each sub-cell into smaller quadrilaterals or triangles by calculating edge midpoints and shape centres, as illustrated in Figure 3. The Gauss-Legendre quadrature is then applied to these smaller elements, allowing $k \times k$ integration points per sub-cell, as in the example where each contains 9 points [1].

Figure 2. Cell shapes with integration points. a) triangular. b) quadrilateral [1].

Figure 3. Gauss-Legendre integration for a) quadrilateral and b) triangular cells with 9 points each.

2.3 Shape functions

Both RPIM and NNRPIM construct their shape functions using the radial point interpolation technique. In a 2D domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ with N nodes, the field function $u(\mathbf{x}_I)$ at an integration point \mathbf{x}_I is interpolated as eq.(3)

$$u(\mathbf{x}_I) = \left\{ \mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T, \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \right\} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_I)$ is the radial basis function (RBF), $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_I)$, is the polynomial basis, and \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} are their respective coefficients, J. Belinha [2]. The polynomial basis improves stability and robustness. The Multiquadric RBF (MQ-RBF) was later refined by Belinha [2] to optimise the Kronecker delta property, setting optimal parameters to $c = 10^{-4}$ and $p = 1 - 10^{-4}$, enhancing accuracy in complex 2D fields. The refined MQ-RBF is given by eq.(4).

$$r_j(\mathbf{x}_i) = r_{ij} = \left(d_{ij}^2 + (\hat{w}_I \cdot c)^2 \right)^p = \left(\left(\sqrt{(x_j - x_i)^2 + (y_j - y_i)^2} \right)^2 + (\hat{w}_I \cdot c)^2 \right)^p \quad (4)$$

To ensure a unique solution, RPIM satisfies the condition presented in eq.(5).

$$\sum_{i=1}^n p_j(\mathbf{x}_i) a_i(\mathbf{x}_i) = 0 \quad (5)$$

Combining eq.(3) and (5) leads to the matrix form shown in eq.(6):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{P} \\ \mathbf{P}^T & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{G} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_s \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{R} is symmetric, making the full matrix symmetric as well. When solving eq.(6) it is possible to obtain eq.(7), presented below:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{G}^{-1} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_s \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Finally, substituting into eq.(3) gives the interpolation for \mathbf{x}_I presented in eq.(8):

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \left\{ \mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T, \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \right\} \cdot \mathbf{G}^{-1} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_s \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} = \left\{ \Phi(\mathbf{x}_I), \Psi(\mathbf{x}_I) \right\} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_s \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The interpolation function $\Phi(\mathbf{x}_I)$ is thus expressed as eq.(9):

$$\Phi_{\xi}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \left\{ \mathbf{r}(\mathbf{x}_I)_{\xi}^T, \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}_I)_{\xi}^T \right\} \cdot \mathbf{G}^{-1} \quad (9)$$

These functions preserve the partition of unity and satisfy the Kronecker delta property, allowing easy application of boundary conditions [2].

2.4 System of equations

The global system of equations for elasticity problems in both RPIM and NNRPIM is based on the virtual work principle, which states that the internal virtual work must equal the external virtual work [4]. The problem's domain Ω includes the volume and its boundaries, divided into Γ_t (natural boundary conditions) and Γ_u (essential boundary conditions), with possible body forces \mathbf{b} acting over Ω (eq.(10)).

For a two-dimensional problem, displacements $\{u, v\}$ are interpolated using the shape functions (eq.(11)), which are then used to compute strains via the strain-displacement matrix $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I)$ (eq.(12)). Stresses follow from Hooke's law seen in eq.(13), with the constitutive matrix $\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I)$ defined for the material properties presented in eq.(14). Substituting these into the virtual work principle yields the final formulation, eq.(15), representing the balance between internal forces, body forces, and boundary tractions.

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_t} \delta \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I)^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \cdot d\Gamma \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{Bmatrix} u(\mathbf{x}_I) \\ v(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_1(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 & \cdots & \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_I) & 0 \\ 0 & \phi_1(\mathbf{x}_I) & \cdots & 0 & \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_I) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ v_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \\ v_n \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ v_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \\ v_n \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u} \quad (12)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}_I) = \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{c} = \frac{E_2}{1 - \alpha_1 \cdot \nu_{21}^2} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_1 \cdot \nu_{12} & 0 \\ \alpha_1 \cdot \nu_{12} & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_2 \cdot (1 - \alpha_1 \cdot \nu_{21}^2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta (\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u})^T \cdot (\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u}) \cdot d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta (\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u})^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_t} \delta (\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u})^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{t}} \cdot d\Gamma \quad (15)$$

3 Results

To validate the effectiveness of the NNRPIM method utilized in the structural optimization process, a preliminary study is required. Therefore, a benchmark example is submitted to a structural optimization process to understand if the result resembles the benchmark. Then, it is possible to effectively optimize the suspension system of the rover with the best suited method.

3.1 Benchmark analysis

The optimization study considers a two-dimensional beam measuring 2400×400 mm, modeled only for half of its length to simplify the analysis and reduce computational time. The beam is restrained at the left end in the y direction and at the right end only in the x direction, allowing vertical displacement and rotation. A vertical load of 20 kN is applied to the top surface, and the material used is aluminum. For the NNRPIM method, the analysis

was carried out considering second-degree neighbors, with full integration and parameters $c=0.0001$ and $p=0.9999$. The structure was obtained using the Bi-directional Evolutionary Structural Optimization (BESO) method. This approach works by iteratively adjusting the material distribution based on the stress field: regions with higher stress are reinforced, while areas with lower stress are penalized to simulate material removal. After each iteration, the structure is re-analysed, and the process repeats until a stable and efficient layout is achieved, concentrating material only in the most critical regions. As shown in Figure 4, the result obtained with the NNRPIM method closely matches the benchmark example, confirming the effectiveness of the BESO method in generating optimized structures when combined with the NNRPIM approach.

Figure 4. a) Benchmark example result; b) structural optimization with NNRPIM method result.

3.2 Rover structural optimization

The structural optimization began with a simplified 2D rectangular model created in FEMAP to represent the initial geometry of the rocker bogie suspension system. Measuring 3 m in length and 1 m in height, this baseline geometry served as a neutral starting point, allowing clear observation of material redistribution under applied loads and boundary conditions. In the rectangular domain, certain non-removable areas were defined to preserve critical mechanical connections, such as the interfaces with the rover's wheels. These regions, modelled as small rectangular pads, remained unchanged throughout the optimization process to maintain the structure's functionality. The material used in the simulations was Ti-6Al-4V STA, with a constant density of 4.43 g/cm^3 assigned to the non-removable zones to prevent any material removal or redistribution in these critical areas. This material features a yield strength of 1035 MPa and a tensile strength of 1100 MPa, ensuring high mechanical performance in these structurally essential regions. Despite the present study using the RPIM and the NNRPIM, the latter yields better final geometries. Thus, the results presented here only concern the NNRPIM mode.

The maximum von Mises stress in the optimized structure was 3.47 MPa , presented in Figure 6a), lower than both the yield strength of the material and the maximum observed stress in the original structure, which was 14.0 MPa , shown in Figure 5a). The optimized model also resulted in a stiffer and more complex design, confirming the superior performance and the effectiveness of the meshfree NNRPIM method in creating optimized and structurally efficient structures. By dividing the force by the displacement at the point of application, it is possible to determine the stiffness of the structure. However, since the mass of the optimized structure differs from that of the original structure, it is necessary to calculate the normalized stiffness by dividing the previously determined stiffness by the structure's mass. This allows for a more effective and meaningful comparison between structures. As can be seen in Table 1, the optimized structure exhibits a higher normalized stiffness than the original design. This is possible because the optimized structure has a more robust and complex structural arrangement.

Figure 5. a) Original structure Von Mises stress $V2$ ($\sigma_{ef \text{ máx}} = 14.0 \text{ MPa}$; $\sigma_{ef \text{ mín}} = 0.0248 \text{ MPa}$); b) Original structure displacements ($u_{\text{máx}} = 0$; $u_{\text{mín}} = -3.58 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}$).

Figure 6. a) Optimized structure Von Mises Stress $\sigma_{ef\ max} = 3.47\ MPa$; $\sigma_{ef\ min} = 0.0201\ MPa$; b) Displacements ($u_{max} = 0$; $u_{min} = -2.40 \times 10^{-5}\ m$).

Table 1. Normalized stiffness comparison.

Normalized Stiffness [N/mm/kg]	
Original structure	Optimized structure
67.66	1992.92

4 Conclusions

The results of this study demonstrate that the NRPIM method was successfully validated, confirming its reliability and accuracy for structural analysis applications. Likewise, the BESO method proved to be a robust and effective tool for structural optimization, as evidenced by its ability to generate a design closely resembling the established benchmark example. The rover suspension system was successfully optimized using the NRPIM approach, further reinforcing the efficiency and versatility of this method when applied to complex engineering problems. The optimization process yielded a more intricate and refined structural configuration, which contributed to a noticeable reduction in von Mises stresses compared to the original design, as well as stresses relative to the material yield strength, thereby enhancing the overall safety margin of the structure. Furthermore, the optimized design achieved a significant increase in normalized stiffness. Collectively, these improvements underline the potential of combining NRPIM and BESO as a powerful framework for high-performance structural design and optimization in demanding engineering applications.

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